

**THERMO ACOUSTIC STUDIES ON METHOXY AND
HYDROXY BENZOATE LIQUID MIXTURES**

A

Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW IN PHYSICS

by

Dr AYACHITHULA. NAGARJUNA

Roll No: 22SUPDR043

Under the supervision of

Dr B.M PRAVEEN

Director, Research and Innovation Council

Srinivas University

Mukka, Mangaluru – 574146

**DEPARTMENT OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING
AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, KARNATAKA, INDIA**

DECEMBER 2023

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Signature :

Name : Dr AYACHITHULA .NAGARJUNA

Roll No : **22SUPDR043**

Place: :MUKKA

Date:

Srinivas Nagar, – 574 146, Mangalore, Phone: 0824-2477456

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.

Web: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Certificate

This is to certify that entitled (**Thermo acoustic studies on methoxy and hydroxy benzoate liquid mixtures**) submitted by **Dr AYACHITHULA NAGARJUNA** to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, Mangalore** for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a bonafede record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

Place: Mukka

Date : /_____/ _____

Supervisor

Dr. B.M PRAVEEN

Director, Research and Innovation Council

Srinivas University

Mukka, Mangaluru -574146

I acknowledge and wish to express my humble sense of gratitude and profound thanks to my research supervisor Dr. B.M Praveen, Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University for his guidance, Specially for the constant encouragement, support, academic freedom, flexibility, tolerance and for making this research possible.

I am wholeheartedly grateful to Dr. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, President, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for encouraging me by providing all facilities to carry out this work. I wish to express my sincere thanks to Dr. P. Srinivas Rao, Vice-president, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for their support. I am thankful to Prof. Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal, Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, for inspiring and motivating me in all aspects. I am thankful to Dr. Praveen B M, Director at Srinivas University for providing all facilities to carry out this work.

I wish to express my sincere thanks and gratitude to Dr V.N Mani, Scientist-E, Principal Investigator- DRDO/DST Projects, HOD of E&IT, C-MET (Govt. of. India), Hyderabad, Telangana, Dr Ch. S.L.N Sridhar, Department of Physics and Vice- Principal, VBIT, Hyderabad , Dr. K. Sarangam, Professor, Department of IT, CVR Engineering college, Hyderabad, Dr. Shaik. Babu, Department of Physics, KLEF (Deemed to be university), A.P, Principal and faculty of Physics, Teegala Krishna Reddy engineering college, Hyderabad for their extended support and encouragement during my research work.

I am happy to mention my research friends Dr. K.V.S.N Raju, Dr. N. Kotilingaiah, Dr M. Dasaratham and Dr C. Annapalagan for their cooperation and support with whom I shared lively academic sessions and experimental work during my research work.

My sincere indebtedness to my loving parents Sri A. Kumara Swamy and Smt. A.Vijaya Mitra for their whole hearted blessings. I credit my love and affection to my wife Mrs A.Radha Madhavi and my sons A.Datta Aasrith and A.Bhanu Anvith, for their patience and cooperation in all my deeds, without their moral support this dissertation would not be materialized. I wish to express my sincere thanks to Almighty for upgrade my thinking ability in crucial timings also their continuous blessings and loving care to sustain my goal.

(Dr AYACHITHULA. NAGARJUNA)

DEDICATED TO

LORD SRI VENKATESWARA SWAMY

TIRUPATHI, AP, INDIA

CONTENTS

Sl. No	List of Contents	Page No.
1.	Title Page	i
	Declaration	ii
	Research Supervisor Certificate	iii
	Acknowledgement	iv-v
	Dedication	vi
2.	Contents	vii-xi
3.	Synopsis	13-16
4.	Chapter 1 Introduction	17-27
5.	Chapter 2 Experimental Section	28-41
6.	Chapter 3 Comparative study of binary liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoate acid and amides	42-59
7.	Chapter 4 Study of intermolecular interactions in ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate liquid mixture	60-78
8.	Chapter 5 Speed of sound and Viscosity theories of benzoate liquid mixtures	79-91
9.	Future plan of work	92
10.	Paper Publications	

List of Symbols

S. No	Physical quantity/ chemical name	Symbol
1	p-Methoxy benzoic acid	p-MBA
2	Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate	E-4-HB
3	Formamide	FA
4	N-Methyl formamide	NMF
5	Dimethyl formamide	DMF
6	Aniline	AN
7	O-Chloro aniline	OCA
8	O-Toluidine	OT
9	Density	ρ
10	Viscosity	η
11	Speed of sound	U
12	Mole fraction	x_1
13	Isentropic compressibility	K_s
14	Acoustic impedance	Z
15	Molar volume	V_m
16	Free length	L_f
17	Relaxation time	τ
18	Surface tension	γ
19	Excess isentropic compressibility	K_s^E
20	Excess molar volume	V_m^E
21	Excess free length	L_f^E

22	Excess acoustic impedance	Z^E
23	Excess Surface tension	γ^E
24	Redlich-Kister polynomial equation	R-K
25	Parameters of R-K equation	A_i
26	Average percentage error	APE
27	standard deviation	σ
28	Nomoto's relation for speed of sound	U_{NOM}
29	Van Dael and Vangeel relation for speed of sound	U_{VDV}
30	Junjie's relation for speed of sound	U_{JM}
31	Ideal mixture relation for speed of sound	U_{IMR}
32	Rao's relation for speed of sound	U_{R}
33	Interaction parameter	I.P
34	Partial molar volumes	$\bar{V}_{m,1}, \bar{V}_{m,2}$
35	Partial molar volumes at Infinite dilution	$\bar{V}_{m,1}^\infty, \bar{V}_{m,2}^\infty$
36	Excess partial molar volume at infinite dilution	$\bar{V}_{m,1}^{E,\infty}, \bar{V}_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$
37	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy	FTIR

List of Publications with Srinivas university affiliation

1. *Speed of Sound Studies of Ethyl-4-hydroxy Benzoate with Formamide at different temperatures
Dr A. Nagarjuna, Dr K.V.S. N Raju, Dr Shaik.S Begum, Dr B.M Praveen
International Journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research,
12(02) 365- 368 (2023) DOI: [10.48047/IJIEMR/V12/ISSUE 02/57](https://doi.org/10.48047/IJIEMR/V12/ISSUE 02/57)
2. *Comparative study of binary liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoate acid and amides
A. Nagarjuna K.V.S.N Raju, N. Kotilingaiah, B M Praveen
European Chemical Bulletin, 12 (SI6), 3395 – 3407 (2023)
DOI: [10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.302](https://doi.org/10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.302)
3. Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) metal compounds of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde: Synthesis, crystalline structure, pharmacological assessment, and molecular docking research are all part of the process
N. Kotilingaiah, A.Nagarjuna B M Praveen, B. Srinu, K. Sateesh
European Chemical Bulletin, 12 (SI6), 6808-6821 (2023)
DOI: [10.48047/ecb/2023.12.si4.609](https://doi.org/10.48047/ecb/2023.12.si4.609)
4. Spectroscopic and textural analysis of glucose dispersed fundamental nematic liquid crystals
K.V.S.N Raju, SK Salma Begum, A. Nagarjuna, B M Praveen
Brazilian Journal of Physics, 53, 89 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13538-023-01313-w>
5. * Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures
A.Nagarjuna, G. Sunitha, K.V.S.N Raju, B M Praveen
Accepted in Taylor and Francis journal proceedings
6. *Speed of sound and Viscosity theories of benzoate liquid mixtures

7. *Study of intermolecular interactions in Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate liquid mixture

A.Nagarjuna, K.V.S.N Raju, BM Praveen

Material science and technology, 22(10), 202

DOI:10.10543/f0299.2023.41742

*** Form the part of the thesis.**

Paper/Poster Presentations in Conferences

1. Speed of Sound Studies of Ethyl-4-hydroxy Benzoate with Formamide at different temperatures
Dr A. Nagarjuna, Dr K.V.S. N Raju, Dr Shaik. S Begum, Dr B.M Praveen
International Conference on “Emerging Trends in Science, Engineering and Technology (ICESET-2023)” from 20th to 22nd February 2023 was organized by Dept. of Electronics Andhra Loyola College (Autonomous), Vijayawada-520 008, AP, India
2. Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures
Dr A. Nagarjuna, Dr K.V.S. N Raju, G. Sunitha, Dr B.M Praveen
International Conference on ICDTCCS-2022 was organized by Teegala Krishna reddy Engineering College (Autonomous), Meerpet-500097, Hyderabad, India
3. National level Guest lecture on " Nano science and Technology for Better Future" conducted on 30th June 2023 jointly organized by Department of Physics, KLEF, Guntur, AP in association with Materials Research Society of India (MRSI), India.

**THERMO ACOUSTIC STUDIES ON METHOXY AND HYDROXY
BENZOATE LIQUID MIXTURES**

SYNOPSIS

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW IN PHYSICS

by

Dr AYACHITHULA. NAGARJUNA

Roll No: 22SUPDR043

Under the supervision of

Dr B.M PRAVEEN

Director, Research and Innovation Council

Srinivas University

Mukka, Mangaluru - 574146

DEPARTMENT OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

AND TECHNOLOGY

MUKKA, KARNATAKA, INDIA

November 2023

SYNOPSIS

To study the properties of twofold/ternary fluid blends finds direct applications in chemical, biochemical, medicine industries and defence. Many engineering problems require qualitative data depends on the Speed of sound, viscosity and density of fluid blends hence it has been a subject of active interest during the recent years. Estimation of Speed of sound are very frequently used in chemical and food processing, pharmaceuticals, material testing, underwater ranging and cleaning, and also employed in mechanical properties of materials.

The physicochemical nature and strength of interplays in blends, over whole composition or temperatures, can be obtained from thermo-acoustic and excess thermo acoustic parameters. Study of thermo-acoustic parameters of mix furnish important information concerning intermolecular (both homo and hetro) interactions also the consequential structural rearrangement of molecules in solution. These digresses parameters have been fitted to Redlich–Kister polynomial equation to test the non ideality behaviour in the mixture.

Benzoic acid arises natch in many plants and serves as a median in the biosynthesis of many secondary metabolites. The esters and salts of benzoic acid are called as benzoates. Benzoic acid is a crucial precursor for the industrial synthesis of many other fabrics in medical field. In this present work explicate the molecular interactions of E-4-HB and p-MBA mix at different temperatures.

Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate(E-4-HB) / Ethyl paraben is an ethyl ester ensure from the formal cogitation of p-hydroxy benzoic acid with ethanol; it acts as an antimicrobial food preservative, an antifungal agent, a plant metabolite and a phytoestrogen. Ethyl paraben is found in alcoholic beverages like red wine, white wine and sake.

p- Methoxy benzoic acid (p-MBA) is the sole source of carbon and energy for growth in the cultures of Nocardia. p-MBA was used in oxidation and reduction of cyto chromic in solution through different self-assembled mono layers on gold electrodes using cyclic voltammetry. Metabolite of aniracetam and cognition enhancer that mimics its anxiolytic actions. It is also an inhibitor of tyrosine's. p- Methoxy benzoic acid is a phenolic acid found in anis-seed and a common food spice. In view of the above importance of two-fold fluid blends in various pharmaceutical industries.

I have chosen such studies in the various Benzoate fluid systems for my research work. The quality of sub-atomic associations present between the parts of a twofold fluid blend can be clarified by watching deviations in the overabundance parameters. The overabundance parameter esteems rely upon the shape and size of the segments, temperature and their piece. The estimations of overabundance thermo acoustic capacities are impacted by physical, substance and auxiliary commitments of the atoms.

The fluid systems considered for the present work are:

1) Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate (E-4-HB) with amines at T= 303.15 K -313.15 K

a) E-4-HB + Aniline

b) E-4-HB + O-Chloroaniline

c) E-4-HB + O-Toluidine

2) p-Methoxy benzoic acid (p-MBA) with amides at T=303.15K - 313.15 K

a) p-MBA + Formamide

b) p-MBA + D-Methyl formamide

c) p-MBA + N-Methyl formamide

In the present investigation, the Speed of sound (U), Viscosity (η) and density(ρ) are resolved tentatively for the sterling fluids and their fluid blends over the whole organization run at various temperatures. Utilizing these tentatively decided qualities different thermo-acoustic parameters like isentropic compressibility (K_s), molar volume (V_m), free length (L_f), surface tension(γ), relaxation time (τ) and acoustic impedance (Z) aggregate of 6 parameters were determined. Notwithstanding these counts overabundance parameters of thermo acoustic and transport properties were resolved from the above qualities. The estimations of these overabundance capacities have been fitted by the strategy for nonlinear least squares to R-K type polynomial condition and the comparing standard deviations are determined. The relevance check has been accomplished for various hypothetical frameworks for the deliberate viscosity esteems and speed of sound qualities for all the fluid blends under scrutiny and at prone temperatures. The outcomes acquired are arranged and investigated to clarify the atomic communications between particles of various segments in the paired fluid blends.

The fundamental aim of these examinations is,

- 1) To contemplate atomic connections in the light of varieties of various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters
- 2) To look at the Speed of sound (U), Viscosity(η) and density(ρ) qualities estimated using various speculations with experimental values and to find the suitability of these hypotheses to the fluid mixes viable.
- 3) To look at the acoustic parameters decided using distinctive exact relations with exploratory data and to check important information concerning intermolecular interactions also the consequential structural rearrangement present in the liquid mixture.

- 4) These digresses parameters have been fitted to Redlich–Kister polynomial equation to test the non ideality behaviour in the mixture.
- 5) To look at the speed of sound and viscosity theories decided using distinctive exact relations with exploratory data and to check proper experimental connection to the fluid blends researched.
- 6) FT-IR spectroscopic measurements of these blends were also carried out to analyse the hydrogen bond formation in between unlike molecules in the fluid blend

CHAPTER- 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1

The investigation of ultrasonic waves and the distinction they make in the properties of the material is called ultrasonics; it is about the sound waves whose frequencies are more than around 20 KHz which means they are over the maximum furthest reaches of the perceptible range for people. The term sonic is related to ultrasound rushes of high frequencies.

Hyper sound also called as praeter sound or smaller scale sound is the sound of frequencies more than 10^{13} hertz. An ultrasonic wave being transmitted through a substance is of two sorts. Every benevolent causes a specific improvement in the parts of medium and the manners in which that these segments seek after as they move considering the wave are called their circles. If these circles are parallel to the line of engendering, the waves are called longitudinal waves. If these circles are opposite to the line of engendering, the waves are called transverse waves or shear waves. Since liquids don't have shear adaptability, transverse waves can't exist in liquids. Rectilinear spread is a trademark appeared by ultrasonic waves because of their short wavelength^{1, 2}.

Rectilinear proliferation and the short wavelength of the ultrasonic waves is the purpose behind use of these waves much of the time. Ultrasonic waves with low plenty fullness have been used by a few workers³⁻⁶ to think about the basic and physic-concoction conduct of unadulterated liquids and their liquid mixes.

The examination of the spread conduct of ultrasonic waves in solids, liquids, liquid mixes, electrolyte arrangements, suspensions, polymers, chemicals, etc is as of now entrenched as a convincing technique for taking a gander at certain physical properties of materials or medium,

atomic connections etc. The examination of atomic co-operations and the varieties in these communications as a result of basic changes have been finished by various preliminary systems, for instance, Infrared Spectroscopy technique⁷, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance⁸ and Raman spectra⁹.

The total comprehension of the idea of intermolecular and intra-molecular association may not be conceivable by any single strategy. Ultrasonic techniques have the additional bit of advantage of being less cost with effectiveness compared to different strategies. So various workers have made the investigation through ultrasonic method.^{10,11}

Examinations on sound speed, thickness, consistency, acoustic, thermo physical, abundance thermoacoustic parameters and their deviations in liquid mixes are the subject of various assessments in the progressing years^{12,13}. These assessments on different liquid mixes uncover explicit connections between the atoms of the segment liquids.

It was accounted by a few workers^{4,9} that the nearness of complex course of action can be explained successfully by abundance parameters, for instance, overabundance molar volume (V_m^E), overabundance isentropic compressibility (K_s^E), abundance free length (L_f^E) etc. The positive estimations of V_m^E and negative estimations of K_s^E show solid connections in liquid mixes exhibiting the likelihood of complex formation. This happens in light of the advancement of discrete social occasions of atoms masterminded into explicit geometric structures which are brought about by the state of particles just as by the common co-operations occurring between them.

Concurrent assurance of speed of sound, thickness and consistency of liquid mixes empower us to get information about their molar volume (V_m), compressibility (K_s), free length (L_f), surface tension (χ), relaxation time (τ), acoustic impedance (Z) and changes in their

properties.

Complex arrangements, development of hydrogen bond, dipole – dipole, dipole-initiated dipole associations in liquid mixes and their effect in physical and substance properties of the concoction have gotten a lot of consideration as of late. Thickness and consistency of liquid mixes are required in most building calculations where liquid progression of mix is a huge factor.

Knowledge of the dependence of densities and viscosities of fluid blends on structure is of incredible enthusiasm from theoretical point of view since it might prompt better comprehension of fundamental behavior of fluid blends. Likewise it is basic in the design process including chemical separations, equipment design, solution theory, heat transfer, fluid flow and molecular dynamics.

Viscosity information is helpful for testing hypotheses and empirical relations, for example, Grunberg and Nissan¹⁴, Hind and Ubbelohde¹⁵, Katti and Chaudhri¹⁶, Wiki¹⁷, Kendall-Monroe, Arrhenius¹⁷ and so forth for fluid blends.

In chemical industry there exists a need for reliable thermodynamic information of fluid blends, blended solvents compared to pure fluids. It has practical applications in numerous chemical and industrial processes. Their excess thermodynamic parameters empower us to comprehend the physico-chemical properties in a continuous manner.

The excess thermodynamic parameter indicated by superscript E is characterized as the variation between the thermodynamic function of blending of a real blend and the value relating to the ideal blend at the same temperature, pressure and composition. For an ideal fluid blend all excess functions are zero. Excess parameters may be positive or negative, their sign and size indicate the deviation from ideality. Thermodynamic functions of fluid blend and excess functions become identical in regard of quantities where entropy does not appear. Deviations from perfect

behavior for different properties like molar volume, isentropic compressibility, viscosity and so forth have been widely utilized to explain the structural variations and molecular interactions of fluid blends.

Several theories were proposed to study about the speed of sound in binary and ternary blends. They are Junjie's observational relation,¹⁸ Nomoto's equation,¹⁹ Ideal mixture relations²⁰, Vandael perfect blending relation²¹ and Rao's particular velocity²². Theoretical assessment of speed of sound in paired fluid blends and its correlation to study about inter molecular interactions has been effectively done in recent years^{23,24} utilizing the above theoretical relations.

The fundamental aim of ultrasonic, volumetric and Viscometric examination is,

- 1) To ponder atomic connections in the light of varieties of various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters
- 2) To look at the speed of sound qualities estimated using various speculations with experimental values and to find the suitability of these hypotheses to the liquid mixes viable.
- 3) To ponder sub-atomic connections in the light of deviations of hypothetical velocities from test data.
- 4) To look at the viscosities decided using distinctive exact relations with exploratory data and to check proper experimental connection to the fluid blends researched. Ultrasonics find broad applications in different fields, they are appeared in fig.

1.2 THEORETICAL ASPECTS

The theories utilized in determining different acoustical and thermodynamic parameters and a few empirical conditions utilized in the present investigation are given. The experimentally determined values of speed of sound (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) are utilized to find these following properties.

SOUND VELOCITY (U)

A careful study of literature uncovers that there are bunches of methods for measuring speed of sound^{25,26}. The sound velocity using interferometer technique is considered as reliable and exact. In this instrument, we can find the wavelength (λ) of the ultrasonic wave in fluid and fluid blends. The expression used to find the ultrasonic speed is

$$U = f * \lambda \text{ ms}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Where, f is the frequency of the generator which is utilized to energize the quartz crystal. In

the present examination, a steady frequency (2 MHz) interferometer was utilized and hence forth 'f' value is 2×10^6 hertz.

DENSITY (ρ)

The standardization of specific gravity bottle in its volume is done by considering different temperatures like 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

$$\text{Relative density } (\rho) = (W_{\text{L}} / W_{\text{tw}}) * d_w$$

Where W_{L} , W_{tw} are the weights of liquid and water respectively and d_w is density of water at certain temperature.

VISCOSITY (η)

If t and t_0 are the hours of the stream (of fluid and water) and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the fluid and water separately, at that point the outright consistency of the fluid of fluid arrangement can be determined to utilize the connection.

$$\eta = \left[\frac{\rho t}{\rho_0 t_0} \right] \cdot \eta_0$$

Where η_0 is the thickness of the unadulterated refined water at the exploratory temperature.

1.2.1 THERMO ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS

Different thermo acoustic parameters like, acoustic impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (K_s), molar volume (V_m), free length (L_f), relaxation time (τ), and surface tension (χ) are calculated utilizing the experimentally determined values of U , ρ and η .

$$Z = \rho * U \quad \text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$K_s = \frac{1}{\rho U^2} \quad \text{kg}^{-1} \text{ ms}^{-2} \quad (2)$$

$$V = \frac{M_{\text{eff}}}{\rho} \quad \text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$L_f = K_T \sqrt{K_s} \quad \text{\AA} \quad (4)$$

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \text{ sec} \quad (5)$$

$$\chi = 6.3 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \rho \cdot U^{3/2} \text{ N.m}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

1.2.2 Excess parameters

$$\text{Excess isentropic compressibility } K_s^E = K_s - K_s^{\text{id}} \quad (7)$$

Where K_s^{id} is the ideal isentropic compressibility relation recommended by Benson & Kiyohara ²⁷

$$K_s^{\text{id}} = \sum \phi_i \left\{ K_{s,i}^{o} + \frac{T V_i^{o} (\alpha_i^{o})^2}{C_{p,i}^{o}} \right\} - T (\sum X_i V_i^{o}) \left(\frac{\sum \phi_i \alpha_i^{o,2}}{\sum X_i C_{p,i}^{o}} \right) \quad (8)$$

In which $K_{s,i}^{o}$, V_i^{o} , α_i^{o} , $C_{p,i}^{o}$ are the isentropic compressibility, molar volume, isobaric thermal expansion coefficient and molar isobaric heat capacity of pure component i , T represents temperature and ϕ_i is volume fraction

$$\text{Excess molar volume } V_m^E = X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 / \rho - (X_1 M_1 / \rho_1 + X_2 M_2 / \rho_2) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Excess free length } L_f^E = L_f - K_T (K_s^{\text{id}})^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

K_T is a temperature dependent constant whose value is $K_T = (91.368 + 0.3565 T) \times 10^{-8}$.

$$Z^E = Z - (X_1 Z_1 + X_2 Z_2) \quad (11)$$

$$\chi^E = \chi - (X_1 \chi_1 + X_2 \chi_2) \quad (12)$$

Where V be the molar volume, η and ρ represent obtained viscosity and density for the mixture and X_1 , X_2 represents mole fractions ρ_1 , ρ_2 be the densities η_1 , η_2 represents viscosities V_1 , V_2 represent molar volumes and M_1 , M_2 represent molecular weights of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

ii) The excess values for the above parameters were fitted by the method of nonlinear Least – squares to a Redlich- Kister type polynomial²⁸

$$Y^E = X_1 (1-X_1) (2 X_1 - 1)^{i-1} \quad (13)$$

Where $Y^E = K_s^E, V_m^E, L_f^E$ The values of coefficient A_i were determined by a regression analysis based on the least- squares method

1.2.3 Partial molar volumes

The partial molar volumes for all the binary systems can be calculated using the formulae

$$\bar{V}_{m,1} = V_m^E + V_1^* + X_2 (\partial V_m^E / \partial X)_{P,T} \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{V}_{m,2} = V_m^E + V_2^* + X_1 (\partial V_m^E / \partial X)_{P,T} \quad (15)$$

Where $\bar{V}_{m,1}$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}$ are the partial molar volumes and V_1^* and V_2^* molar volumes of pure compounds.²⁶

The values of infinite dilution of partial and excess partial molar volumes for the binary system ($V_{m,1}^{E,\infty}, V_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$) can be calculated by the following relations.

$$V_{m,1}^{E,\infty} = A_0 + A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + \dots = V_{m,1}^\infty - V_1^* \quad (16)$$

$$V_{m,2}^{E,\infty} = A_0 - A_1 + A_2 - A_3 + \dots = V_{m,2}^\infty - V_2^* \quad (17)$$

Where A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3 are the coefficients obtained from R-K polynomial equation

1.2.4 Speed of sound theories

Nomoto relation $U_{\text{NOM}} = [X_1 R_1 + X_2 R_2 / X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2]$ (18)

Ideal mixture relation $U_{\text{IMR}} = [1/X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2]^{1/2} [X_1/M_1 U_1^2 + X_2/M_2 U_2^2]^{-1/2}$ (19)

Junjie's method $U_{\text{JM}} = [X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2 / (X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2)^{1/2}] [X_1 V_1 / \rho_1 U_1^2 + X_2 V_2 / \rho_2 U_2^2]^{-1/2}$ (20)

Impedance relation $U_{\text{IMP}} = X_1 Z_1 + X_2 Z_2 / X_1 \rho_1 + X_2 \rho_2$ (21)

Vandael & Vangel relation

$$U_{\text{VDV}} \text{ is } [1/X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2] * [1/U_m^2] = [X_1/M_1 U_1^2 + X_2/M_2 U_2^2] \quad (22)$$

Rao's relation $U_R = (R/V)^3$ (23)

Where X_1, X_2 represents mole fractions ρ_1, ρ_2 be the densities U_1, U_2 represents Speed of sounds V_1, V_2 represent molar volumes R_1, R_2 be the molar sound velocities, Z_1, Z_2 represents acoustic impedances and M_1, M_2 represent molecular weights of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

The validity of the theories is checked by applying Chi-square test and by calculating average percentage error, the relations as follows

$$\text{APE} = [(1/n) \sum 100(U_{\text{exp}} - U_{\text{cal}}) / U_{\text{exp}}] \times 100\% \quad (24)$$

$$\text{Chi square } (\chi) = [\sum_{i=1}^n (U_{\text{exp}} - U_{\text{cal}})^2 / U_{\text{cal}}] \quad (25)$$

Where, n - number of data used

1.2.4 Viscosity theories

Hind equation: $\eta = X_1^2 \eta_1 + X_2^2 \eta_2 + 2X_1 X_2 H_{12}$ (26)

Where H_{12} is attributed to unlike pair interactions

Gruenberg-Nissan equation: $\ln \eta_{12} = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 G_{12}$ (27)

Where G_{12} is an approximate measure of the strength of the interaction between the components

Kendall-Monroe equation: $E \eta_m = X_1 X_2 (X_1 \eta_1^{1/3} + X_2 \eta_2^{1/3})$ (28)

E be interaction parameter, η_m mixture viscosity

$$\text{Wiki expression: } \log \eta_m = X_1^2 \log \eta_1 + X_2^2 \log \eta_2 + 2X_1X_2 \log \eta_{12} \quad (29)$$

$$\text{Arrhenius equation: } \log \eta_m = X_1 \log \eta_1 + X_2 \log \eta_2 \quad (30)$$

X_1 and X_2 are the mole fractions and η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of pure component respectively.

The correlating ability of each of the above equations from (20) – (24) was tested by a standard deviation (σ) equation given by $\sigma = [(1/(n-k)\sum 100(\eta_{\text{exp}}-\eta_{\text{cal}})/\eta_{\text{exp}})^2]^{1/2}$ (31)

Where ‘n’ represents the number of data points and k is the number of numerical coefficients

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The fundamental aim of these examinations is,

- 1) To contemplate atomic connections in the light of varieties of various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters
- 2) To look at the Speed of sound (U), Viscosity(η) and density(ρ) qualities estimated using various speculations with experimental values and to find the suitability of these hypotheses to the fluid mixes viable.
- 3) Utilizing these tentatively decided qualities different thermo-acoustic parameters like isentropic compressibility (K_s), molar volume (V_m), free length (L_f), surface tension(γ), relaxation time (τ) and acoustic impedance (Z) aggregate of 6 parameters were determined.
- 4) These digresses parameters have been fitted to Redlich–Kister polynomial equation to test the non ideality behaviour in the mixture.
- 5) To look at the speed of sound and viscosity theories decided using distinctive exact relations with exploratory data and to check proper experimental connection to the fluid blends researched.
- 6) FT-IR spectroscopic measurements of these blends were also carried out to analyse the hydrogen bond formation in between unlike molecules in the fluid blend
- 7) The outcomes acquired are arranged and investigated to clarify the atomic communications between particles of various segments in the paired fluid blends.

REFERENCES

1. Nozdrev V F(1965), *The use of ultrasonics in molecular physics*, pergamon, London
2. Richardson E G (1962), *Ultrasonic Physics*, Elsevier, NewYork.
3. Richardi, J., Krienke, H., & Fries, P. H. (1997). Dielectric constants of liquid formamide, N-methylformamide and dimethylformamide via molecular Ornstein-Zernike theory. *Chemical physics letters*, 273(3-4), 115-121.
4. Ali, A., Nain, A. K., & Kamil, M. (1996). Physico-chemical studies of non-aqueous binary liquid mixtures at various temperatures. *Thermochimica acta*, 274, 209-221.
5. Nigam, P. S., Jagdale, B. S., Sawant, A. B., & Hasan, M. (2001). Ultrasonic studies in mixtures of benzonitrile with some alkanols and toluene.
6. Fort, R. J., & Moore, W. R. (1965). Adiabatic compressibilities of binary liquid mixtures. *Transactions of the Faraday Society*, 61, 2102-2111.
7. Hammaker, R. M., Clegg, R. M., Patterson, L. K., Rider, P. E., & Rock, S. L. (1968). Hydrogen-bonded dimers and the 2.86-. mu. band in alcohols. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 72(5), 1837-1839.
8. Halder, S., Agrawal, P. S., Thakur, S., & Paliwal, L. J. (2014). Study of structural and temperature dependence on stability constants of certain charge transfer complexes in solution by ultrasonic method. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(9), 241-245.
9. Pimentel, G. C., & McClellan, A. L. (1971). Hydrogen bonding. *Annual Review of Physical Chemistry*, 22(1), 347-385.
10. Kannappan, V., & Santhi, R. J. (2006). Ultrasonic investigation of induced dipole-induced dipole interactions in binary liquid mixtures at 298K. 29 ,192.
11. Rastogi, M. (2002). awasti A, Gupta M and Shukla JP. "Ultrasonic investigations of X... HO bond complexes." *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys*, 40, 256
12. Katyal, R. C., Singh, S., Rattan, V. K., Kanda, P., & Acharya, S. (2003). Viscosities, densities, and ultrasonic velocities of 3-pentanone+ ethylbenzene and 3-pentanone+ o-xylene at (293.15, 303.15, and 313.15) K. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 48(5), 1262-1265.
13. Misra, A., Vibhu, I., Singh, R. K., Gupta, M., & Shukla, J. P. (2007). Acoustic, viscometric and optical properties of binary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran with 1-propanol and 2-propanol. *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids*, 45(1), 93-104.
14. Katti, P. K., & Chaudhri, M. M. (1964). Viscosities of Binary Mixtures of Benzyl Acetate with Dioxane, Aniline, and m-Cresol. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 9(3), 442-443.
15. Grunberg, L., & Nissan, A. H. (1949). Mixture law for viscosity. *Nature*, 164(4175), 799-800.
16. Hind, R. K., McLaughlin, E., & Ubbelohde, A. R. (1960). Structure and viscosity of liquids. Camphor+ pyrene mixtures. *Transactions of the Faraday Society*, 56, 328-330.
17. Kendall, J., & Monroe, K. P. (1917). The viscosity of liquids. II. The viscosity-composition curve for ideal liquid mixtures. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 39(9), 1787-1802.

18. Junjie, Z. (1984). Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Benzene. *J. China Univ. Sci. Technol*, 14, 298-299.
19. Nomoto, O. (1958). Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures. *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan*, 13(12), 1528-1532.
20. Babu, S. (2015). Comparison of Computational and Experimental Ultrasonic Velocities in Binary Mixtures at Different Temperatures. *International Journal of Chemical Concepts*, 1, 81-84.
21. Vandael W, & Vangeel E.,(1969). *Proc of the first international conference on calorimetry and thermodynamics*, Warsaw , 556.
22. Babu, C. P., Kumar, G. P., Nagarjun, B., & Samatha, K. (2014). Theoretical evaluation of ultrasonic velocities of binary liquid mixtures of 1-bromopropane in chlorobenzene at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. *International Letters of Chemistry, Physics and Astronomy*, 11(1), 9-17.
23. Babavali, S. F., Srinivasu, C., & Narendra, K. (2018, August). Study of nature of interactions in liquid mixtures containing aniline with mesitylene in the usage of non-conventional energy sources by theoretical ultrasonic velocity at temperatures T=(303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15) K. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 1992, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
24. Al-Kandary, J. A., Al-Jimaz, A. S., & Abdul-Latif, A. H. M. (2006). Viscosities, densities, and speeds of sound of binary mixtures of benzene, toluene, o-xylene, m-xylene, p-xylene, and mesitylene with anisole at (288.15, 293.15, 298.15, and 303.15) K. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 51(6), 2074-2082.
25. Gupta, P. N., & Sinha, S. C. (1971). Ultrasonic Study of the Physical Parameters of Pure Organic Liquids. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, 25(3), 146-149.
26. Millero, F. J. (1970). The apparent and partial molal volume of aqueous sodium chloride solutions at various temperatures. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 74(2), 356-362.

CHAPTER-2

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The trial procedures utilized in the present examination for assurance of Sound velocity, Density and Viscosity are depicted in this section. Trial procedures utilized in the present examination are depicted as follows,

2.1. TEST TECHNIQUES

2.1.1. SOUND VELOCITY:

Interferometer method

Sound velocity can be estimated for fluids and fluid blends by utilizing interferometric method with great precision and it is generally a decent decision over the other two strategies referenced above and thus it is picked for the present examination. A few workers¹⁻³ have estimated the sound velocity for fluids and their blends utilizing this interferometer technique. Here, a solitary gem variable way interferometer provided by Mittal enterprises (F-81) has been utilized for the present investigation of Sound velocity. This comprises of two sections.

1. The High Frequency Generator: 2 MHz
2. The estimating cell: 2 MHz

The High Frequency Generator is proposed to empower the quartz valuable stone fixed at the base of the evaluating cell at its resonating repeat to make ultrasonic waves in test liquid filled in the assessing cell. A micrometer to watch the changes in present and two controls with the ultimate objective of affectability rule and beginning modifications of the micrometer are given on the high recurrence generator. The assessing cell: - This is phenomenally arranged twofold walled cell for keeping up liquid temperature predictable during the examination. At the main a micrometer fine screw is given, it can move the place of the reflector plate in the

liquid cell for a known separation if a quartz precious stone has fixed at its base. The interferometer cell is appeared in Fig.2.1.

Fig. 2.1

Test procedure:

The top recurrence generator has two handles 'ADJ' to modify the situation of the pin on the ammeter and the handle stamped 'Addition' which is utilized to build the instrument for more noteworthy redirection. The estimating cell is comprised of hardened steel (12cc limit) container of inward width 0.9cm (12cc limit) is solidified at base of the cell. The ultrasonic

waves move from this precious stone till they reflected by a portable reflector. A melded quartz pole is utilized as a reflector. The reflecting surface is 1.4cm in breadth. This is combined with micrometer screw gathering perusing up to 0.001 mm utilizing Teflon couples through the steel bar. The micrometers screw enacts the steel pole which is spring stacked to deal with any back case. The micrometer get together, alongside reflector is fixed to the fluid cell with the assistance of a strung top and Teflon ring. Unscrewed the knurled top of cell and lifted it away from twofold walled development of the cell. The exploratory fluid or fluid arrangement is poured in its center bit and screwed the knurled top. The overabundance fluid flooding from the cell is cleaned. At that point the cell is embedded in the square base attachment and clasped it with the assistance of a screw gave on its side. The high recurrence generator is associated with cell by co-pivotal link furnished with the instrument. The micrometer is gradually moved in either clock shrewd or against clockwise course till the anode current on the ammeter on the high recurrence generator demonstrates a most extreme or least. The readings of micrometer comparing to the most extreme or least in micrometer were recorded. Around 50 readings of continuous most extreme or least are taken and the normal of the considerable number of contrasts determined ($\lambda/2$). The sound speed is assessed from the learning of λ utilizing the recipe, $U = \lambda .f$, where f is the recurrence of the generator i.e., 2MHz. The estimations of the sound speed are exact to $\pm 0.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The presentation of the interferometer was checked by looking at the sound speeds recorded in the present investigation with those of revealed in the writing.

The following precautions have to be taken while measuring sound velocity.

The accompanying precautionary measures must be taken while estimating sound speed.

- i. The Generator ought not be turned on without filling the test fluid in the cell.

- ii. The test fluid ought to be evacuated promptly and the cell ought to be kept perfect and dry.
- iii. The micrometer ought to be kept open 25mm after use.
- iv. Sudden rise or flop in temperature of circled fluid ought to be maintained a strategic distance from to avoid warm stun to the quartz gem.
- v. care need to be taken not to damage the gold plating while cleaning the quartz gem.
- vi. The Generator is taken into consideration 15 seconds for heating up before the perception.

Technical specifications:

- i. High Frequency Generator specifications:
Mains source voltage – 220v, 50Hz, gleam light - 6.3v, 0.3amp wire 500mA, size 41x30x13cm, weighing- 3.5kg approx.
- ii. Measurement cell:
Recurrence - 1.0003MHz, Maximum dislodging of the reflector 20mm, amount of fluid required - 12cc, least tally on the micrometer - 0.001mm, dimensions of -10.5x11.5x31cm, weight - 3.75M approx.
Least tally = $1/2 \times 1/50 \times 1/10 \text{mm} = 0.001 \text{mm}$
- iii. Shielded link:
Associating link is roughly 50cm in length in the gap of generator and the cell.

Working Principle:

An ultrasonic interferometer is a fundamental and direct contraption to choose the ultrasonic speed in liquids with elevated level of exactness showed up in Fig. 2.2. The standard used in

the estimation of speed (U) relies upon the careful affirmation of the wavelength (λ) in the medium. Ultrasonic surges of known repeat (f) are made by a quartz valuable stone fixed at the base of the cell. These are sent back by an adaptable metallic plate held parallel to the quartz jewel. The segment between these two plates is really a whole different of the sound wavelength, standing waves are molded in the medium, these acoustic resonation offers rise to an electrical reaction on the generator driving the quartz valuable stone and the anode stream of the generator transforms into a generally outrageous. The partition is by and by extended or decreased and the assortment is really one half wavelength ($\lambda/2$) or distinctive of it, anode current winds up most prominent. From the learning of wavelength (λ) the speed (U) can be procured by the association, $U = \lambda \cdot f$

Trouble shooting:

In the event that the avoidance in the ammeter is nil or lacking for a specific fluid attempt to build the diversion with the assistance of GAIN handle. If that issue still continue the accompanying guidelines ought to pursue. Turn trimmer “An” on the rear of the generator till greatest diversion is accomplished in Ammeter. At that point turn trimmer B for least diversion. Rehash the procedure by turning trimmer “An” again for greatest pursued by turning trimmer B for least. This should be possible for various occasions till they are appropriately tuned.

Fig. 2.2. Ultrasonic interferometer used in the preset study.

2.1.2. Density measurements

Specific gravity bottle:

The density of liquids is measured with the help of a specific gravity bottle^{4,5} which is the most common and also precise method for finding the density with high precision. The standardization of specific gravity bottle in its volume is done by considering different temperatures like 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

$$\text{Relative density } (\rho) = (W_{tL} / W_{tw}) * d_w$$

where W_{tL} , W_{tw} are the weights of liquid and water respectively and d_w is density of water at certain temperature. The values of density at different temperatures for water were collected from the literature. The thermostat has the thermal stability of $\pm 0.01K$. The specific gravity bottle is dipped up to the neck in water bath to maintain temperature at constant. For this method, accuracy

is better than $\pm 0.5\%$ in the density measurement. A METTLER TOLEDO digital balance (Switzerland make) ABB5- S/FACT with accuracy of ± 0.01 mg shown in Fig.2.3 was used for weight measurements.

Fig. 2.3. Digital balance

2.1.3. Viscosity measurements

Viscosities of an unadulterated fluid and fluid blend have been estimated by utilizing an Ostwald's glass narrow viscometer^{6,7}. The viscometer comprises of two appendages marked as A and B as appeared in Fig.2.4. Appendage A comprises of a huge bulb at the base where the fluid can be taken. Appendage B comprises of a slim and two markings above and underneath of the bulb of appendage B. At first the viscometer is completely cleaned and dried utilizing a tourist blow, at that point the arrangement of realized fixation is poured in the appendage An (almost 10ml). The arrangement is sucked into the bulb B by utilizing an elastic bulb at the highest point of the appendage B. At the point when the arrangement just crosses the upper imprint, the elastic bulb is evacuated. The

arrangement currently starts to fall because of the gravitational power, when the arrangement arrived at the upper imprint, promptly a stopwatch (1/100 sec) is turned on and the time needed to pass the arrangement lower imprint is estimated. Presently the arrangement is expelled from the viscometer and it is completely washed with the dissolvable acetone and dried with hot blower. So as to keep up consistent temperature the viscometer is inundated in the indoor regulator the warm steadiness of the indoor regulator is $\pm 0.01\text{K}$. If t and t_0 are the hours of the stream (of fluid and water) and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the fluid and water separately, at that point the outright consistency of the fluid of fluid arrangement can be determined to utilize the connection.

$$\eta = \left[\frac{\rho \cdot t}{\rho_0 \cdot t_0} \right] \cdot \eta_0$$

Where η_0 is the thickness of the unadulterated refined water at the exploratory temperature. The viscosities of water at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are gathered from writing the exactness of thickness estimation is $\pm 0.001 \text{ mPaS}$.

These precautions were taken for accurate results.

Figure 2.4

- All estimations are taken at a steady temperature with a precision of ± 0.01 K, since consistency is profoundly temperature touchy. At a given temperature, the consistency of water has been taken from literature³¹.
- Care was taken while mounting the viscometer to see that the thin is continually held in a vertical position.
- The arrangements are equilibrated with the indoor regulator for 15 minutes, so the trial arrangement accomplishes a similar temperature of the indoor regulator.

2.1.4 FTIR Characterization

FTIR of pure fluids of Benzoates, Amides, Amines, Alkanols and their twofold blends at equal proportion were taken. FTIR is a method used to procure an IF spectrum of absorption or emission of a fluid or solid. It gathers high-spectral-resolution data above a broad spectral range. This grants a significant advantage over a dispersive spectrometer, which measures intensity over a narrow range of wave numbers at a time. FT-IR is a method of obtaining infrared spectra by first collecting an interferogram of a sample signal using an interferometer. As per literature of similar works in this field, the intensity of an absorption in the IR spectrum indicates the change in dipole moment occurs during vibration. Consequently these are also explains various stretching's formation between molecules also analyze the H- bond inception in between unlike molecules.⁸⁻¹⁰

The infrared spectra for all systems have been recorded using (Alpha-2, M/S Bruker, Germany) at Chalapathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences -drug testing Lab, Guntur and also at Lila Nutraceuticals R&D Centre, Vijayawada, A.P, India

2.1.5. Materials employed & Purification

The chemicals utilized in the current study are of AR grade purchased from (i) Hi Media Lab.Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India (ii) Sisco Research lab Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India (iii) Tokyo Industries. co. Ltd, Japan and (iv) TCI Co. Ltd, Tokyo, Japan with purities more than 99%.

All the fluids used in the current study were purified further by the standard procedure³³ and just center divisions were taken. Preceding use, the synthetic substances were kept in 0.4µm atomic strainers for around 72hours to evacuate water content and were then degassed. Further the virtue of the synthetic concoctions was affirmed by gas fluid chromatography single sharp pinnacles. The virtue investigation of the synthetic compounds is given in table 2.1.

Table 2.1. Purity Analysis

Chemical name	CAS number	Source	Mass fraction(initial)	Mass fraction (final)	Water content (%)	Analysis method
p –Methoxy benzoic acid	100-09-4	Hi Media Lab. Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	0.98	0.992	0.036	Vacuum drying
Aniline	62-53-3	Hi Media Lab. Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	0.99	0.997	0.034	GLC
Formamide	75-12-7	Hi Media Lab. Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	0.99	0.997	0.029	GLC
DMF	68-12-2	Hi Media Lab. Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	0.99	0.997	0.032	GLC
NMF	123-39-7	Tokyo Industries.co. Ltd, Japan	0.99	0.997	0.034	GLC
Ethyl-4 Hydroxy benzoate	120-47-8	Hi Media Lab. Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	0.99	0.995	0.032	Vacuum drying
O-toluidine	95-53-4		0.97	0.996	0.036	GLC
O-Chloro aniline	95-51-2	Sigma-Aldrich Pvt. Ltd, Germany	0.98	0.994	0.036	GLC

*GLC-Gas liquid chromatography

Table 2.2: Physio -Chemical properties of the systems for the present study in their**Pure form**

Property	Compound			
	p-MBA	E4HB	Formamide	Di-Methyl formamide
Molar Mass	152.15 g/mol	166.17 g/mol	45.04 g /mol	73.09 g/mol
Appearance	Powder form	Powder form	Clear liquid	Colorless liquid
Density	1.380 g/ cm ³	1.168 g/cm ³	1.13 g/cm ³	0.944 g/cm ³
Melting Point	457 K	391 K	275 K	212 K
Boiling Point	737 K	571 K	483 K	426 K
Molecular Structure				

(Red: Oxygen, Black: Carbon, Blue: Nitrogen and White: Hydrogen)

Property	Compound			
	N-Methyl formamide	Aniline	O-toluidine	O-Chloro aniline
Molar Mass	59.07 g/mol	93.13 g/mol	107.15g/mol	127.56 g/mol
Appearance	Colorless liquid	Colorless liquid	Colorless liquid	Pale yellow
Density	1.011 g/cm ³	1.021 g/cm ³	0.998 g/cm ³	1.213 g/cm ³
Melting Point	269 K	266.8 K	249.47 K	345.65 K
Boiling Point	455.7 K	457.2 K	473.15 K	481.95 K
Molecular Structure				

(Yellow/Red: Oxygen, Black: Carbon, Blue: Nitrogen and Orange/White: Hydrogen)

REFERENCES

- 1 Dobbs, E. R., & Finegold, L. (1960). Measurement of the velocity of sound in liquid argon and liquid nitrogen at high pressures. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 32(10), 1215-1220.
2. Thabane Y A, Mulay V D, Ghose S and Khasare S B(1993), *ultrasonic studies on molecular interactions in certain binary and ternary systems* Acustica, 81C, 181-187.
3. Nozdrev V F(1965), *The use of ultrasonics in molecular physics*, pergamon, London
4. Millero Jr, F.J. (1967) High precision magnetic float densimeter. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 38(10), 1441-1444.
5. Kannappan, V., & Santhi, R. J. (2006). *Ultrasonic investigation of induced dipole-induced dipole interactions in binary liquid mixtures at 298K*. 44(11):815-819
6. Manoj Ku P, Abhiram S, Prativarani M and Sarmistha M, *Ultrasonic studies of molecular interactions in pyridine + N-N dimethylformamide + cyclohexane ternary liquid mixtures at different temperatures* Int. J. Chem.Pharm. Sci., 3(3) (2012) 6
7. Thirumaran, S., & Ramesh, J. (2009). Acoustic and excess thermodynamical studies on 1-alkanols with DMA in cyclohexanone at different temperatures. *Rasayan J Chem*, 2, 733-739.
8. Chandra Sekhar, M., Madhu Mohan, T., Vijaya Krishna, T., Venkatesulu, A., & Siva Kumar, K. (2015). Density, refractive Index, speed of sound and computational studies of intermolecular interactions in binary mixtures of 2-Chloroaniline with butanols (1-butanol, 2-butanol) at T=(303.15–318.15) K. *Journal of Solution Chemistry*, 44, 237-263.
9. Awasthi, A., Pandey, P. K., & Awasthi, A. (2023). Densities and volumetric properties of binary mixtures of 2-ethoxyethanol with 2-pyrrolidinone and N-methylacetamide from 303.15 to 323.15 K. *The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics*, 178, 106959.
10. Hasan, M., Hiray, A. P., Kadam, U. B., Shirude, D. F., Kurhe, K. J., & Sawant, A. B. (2010). Densities, sound speed, and IR studies of (methanol+ 1-acetoxybutane) and (methanol+ 1, 1-dimethylethyl ester) at (298.15, 303.15, 308.15, and 313.15) K. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 55(1), 535-538.

CHAPTER 3

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF BINARY LIQUID MIXTURES CONTAINING p-METHOXY BENZOATE ACID AND AMIDES

This work was published in European Chemical Bulletin, 12 (SI6), 3395 – 3407 (2023)

DOI: [10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.302](https://doi.org/10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.302)

INTRODUCTION

Pure fluids and fluid blends used in this study are effective preservatives in many varieties like antimicrobial food preservative, antifungal as well as antiseptic agents, solvents as cosmetic and perfumery industries and also acts as metabolites in pharmaceutical industries. P-Methoxy benzoic acid ($C_8H_8O_3$) has antiseptic property and it is soluble in water, alcohols, and ethyl acetate because it is available in powder form. It is also known as P-anisic acid and draconic acid. P-Methoxy benzoic acid has a boiling of about $280^\circ C$ and a melting of $184^\circ C$, it is a metabolite of aniracetam. Measurement of density and ultrasonic velocity in binary liquid mixtures and its observed results of excess values reflects the molecular interaction in liquid mixtures, which is very useful to build comprehensive calculations like RK polynomials/partial molar volumes for the considered liquids. Similar kinds of results were obtained by the earlier workers [1-3] carried out variety of research investigations on the liquid mixtures. The effects shown by the molecules with other functional groups on these molecules plays a vital role in understanding the behavior of hydrogen bonding in the considered mixture. The precision of experimentally measured values of density, viscosity, and speed of sound data was compared with their literature values are shown in Table 01

Table 1: Comparison of measured to literature values of pure liquids

Liquid	Temp (K)	Density(ρ) kg m ³		Viscosity(η) mPa s		Speed of sound(U) m.s ⁻¹		C _p J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	α k K ⁻¹
		lit	Expt	lit	Expt	lit	Expt		
P-Methoxy	303.15	1.1896	1.1886	1.585	1.581	1559.6	1557.2	204.07	1.0004
benzoic acid (a)	308.15	1.1226	1.1246	1.428	1.422	1539.6	1532.6	205.03	1.0013
	313.15	1.0956	1.0966	1.341	1.346	1520.6	1524.4	205.00	1.0028
Formamide (b)	303.15	1.1257	1.1255	2.877	2.784	1588.0	1584.6	107.11	0.9962
	308.15	1.1198	1.1197	2.500	2.461	1577.2	1581.4	105.20	0.9966
	313.15	1.1183	1.1186	2.273	2.251	1568.0	1564.0	108.56	0.9992
NMF (b)	303.15	0.9946	0.9944	1.585	1.566	1408.5	1408.4	124.95	0.9988
	308.15	0.9903	0.9902	1.462	1.474	1400.6	1401.6	126.05	0.9964
	313.15	0.9861	0.9858	1.352	1.361	1382.2	1393.2	129.47	1.0042
DMF (b)	303.15	0.9476	0.9468	0.767	0.770	1459.6	1454.2	152.00	1.0034
	308.15	0.9421	0.9419	0.726	0.732	1434.7	1431.8	153.02	1.0011
	313.15	0.9351	0.9343	0.679	0.681	1420.8	1417.6	157.14	1.0022

(a) Reference [4] (b) Reference [5]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The excess thermo-acoustical parameters measure the system's non-ideality as a consequence of associative/other interactions between the molecules. Excess properties of studied binary systems at different mole fractions have been calculated from the experimental values of densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and speed of sounds (U) of p-Methoxy benzoic acid with formamide, DMF and NMF at temperatures from $T = 303.15$ K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K determined [6] by the equations from (1) to

(4)

$$V_m^E = X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 / \rho - (X_1 M_1 / \rho_1 + X_2 M_2 / \rho_2) \quad (1)$$

$$K_s^E = K_s - K_s^{id} \quad (2)$$

Benson & Kiyohara [7] suggested a relation for calculating the ideal mixture K_s^{id}

$$K_s^{id} = \sum \phi_i \{ K_{s,i}^0 + T V_i^{0(\alpha_i)^2} / C_{p,i}^0 \} - T (\sum X_i V_i^0) (\sum \phi_i \alpha_i^{0,2} / \sum X_i C_{p,i}^0) \quad (3)$$

$$L_f^E = L_f - K_T (K_s^{id})^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

K_T be a temperature dependent constant whose value is $91.368 + 0.3565 T \times 10^{-8}$

$$Z = U * \rho \quad (5)$$

$$(\gamma) = 6.3 \times 10^{-4} \cdot \rho \cdot U^{3/2} \quad (6)$$

Where ρ is the density, U be the Speed of sound of the mixture and $X_1, X_2, M_1, M_2, \rho_1, \rho_2, Z_1, Z_2$ and χ_1, χ_2 are the mole fractions, molar mass, densities, acoustic impedances and surface tensions of actual compounds. In equation (3) $T, \alpha_i^0, C_{p,i}^0$, and ϕ_i be the Temperature, thermal expansion coefficient, isobaric molar heat capacity and volume fraction of i^{th} component.

Surface tension forces are due to intermolecular forces between the liquid's molecules at the liquid's outer boundaries. Surface tension is a principal factor in capillary action. The higher values over the whole composition for these systems can be suggested that strong molecular interactions are present in these mixtures because of density and acoustic impedance values are varies with mole fraction this results increase the speed of sound. Similar studies were observed for excess surface tension in the considered binary liquids. Surface tension (γ) and acoustic impedance (Z) were determined with the help of equation (5,6) reported in Table 2

Table 2 Calculated values of surface tension (χ) and acoustic impedance (Z)

Mole fraction	PMBA+ FA		Mole fraction	PMBA + DMF		Mole fraction	PMBA + NMF	
	$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	Zx10 ³ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	Zx10 ³ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	Zx10 ³ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹
303.15K								
0.0000	8.1948	1.0504	0.0000	8.2228	1.0604	0.0000	8.8460	1.1287
0.2322	8.8022	1.1884	0.2240	9.6492	1.2028	0.2523	9.1522	1.1523
0.4701	9.4501	1.2866	0.4761	10.4616	1.2921	0.4819	10.1538	1.2617
0.6342	10.1328	1.4270	0.6789	11.3744	1.3266	0.6524	11.1603	1.3295
0.8246	11.8998	1.5192	0.8332	13.2249	1.3667	0.8286	12.1517	1.3743
1.0000	12.2796	1.5358	1.0000	14.2151	1.3790	1.0000	13.2651	1.3840
308.15K								
0.0000	7.9459	1.0549	0.0000	7.9801	1.0842	0.0000	8.1746	1.1359
0.2322	8.9133	1.1984	0.2240	9.2562	1.2129	0.2523	8.7450	1.1644
0.4701	9.1142	1.2499	0.4761	10.0908	1.3013	0.4819	9.7632	1.2735
0.6342	9.9833	1.3676	0.6789	10.9623	1.3222	0.6524	10.7272	1.3160
0.8246	11.6549	1.5975	0.8332	12.5275	1.3499	0.8286	11.5844	1.3317
1.0000	11.9075	1.6099	1.0000	12.9050	1.3851	1.0000	12.4350	1.3553
313.15K								
0.0000	7.8777	1.0595	0.0000	7.7763	1.0618	0.0000	8.1729	1.1458
0.2322	9.3680	1.2672	0.2240	8.9450	1.2217	0.2523	8.4470	1.1705
0.4701	10.1396	1.3934	0.4761	9.7417	1.3128	0.4819	9.4347	1.2806
0.6342	10.8890	1.5667	0.6789	10.4494	1.3422	0.6524	10.2812	1.3085
0.8246	11.7179	1.6647	0.8332	11.7952	1.3775	0.8286	10.9259	1.3295
1.0000	12.1724	1.6724	1.0000	12.1341	1.3887	1.0000	12.6481	1.3967

The excess values for the above parameters were fitted to a Redlich- Kister type polynomial by the nonlinear Least – squares method [8]

$$Y^E = X_1 (1-X_1) \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (2 X_1 - 1)^{i-1} \quad (7)$$

Where $Y^E = K_s^E, V^E, L_f^E$. The values of coefficient A_i were determined by a regression analysis based on the least- squares method.

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = [\sum_{i=1}^n (Y^E_{\text{exp}} - Y^E_{\text{cal}}) / (D-N)]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

Where D is number of experimental data points and N is number of parameters

Fig. 1(a-c) Variation of **Excess isentropic compressibility** with respect to mole fraction of PMBA + FA/DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

Fig. 2(a-c) Variation of **Excess molar volume** with respect to mole fraction of p-MBA + FA/DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

Fig 3(a-c) Variation of **Excess free length** with respect to mole fraction of PMBA +FA/ DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

The estimations of these abundance parameters K_s^E , V_m^E and L_f^E are fitted to the R-K type polynomial condition and the coefficients A_i are dictated by the strategy for least squares, these qualities alongside the estimations of (σ) are appeared in table 3

By watching the deviations in the estimations of abundance parameters for the blend of double fluid blends under scrutiny, we can foresee the quality of associations between the particles of fluid mixture [9]. The deviations in the estimations of these abundance parameters are because of a few contributing variables, they are (1) The various powers of collaboration between the atoms, similar to the charge move powers and development of hydrogen bonds between particles prompts negative/positive abundance values (2) Geometrical fitting of one atom in to the next because of the varieties fit as a fiddle and size of the particles of segment fluids, it is called structural contribution. (3) Physical inter atomic forces.

Table 3 Parameters of Redlich-Kister equation (A_k) and Standard Deviation (σ) for P-MBA with FA/DMF/ NMF at different temperatures

Parameter	Temperature (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
P-MBA + Formamide					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	-2.6218	0.2923	1.8532	0.0431
	308.15	-3.0613	0.3064	0.9877	0.0498
	313.15	-3.4820	0.4105	0.0953	0.0610
$10^6 V_m^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	2.3742	-0.1227	-1.0137	0.6402
	308.15	2.7109	-0.0328	0.0471	0.8217
	313.15	3.0296	0.1104	1.0045	0.9956
$10^{13}L_f^E/ (m)$	303.15	-0.2921	0.1350	0.0668	0.0029
	308.15	-0.2131	0.0945	0.0949	0.0028
	313.15	-0.1426	0.0605	0.0782	0.0020
P-MBA + DMF					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	-2.0012	-0.8225	3.1475	0.0409
	308.15	-2.6173	-0.5763	3.1322	0.0516
	313.15	-3.1030	-0.2168	2.3809	0.0532
$10^6 V_m^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	3.4078	0.4973	-3.2442	0.8963
	308.15	4.0893	0.5705	-2.1330	1.1268
	313.15	4.5663	1.5875	-1.2388	1.3810

	303.15	-0.0215	-0.0047	0.0284	0.2708
$10^{13}L_f^E / (\text{m})$	308.15	-0.0181	-0.0039	0.0276	0.3779
	313.15	-0.0276	-0.0064	0.0318	0.4595
		P-MBA + NMF			
	303.15	-0.0153	0.0002	0.0052	0.3962
$10^{12}K_S^E / (\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{N}^{-1})$	308.15	-0.0242	0.0040	0.0041	0.4864
	313.15	-0.0273	0.0074	-0.0032	0.5778
	303.15	0.5758	0.1866	-0.3220	0.1384
$10^6 V_m^E / (\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1})$	308.15	0.6614	-0.0137	0.0292	0.1456
	313.15	0.2921	0.0766	-0.2655	0.0668
	303.15	-0.0143	-0.0019	0.0049	0.0478
$10^{13}L_f^E / (\text{m})$	308.15	-0.0197	-0.0042	0.0053	0.0310
	313.15	-0.0219	-0.0053	0.0082	0.0188

From the treatment of excess thermo acoustic quantities for liquid mixtures proposed by Desnoyers and Perron [10] in agreement with the original statements of Redlich and Kister from equation (7), table 3 concludes that the excess quantity (K_s^E , L_f^E and V_m^E) gives the spring of upshots in the systems it shows the non-ideality in the mixtures but the values of (σ) are less than one that indicates strong interactions at huge suffusion.

The obtained values of partial molar volumes are reported in Table 4 by using the equations (9-12), also tabulated the infinite dilution values of partial molar volume and Excess partial molar volumes at infinite dilution in table 5.

The partial molar volumes for all the binary systems can be calculated using the formulae

$$\bar{V}_{m,1} = V_m^E + V_1^* + X_2(\partial V_m^E / \partial X)_{P,T} \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{V}_{m,2} = V_m^E + V_2^* + X_1(\partial V_m^E / \partial X)_{P,T} \quad (10)$$

Where $\bar{V}_{m,1}$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}$ are the partial molar volumes and V_1^* and V_2^* molar volumes of pure compounds.

The values of infinite dilution of partial and excess partial molar volumes for the binary system ($V_{m,1}^{E,\infty}, V_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$) can be calculated by the following relations.

$$V_{m,1}^{E,\infty} = A_0 + A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + \dots = V_{m,1}^\infty - V_1^* \quad (11)$$

$$V_{m,2}^{E,\infty} = A_0 - A_1 + A_2 - A_3 + \dots = V_{m,2}^\infty - V_2^* \quad (12)$$

Where A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3 are the coefficients obtained from R-K polynomial equation

Table 4: Partial molar volumes for PMBA with FA/DMF /NMF at different temperatures

Mole fraction	PMBA + FA		Mole fraction	PMBA+ DMF		Mole fraction	PMBA + NMF	
	$\bar{V}_{m,1}\times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2}\times 10^{-5}$		$\bar{V}_{m,1}\times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2}\times 10^{-5}$		$\bar{V}_{m,1}\times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2}\times 10^{-5}$
303.15K								
0.0000	3.28	20.14	0.0000	3.13	19.64	0.0000	3.14	18.79
0.2322	4.52	19.26	0.2240	4.24	18.53	0.2523	3.79	17.90
0.4701	4.77	18.14	0.4761	4.58	17.30	0.4819	4.06	16.84
0.6342	4.48	19.50	0.6789	4.78	19.66	0.6524	4.25	17.15
0.8246	5.48	20.76	0.8332	5.35	20.89	0.8286	5.39	18.57
1.0000	6.33	23.46	1.0000	5.84	22.27	1.0000	6.94	21.95
308.15K								
0.0000	3.88	19.14	0.0000	3.24	16.17	0.0000	4.15	15.66
0.2322	4.15	18.62	0.2240	4.29	15.35	0.2523	4.40	13.64
0.4701	4.89	17.11	0.4761	4.72	14.48	0.4819	4.96	11.58
0.6342	5.05	18.98	0.6789	5.81	16.16	0.6524	5.15	14.77
0.8246	5.87	19.47	0.8332	6.34	18.85	0.8286	6.49	17.82
1.0000	6.37	22.03	1.0000	7.79	21.04	1.0000	7.24	18.88
313.15K								
0.0000	4.36	19.27	0.0000	8.35	18.19	0.0000	10.63	15.82
0.2322	5.05	18.14	0.2240	9.85	17.44	0.2523	11.13	14.45
0.4701	5.74	17.07	0.4761	10.03	16.18	0.4819	11.63	13.80
0.6342	6.46	18.92	0.6789	10.93	18.76	0.6524	12.37	15.88
0.8246	7.51	19.67	0.8332	11.80	19.20	0.8286	13.39	18.08
1.0000	7.88	22.68	1.0000	11.91	21.44	1.0000	13.88	19.16

Table 5 Values of partial molar volume of the components at infinite dilution ($V_{m,1}^{\infty}$, $V_{m,2}^{\infty}$) and excess partial molar volume at infinite dilution ($V_{m,1}^{E,\infty}$ and $V_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$) for all the systems at three different temperatures

System	Temperature(K)	$V_{m,1}^{\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,2}^{\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,1}^{E,\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,2}^{E,\infty} \times 10^{-5}$
PMBA +FA	303.15	3.28	23.46	-3.05	-3.32
	308.15	3.88	22.03	-2.71	-2.63
	313.15	4.36	22.68	-3.80	-3.16
PMBA +DMF	303.15	3.18	22.27	-2.49	-2.89
	308.15	3.24	21.04	-4.55	-4.87
	313.15	4.15	21.44	-3.09	-3.22
PMBA +NMF	303.15	4.36	21.95	-3.55	-3.41
	308.15	8.35	18.88	-3.56	-3.25
	313.15	10.63	19.16	-3.25	-3.34

The molecular interactions present in the P-MBA + amides are also reflected in terms of partial molar volumes. The obtained values are shown in table 4 and table 5, from which it culminates that strong interactions exist throughout the taking liquid mixtures. From these results, it is also observe that the partial molar volumes is proportional with concentration of the composition. Harkot suggested [11,12]that the large negative excess volumes for liquid mixtures are due to geometrical factors, and hydrophilic interactions that give the higher degree of dissociation results were obtained by the increase of specific conductivity in a mixture.

FT-IR SPECTRA

The FT-IR spectra of pure solvents have been done in the wave number region $400\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and are presented in the (fig 4- fig 7). Partial band assignments of the solvent mixtures by comparing with the pure solvents have been made and compounds are discussed with the mole fractions at different cases considered in three combinations recorded at room temperature. Case (i)30% component (1) and 70% of the component (2),Case (ii)50% of component (1) and component(2) and case(iii) 70% of component(1) to 30% of component(2). For this figures the intensity of an absorption in the IR spectrum can be observed with variation in dipole moment that develops during the vibration. But, vibrations are develop a shift in dipole moment (C=O/C-O/C-H/N-H stretch) for P-MBA+ amides. From this outcome in a more intense absorption produce the analysis of hydrogen bonding formation in between the P-MBA+ amides mixture [13, 14].

Fig 4. FTIR analysis for Formamide

Fig 5 FTIR analysis for N methyl Formamide

Fig 6 FTIR analysis for Di Methyl Formamide

Fig 7 FTIR analysis of p-methoxy benzoic acid

CONCLUSIONS

The speed of sound, viscosity and densities of binary mixtures for P-Methoxy benzoic acid with amides were measured at temperature from 303.15K - 313.15K using standard techniques also compared using the standard relations obtained from the literature. Further various thermo - acoustic parameters were computed by the obtained data, the excess values of molar volume and excess acoustic impedance are found to be positive for all the binary systems over the entire range of composition. The values of excess properties of K_s^E and L_r^E are found to be negative for binary mixtures of P-Methoxy benzoic acid with formamide, DMF and NMF in the whole mole fraction range at the three different temperatures. The results can be explained in terms of the intra and inter molecular H-bonding of amide and the formation of the same between the polar and nonpolar molecules of the liquid mixtures. Further the values of the excess parameters are fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial equation and the results are also represented in table 3. Furthermore to showcase the molecular interactions in between methoxy molecules and amides with the upshots of partial molar volumes. Finally, FT-IR analysis of the pure solvent and their mixtures are also reported where the principal bands in the mixture.

REFERENCES

1. Godhani, D. R., Dobariya, P. B., Sanghani, A. M., & Mehta, J. P. (2017). Thermodynamic properties of binary mixtures of 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole derivative with chloroform, N, N-dimethyl formamide at 303, 308 and 313 K and atmospheric pressure. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10, S422-S430.
2. Madhuri, N. J., Naidu, P. S., Glory, J., & Prasad, K. R. (2011). Ultrasonic investigations of molecular interaction in binary mixtures of benzyl benzoate with acetonitrile and benzonitrile. *Journal of Chemistry*, 8, 457-469.
3. A.V Rao, P.Venkateswaralu, G.K Raman and A.V Rajulu, *Acta Polym.*, 43, (1992) 185
4. Nagarjuna, A., Babu, S., & Gowrisankar, M. (2022). Thermo-physical and spectroscopic studies of liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoic acid. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*, 43(1), 1974-1985.
5. Nagarjuna, A., Kanth, K. Y., Prakash, G. B., & Das, D. (2019). Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures containing benzyl benzoate. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 12(4).
6. Nayeem, S. M., Nyamathulla, S., Khan, I., & Rao, D. K. (2016). Investigation of molecular interactions in binary mixture (benzyl benzoate+ ethyl acetate) at T=(308.15, 313.15, and 318.15) K: An insight from ultrasonic speed of sound and density. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 218, 676-685.
7. Kiyohara, O., & Benson, G. C. (1979). Ultrasonic speeds and isentropic compressibilities of n-alkanol+ n-heptane mixtures at 298.15 K. *The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics*, 11(9), 861-873.
8. Redlich, O., & Kister, A. T. (1948). Algebraic representation of thermodynamic properties and the classification of solutions. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry*, 40(2), 345-348.
9. Balaji, R., Sankar, M. G., Sekhar, M. C., & Shekar, M. C. (2016). Thermodynamic properties of n-methylformamide+ short carboxylic acids as a function of temperature. *Karbala International Journal of Modern Science*, 2(1), 10-19.
10. Desnoyers, J. E., & Perron, G. (1997). Treatment of excess thermodynamic quantities for liquid mixtures. *Journal of solution chemistry*, 26, 749-755.
11. M. Mc Dowall , C.A Joseph and Vincent, *J. Chem. Soc Faraday Trans.*, 70, (1974) 1862
12. Harkot, J., & Jańczuk, B. (2009). Surface and volume properties of dodecyl ethyl dimethyl ammonium bromide and benzyl dimethyl dodecyl ammonium bromide: II. Volumetric properties of dodecyl ethyl dimethyl ammonium bromide and benzyl dimethyl dodecyl ammonium bromide. *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 330(2), 467-473.

- 13.** Pandey, P. K., Awasthi, A., & Awasthi, A. (2013). Acoustic, volumetric and spectroscopic investigations in binary mixtures of formamide/N-methyl formamide+ 2-chloroethanol at various temperatures. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 187, 343-349.
- 14.** Karunakar, T., & Srinivas, C. H. (2013). Thermo acoustic and infrared study of molecular interactions in binary mixture aniline+ 1-butanol. *Res. Rev.: J. Pure Appl. Phys*, 1, 5-15. 5

CHAPTER-4

STUDY OF INTERMOLECULAR INTERACTIONS IN ETHYL-4-HYDROXY BENZOATE LIQUID MIXTURE

This work is reported in Material science and technology, 22(10), 2023

DOI:10.10543/f0299.2023.41742

Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures

Accepted in Taylor and Francis journal proceedings

INTRODUCTION

Study of Physico-chemical characteristics of fluid mixtures understanding the changes in thermodynamic behavior in a given mixture. One of the most significant uses of these features is their potential to reveal details of system structure effects and intermolecular interactions. Ethyl-4-hydroxy-benzoate, ($C_9H_{10}O_3$) is ethyl ester of p-hydroxy benzoic acid, or Ethyl paraben's. It is also utilized as an antifungal preservative and has a high melting point ranging from 115⁰-118 °C. The antibacterial properties of ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate are used extensively in the food, cosmetic, and textile industries. It serves as an ingredient in cleaners, hair dyes, beverages, lotions, shampoos, and other products. On the other hand Anilines, also known as amino benzene or phenyl amine, are organic compounds that belong to the category of substances in organic chemistry. These substances are classified as aromatic amines and are thought to be poisonous in nature. An oily liquid with a musty and fishy smell, aniline is yellowish and somewhat brownish in color. It has the stench of rotting fish.

The non-bonding interactions like hydrogen bonding and additional forces present, such as charge transfer, dispersive force, and dipole-dipole interactions that happen in the investigated liquid mixes are explained in this work [1-3]. The excess characteristics were calculate by using observe principles of viscosity (η), density (ρ), & sound speed (U), and these values were then simplified the theoretical relations of speed of sound then compare with the experimental results of speed of sound.

The experimentally measured data on density, viscosity and sound velocity are compared with research values and are shown in Table 01.

Table 01: Comparison of pure fluid densities, viscosities, and sound speeds with obtained values.

Liq.	Temp T (K)	Density(ρ)kg m ⁻³		Viscosity(η) mPaS		Speed of sound (U) m.s ⁻¹		C _p J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		lit	Expt	lit	Expt	lit	Expt	
E-4-HB [a]	303.15	1.1035	1.1037	1.283	1.293	1523.0	1525.4	304.03
	308.15	1.0313	1.0315	1.198	1.195	1541.4	1544.6	317.64
	313.15	0.9973	0.9985	1.175	1.173	1572.6	1576.2	338.27
Aniline [b]	303.15	0.8019	0.8023	2.224	2.235	1228.2	1225.4	191.01
	308.15	0.7982	0.7986	1.958	1.947	1217.8	1215.6	192.05
	313.15	0.7946	0.7864	1.700	1.723	1198.8	1197.2	193.70
O-Chloro Aniline [c]	303.15	1.2026	1.2025	3.825	3.815	1469.6	1464.8	218.41 ^e
	308.15	1.1980	1.1967	3.412	3.479	1453.3	1457.2	222.37 ^e
	313.15	1.1930	1.1946	3.060	3.105	1435.2	1434.8	231.82 ^e
O-toluidine [d]	303.15	0.9900	0.9935	4.433	4.467	1572.2	1575.4	211.30 ^e
	308.15	0.9859	0.9877	5.666	5.684	1553.2	1557.2	213.41 ^e
	313.15	-----	0.9748	-----	6.126	-----	1535.6	218.66 ^e

^a Reference [7] ^b Reference [8] ^c Reference [9] ^d Reference [10] ^e Estimated from NIST web book

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

(i) Excess Properties

The excess properties of research binary system E-4-HB containing aniline, O-chloroaniline and O-toluidine at, $T = 303.15\text{ K}$, 308.15 K and 313.15 K was calculated by using an excel spread sheet and are shown in Figures 1–3 [4, 5]

The observed values of K_s^E , V_m^E , L_f^E and Z^E can be explained by different effects depending on chemical, physical & geometrical properties of current components of binary system under research. Physical interactions are mainly concerned with dispersion forces, which positively affect V_m^E and L_f^E . The positive V_m^E values over entire blend composition range may be due to disruption of predominant hydrogen structures by formation of weak hydrogen bonds, between E-4-HB and OCA/OT molecules and insertion of smaller molecules into cavities created by larger molecules, Z values that are positive for mixtures in composition range indicate that interaction between E-4-HB and substituted amines is stronger than the ester or amine–amine interactions. How strongly two things interact E-4-HB and was replaced amino particles appears to be highly reliant on position of ethyl groups in amino molecules. Substituted amine, when molecules are pure, they have a smaller more H-bonds than primary amines. Chemical/ specific interactions arise from formation and breaking of hydrogen bonds and another complex interaction, ending in negative up shots of L_f^E and K_s^E due to geometric effects that allow molecules of smaller size to enter the structure of other molecules.

Mixing E-4-HB with replaced amines can lead to H-bond formation between amide H-atom and ester carbonyl group, and vice versa. The sound speed of amine mixtures was found to decrease with increasing E-4-HB mole fraction and that of substituted amines with increasing hydroxyl mole fraction three contrasting temperatures. The outcome displays a positive deviation from Z^E for all compositions [6, 11]. Plausible qualitative interpretations for behavior of this mixture with composition have proposed. As mentioned earlier, amine molecule has an extensive intramolecular and inter molecular hydrogen bonding network due to the strong proton accepting group $C=O$ in the molecule. Addition of E-4-HB with OT causes slow hydrogen bond dissociation in hydroxyl molecule, at same time, hydrogen bonding between Aniline and E-4HB is also possible because it has three H-bond moreover, donations to the $C=O$ group of proton acceptors. [12, 13]

Fig.1 **Excess isentropic compressibility** with respect to mole fraction of E-4-HB + Aniline/OCA /OT at three different temperatures

Fig. 2 Excess molar volume changes depending on mole fraction of E-4-HB + Aniline/OCA /OT at three various temperatures

Fig.3 Extra free length in relation to mole fraction varies of E-4-HB + Aniline/ OCA / OT at three different temperatures

Then, Redlich & Kister type polynomial [14] a non-linear regression method and values of coefficient, are determined by least squares and are reported in Table 3. The outcomes of Redlich & Kister, concluding that redundancy quantities (K_s^E , V_m^E and L_f^E) give a general view of systems that are not ideal in mixtures because of the strong correlations but can still be quite difficult to capture specially large systems with over flows when (σ) is smaller.

Table 03: Parameters (A_k) and typical Deviation (σ) for E-4-HB with aniline, O-CA and OT at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

parameter	Temp.(K)	A0	A1	A2	σ
E-4-HB + Aniline					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	2.3704	-1.3748	-0.9249	0.2007
	308.15	2.0288	-1.0836	-0.7129	0.3504
	313.15	1.3350	-0.9372	-0.4082	0.5701
$10^6 V^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	17.3747	6.8536	-3.2657	0.6440
	308.15	19.9782	9.2488	-7.0781	0.3010
	313.15	23.4971	14.1826	-9.1038	0.1494
$10^{13}L_f^E (m)$	303.15	7.1156	-5.8063	-1.9931	0.1275
	308.15	9.1964	-8.6581	-4.5350	0.4114
	313.15	12.5114	-10.3484	-7.1696	0.8385
E-4-HB+O-Chloroaniline					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	1.4614	-0.8296	-0.1058	0.2518
	308.15	1.7546	-1.0317	-0.1870	0.3048
	313.15	1.9477	-1.1420	-0.2124	0.5396
$10^6 V^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	18.2028	-9.0543	-6.9865	0.3216
	308.15	25.7451	-13.3676	-9.9245	0.6305
	313.15	36.9254	-17.5164	-13.8109	0.9648

	303.15	7.3817	-1.7284	-2.0534	0.2144
$10^{13}L_f^E$ (m)	308.15	10.5263	-5.0221	-3.4669	0.5187
	313.15	13.2294	-8.5134	-5.3038	0.9614
E-4-HB +O-Toluidine					
	303.15	1.6911	-1.2104	-0.5379	0.3161
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	308.15	1.1416	-1.0316	-0.3752	0.2664
	313.15	1.1011	-0.8025	0.2283	0.1979
	303.15	11.5881	-6.0457	-5.6157	0.4402
$10^6 V^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	308.15	19.9257	-9.9456	-11.7846	0.7486
	313.15	25.6942	-12.9867	-20.8105	0.9134
	303.15	4.5685	-9.6651	-1.9716	0.5762
$10^{13}L_f^E$ (m)	308.15	7.6253	-11.8947	-4.7564	0.7234
	313.15	10.7254	-14.2574	-6.1755	0.9166

(ii) Speed of sound theories

The exhibitory adroitness of speeds of sound theories based upon the brawn of interactivity influence in a framework. The measured values of speed of sound along with their theoretically determined values of Nomoto's, Ideal mixing, Junjie's, Vandael & Vangel and Rao's [16-19] with mole fraction in the twofold fluid blends of E-4-HB + amines at three different temperatures were noticed at table 2. The deviation in upshots may be ascribed to the précised made in these theories for the odd-odd speaks interactivities between the motes in the whole captivation. This implies the impedance relation (UIMR) and Nomoto (UNMR) and reveals merit of concurrence among theoretical to measured data. Speed of sound for both real and experimental increases/decreases with acoustic impedance compliance with mole fraction. This drift is due to own alliance of solvent molecules have more strong dipole- induced dipole interactions between the molecules.

From table 2 we also observes slight changes in Junjie UJN, Rao's (UR) and Vandael & Vangel (UVDV) relations. This type of alterations are presumed in the blends due to volume variation after fluid mixing, also there is much deviation in theoretical prediction of speed of sound with measured data recommend the exits of solid inclination for the relationship between the segment atoms because of hydrogen bond in the mix.

The Chi-square and APE values are less for all these theories. These results are used to judge non-ideality behavior in the fluid blends and it can also perceive the mote ally with positive/negative alteration in speed of sound specifies atomic dissociation/ association between molecules.

Table 2: Speed of sound theories for the binary system of E -4-HB with aniline/o-Chloro Aniline/ o-toluidine at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

X_1	U_{EXP} m.s ⁻¹	U_{NOM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{IMR} m.s ⁻¹	U_{JM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{VDV} m.s ⁻¹	U_R m.s ⁻¹
E-4-HB + Aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	1225.4	1225.4	1225.4	1225.4	1225.4	1225.4
0.2126	1298.2	1298.8	1297.2	1291.2	1293.2	1295.2
0.4567	1388.6	1388.2	1386.6	1385.6	1387.6	1386.6
0.6473	1474.6	1472.8	1471.6	1476.6	1475.6	1476.6
0.8253	1509.4	1509.6	1509.8	1507.4	1508.4	1506.4
1.0000	1525.6	1525.6	1525.6	1525.6	1525.6	1525.6
	APE	0.0008	0.0037	0.0011	0.0028	0.0109
	chi square	0.0036	0.0427	0.0018	0.0317	0.1247
308.15 K						
0.0000	1215.4	1215.4	1215.4	1215.4	1215.4	1215.4
0.2126	1273.2	1273.6	1273.8	1272.2	1276.2	1277.2
0.4567	1383.8	1383.0	1383.4	1381.8	1384.8	1386.8
0.6473	1479.4	1479.4	1479.2	1473.4	1475.4	1477.4
0.8253	1522.6	1522.2	1522.0	1524.6	1524.6	1526.6
1.0000	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6
	APE	0.0017	0.0052	0.0001	0.0020	0.0105
	chi square	0.0024	0.0604	0.0015	0.0247	0.1119
313.15K						
0.0000	1197.4	1197.4	1197.4	1197.4	1197.4	1197.4
0.2126	1253.8	1253.6	1253.2	1252.8	1256.8	1257.8
0.4567	1388.2	1388.8	1388.6	1384.2	1382.2	1386.2

0.6473	1479.6	1479.4	1479.4	1477.6	1478.6	1474.6
0.8253	1531.2	1531.6	1531.8	1533.2	1535.2	1537.2
1.0000	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2
APE		0.0003	0.0022	0.0005	0.0032	0.0025
chi square		0.0026	0.0324	0.0066	0.0309	0.0222

E-4-HB +O-Chloroaniline

303.15K

0.0000	1464.8	1464.8	1464.8	1464.8	1464.8	1464.8
0.2469	1486.2	1486.6	1486.4	1484.2	1485.2	1481.2
0.4353	1498.8	1498.2	1498.0	1492.8	1496.8	1497.8
0.6674	1506.6	1506.0	1506.8	1505.6	1507.6	1509.6
0.8759	1514.4	1514.8	1514.2	1513.4	1519.4	1516.4
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
APE		0.0005	0.0057	0.0003	0.0044	0.0102
Chi square		0.0041	0.0418	0.0028	0.0032	0.1134

308.15K

0.0000	1457.2	1457.2	1457.2	1457.2	1457.2	1457.2
0.2469	1481.2	1481.6	1481.8	1481.6	1483.2	1484.2
0.4353	1496.6	1496.2	1496.2	1493.0	1495.6	1498.6
0.6674	1514.4	1514.8	1514.6	1517.4	1516.4	1519.4
0.8759	1532.8	1532.0	1532.4	1535.8	1537.8	1536.8
1.0000	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6
APE		0.0001	0.0063	0.0002	0.0027	0.0103
Chi square		0.0029	0.0216	0.0013	0.0419	0.1086

313.15 K

0.0000	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8
0.2469	1474.2	1474.4	1474.6	1471.2	1473.2	1476.2
0.4353	1496.4	1496.8	1496.0	1495.4	1498.4	1493.4

0.6674	1527.6	1527.0	1527.6	1523.6	1521.6	1528.6
0.8759	1561.8	1561.6	1561.4	1564.8	1563.8	1566.8
1.0000	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2
	APE	0.0003	0.0052	0.0006	0.0037	0.0137
	Chi square	0.0043	0.0409	0.0047	0.0512	0.1829

E-4-HB +O- Toluidine

303.15K

0.0000	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4
0.2068	1563.2	1563.6	1563.8	1561.2	1565.2	1566.2
0.4051	1552.8	1552.2	1552.0	1554.8	1553.8	1555.8
0.6076	1541.6	1541.8	1541.2	1546.6	1544.6	1546.6
0.8054	1536.4	1536.0	1536.6	1533.4	1535.4	1532.4
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
	APE	0.0003	0.0051	0.0005	0.0052	0.0141
	Chi square	0.0021	0.0358	0.0037	0.0062	0.1254

308.15K

0.0000	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2
0.2068	1553.2	1553.4	1553.0	1551.2	1554.2	1556.2
0.4051	1549.6	1549.8	1549.8	1548.6	1542.6	1547.6
0.6076	1547.4	1547.6	1547.2	1546.4	1548.4	1546.4
0.8054	1546.8	1546.0	1546.4	1548.8	1545.8	1545.0
1.0000	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6
	APE	0.0002	0.0045	0.0003	0.0036	0.0113
	Chi square	0.0021	0.0201	0.0010	0.0309	0.1126

313.15 K

0.0000	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6
0.2068	1540.2	1540.8	1540.0	1541.2	1543.2	1544.2
0.4051	1545.4	1545.2	1542.8	1543.4	1544.4	1547.4

0.6076	1550.6	1550.4	1551.2	1553.6	1552.6	1554.6
0.8054	1567.8	1560.0	1560.4	1562.8	1564.8	1565.8
1.0000	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2
APE		0.0002	0.0048	0.0004	0.0036	0.0129
Chi square		0.0047	0.0386	0.0038	0.0418	0.1523

(iii) FT-IR SPECTRA

FT-IR data of fewer cleaners (Figures 4-7) and their mix with other compositions were performed in the wave number range of 500-3500 cm^{-1} . The single-shot FT-IR spectra of this three blends with different compositions show that there are some differences in peaks that include components, specifically 30% E-4-HB with 70% aniline and two more compositions for E-4-HB+OCA/OT blends, but there is no difference in compositional peaks of other two blends. A partial assignment of solvent mixtures and pure solvent bands has been performed and discusses accordingly. The main absorption bands of esters, are due to C=O (extending) & N-H (extending) motions. The C=O shift (extending) frequency of various amines in E-4-HB also results from the breaking of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds in amides and their formation between different molecules in liquid mixtures. This is due to intra-inter molecular hydrogen-bond dissociation of amine molecules or its formation between molecules. [14, 15]

Fig 4. FT-IR analysis of Ethyl-4-hydroxybenzoate pure component

Fig 5. FTIR analysis of Aniline pure component

Fig 6. FT-IR analysis of O-Chloroaniline pure component

Fig 7. FT-IR analysis of O-Toluidine pure component

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental values of sound of speed, viscosities and densities for the binary mixture E-4-HB with amines at 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K was determined. In addition, thermo acoustic variables of various types were determined by comparing gathered info by using standard relations taken from research. The excess molar volume values are discovered to be positive and low with relation to all binary systems across compositional range at all temperatures. The extra attributes K_s^E and L_f^E are negative for mixture binary over entire range of moles per mole at three degrees. The outcomes are explicable by breakdown of intra- inter molecular H-bonds of amines and its creation between different components of liquid mixtures. In addition, certain interactions between dipoles may exist in all blends, particularly between OCA and OT, which is confirmed by the higher value of acoustic impedance of the thermo-acoustic function. In addition, the Speed of sound values of impedance relation (UIMR) and Nomoto (UNMR) and reveals merit of concurrence among all the theoretical to measured data. Analysis of the pure solvent and its mixes using FT-IR, assigning the main benzoate and amine bands are also reported. The shift of main bands supports the formation of new H-bonds between the components of mix.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chinnarao, D., Padmarao, C. V., Beena, C., Srilatha, M., Ramanjaneyulu, M. V. V., Choppara, P., & Rao, B. V. (2023). Acoustic, excess thermodynamical, molecular interaction and anti-microbial activity studies on binary liquid mixtures of geranyl acetate and benzyl benzoate in the temperature range of 303.15 K–318.15 K. *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*, 100(5), 100969.
- [2] Poling, B. E. Reid, R.C & Prausnitz, J.M (2004). *The properties of gases and liquids*. 4th ed., (McGraw Hill book company, New York)
- [3] Rajagopal, K., & Chenthilnath, S. (2010). Excess thermodynamic studies in binary liquid mixtures of 2-methyl-2-propanol with ketones at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 155(1), 20-28.
- [4] Kalimulla, T., Babu, S., Das, D., Gowrisankar, M., & Rao, K. G. (2019). Ultrasonic investigations in binary liquid mixtures of 2-methylcyclohexanone with formamide, n-methylformamide and n, n-dimethylformamide at different temperatures. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 11(7), 2645-2655.

- [5] Narasimha Rao, C., Ramanaiah, S., Chowdappa, A., Sivakumar, K., & Venkateswarlu, P. (2015). Thermodynamic and transport properties of binary liquid mixtures of cyclohexanol with isomeric chlorotoluenes. *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids*, 53(2), 264-274.
- [6] Garcia, B., Alcalde, R., & Leal, J. M. (1991). Excess properties for binary liquid mixtures of propionic acid with aniline derivatives. *Canadian journal of chemistry*, 69(3), 369-372.
- [7] Nagarjuna, A., & Babu, S. (2020). Spectroscopic and volumetric study of binary liquid mixtures containing Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate and alkanols. *Chemical Data Collections*, 26, 100347.
- [8] Nagarjuna, A., Babu, S., & Gowrisankar, M. (2022). Thermo-physical and spectroscopic studies of liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoic acid. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*, 43(1), 1974-1985.
- [9] Chandra Sekhar, M., Venkatesulu, A., Gowrisankar, M., & Srinivasa Krishna, T. (2017). Thermodynamic study of interactions in binary liquid mixtures of 2-Chloroaniline with some carboxylic acids. *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids*, 55(2), 196-217.
- [10] Saini, N., Yadav, J. S., Jangra, S. K., Sharma, D., & Sharma, V. K. (2011). Thermodynamic studies of molecular interactions in mixtures of o-toulidine with pyridine and picolines: excess molar volumes, excess molar enthalpies, and excess isentropic compressibilities. *The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics*, 43(5), 782-795.
- [11] Siddharthan, N., & Jayakumar, S. (2016). Theoretical evaluation of sound velocity, viscosity and density of binary liquid system. *Int. J. Chem. Sci*, 14(4).
- [12] Sulthana, S. P., Gowrisankar, M., Babu, S., & Santos, D. (2022). Investigation of ketonic effect in molecular interactions of 2-methylcyclohexanone with aniline, N-methyl aniline and N, N-dimethyl aniline at various temperatures. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*, 43(1), 894-904.
- [13] Thirumaran, S., & Ramesh, J. (2009). Acoustic and excess thermodynamical studies on 1-alkanols with DMA in cyclohexanone at different temperatures. *Rasayan J Chem*, 2, 733-739.
- [14] Awasthi, A., Rastogi, M., & Shukla, J. P. (2004). Ultrasonic and IR study of molecular association process through hydrogen bonding in ternary liquid mixtures. *Fluid phase equilibria*, 215(2), 119-127.
- [15] Karunakar, T., & Srinivas, C. H. (2013). Thermo acoustic and infrared study of molecular interactions in binary mixture aniline+ 1-butanol. *Res. Rev.: J. Pure Appl. Phys*, 1, 5-15.
- [16] Shihab, S. S., Babu, S., & Sastry, S. S. (2016). Experimental and theoretical studies of speed of sound and viscosity in some liquid mixtures of Methyl Benzoate: a comparative study. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 9(4).
- [17] Nomoto, O. (1958). Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures. *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan*, 13(12), 1528-1532.

[18] Van Dael, W., & Vangeel, E. (1975). Theory of ultrasound. *Van Deal W. Thermodynamic properties and velocity of sound*, London: Butterworth.

[19] Junjie, Z. (1984). Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Benzene. *J. China Univ. Sci. Technol*, 14, 298-299.

CHAPTER-5

Speed of sound and Viscosity theories of benzoate liquid mixtures

This work was reported at Industrial Engineering Journal, 52(9), 2023

http://www.journal-iiie india.com/1_sep_23.html

International Journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research, 12(02)

365-368 (2023)

DOI: [10.48047/IJIEMR/V12/ISSUE_02/57](https://doi.org/10.48047/IJIEMR/V12/ISSUE_02/57)

INTRODUCTION:

Measurement of speed of sound gives the valuable information about the physicochemical behavior of the fluid and fluid mixtures. Several empirical relations and theories are available for the theoretical computation of speed of sound and viscosity in fluid and fluid mixtures. They are broadly used in perfumery and pesticides. The benzenes are a widely used industrial chemical. Benzene is found in crude oil and is a major part of gasoline. It's used to make metabolites, plastics, resins, synthetic fibers, rubber lubricants, dyes, detergents and pharmacy. The amides of commercial importance are acetamide, also called formamide and dimethylformamide, which are used as solvents, sulfa drugs and nylons and *amines* play important roles in many drugs, cosmetics, detergents, plastics, and antimicrobials. In present study the authors want to observe the molecular interactions between the similar featured fluids using speed of sound and viscosity theories. [1, 3]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Speed of sound theories: The prognostic artistries of speeds of sound theories based upon the brawn of interactivity persuading in a framework. The deviation in upshots may be ascribed to the précised made in these theories for the odd-odd speaks interactivities between the notes in the whole captivation. This implies the impedance relation (UIMP) and Nomoto (UNMR) and reveals merit of concurrence among theoretical to measured data. The measured values of speed of sound along with their theoretically determined values of Nomoto's, Ideal mixing, Junjie's,

Vandael & Vangel and Rao's [4-7] with mole fraction in the twofold fluid blends of amides/amines + benzoates at three different temperatures were noticed at table (1 & 2). The APE and chi square test (χ) is also included for the individual twofold blends. U for both real and framework increases/decreases with ρ and z compliance with mole fraction. This drift is due to own alliance of solvent molecules have more strong dipole- induced interactions between the molecules. For sound procreation Eyring and Kincaid [14] was proposed that U should increase/decrease with alteration of Lf decreases in mixing of speaks.

On other side, slight changes in Junjie UJN, Rao's (UR) and Vandael & Vangel (UVDV) relations. This type of alterations are presumed in the blends due to volume variation after fluid mixing, also there is much deviation in theoretical prediction of U with measured data recommend the exits of solid inclination for the relationship between the segment atoms because of hydrogen bond in the mix.

The Chi-square and APE values are less for all these theories. These upshots are used to judge non-ideality behavior in the fluid blends and it can also perceive the mote ally with positive/negative alteration in ' U ' specifies atomic dissociation/ association of species by heap of solvent. Regarding this behavior of twofold blends implies positive digression in ' U ' accredits elastic nature of spherical motes is liable for the atomic coalition. [2]

Viscosity theories: The standard deviation is small in all systems where the interactions are less there exists strong interactions between mixes. This shows that, the envisage flair of various viscosity theories depend upon the strength interplay prevailing in a system. The experimental and theoretical viscosity values of Gruenberg-Nissan model, Hind rule, Arrhenius equation, Wijk and Kendall-Monroe relations [9-13] for p-MBA /E-4-HB systems are presented in table (3&4) along with interaction parameters and standard deviations. On all of these models fairly predicted viscosity theories, they are reasonably close to the measured values for the twofold mix reported in this work, this showing the validity of studied theoretic models for twofold mix. Out of all equations used to correlate measured data of mix viscosity standard deviation calculated using Wijk and Hind is lower than other theories. Hence, Hind and Wijk theories are more convenient and fit well for this mix. [8]

Table 1: Speed of sound theories for the binary system of E -4-HB with aniline/o-Chloro aniline at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

X_1	U_{EXP} $m.s^{-1}$	U_{NOM} $m.s^{-1}$	U_{IMR} $m.s^{-1}$	U_{JM} $m.s^{-1}$	U_{VDV} $m.s^{-1}$	U_R $m.s^{-1}$
E-4-HB + Aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4
0.2136	1318.2	1318.2	1314.0	1316.6	1318.8	1312.2
0.4547	1398.6	1394.0	1397.4	1391.2	1396.6	1389.2
0.6493	1454.6	1454.2	1452.6	1451.8	1458.4	1456.0
0.8753	1507.4	1507.8	1504.6	1507.4	1507.4	1507.4
1.0000	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6
APE		0.0006	0.0052	0.0013	0.0058	0.0149
chi square(χ)		0.0046	0.0622	0.0038	0.0613	0.1714
308.15 K						
0.0000	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4
0.2136	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2
0.4547	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8
0.6493	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4
0.8753	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6
1.0000	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6
APE		0.0015	0.0057	0.0011	0.0050	0.0165
chi square(χ)		0.0054	0.0674	0.0035	0.0647	0.1239
313.15K						
0.0000	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4
0.2136	1248.8	1248.2	1241.8	1240.8	1239.6	1249.6
0.4547	1378.2	1378.6	1373.4	1371.6	1381.0	1376.8
0.6493	1464.6	1464.0	1462.8	1468.0	1470.8	1461.4
0.8753	1544.2	1544.8	1541.6	1547.4	1539.4	1549.0

0.2032	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2
0.4150	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6
0.6344	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8
0.8576	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
APE		0.0004	0.0036	0.0008	0.0036	0.0022
chi square(χ)		0.0042	0.0397	0.0084	0.0397	0.0247
p-MBA+DMF						
303.15K						
0.0000	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4
0.2731	1486.2	1486.2	1481.2	1485.2	1486.0	1480.2
0.4407	1508.6	1508.6	1506.6	1503.0	1501.2	1518.2
0.6993	1524.8	1524.8	1529.8	1527.2	1523.6	1531.8
0.8139	1541.4	1541.4	1540.4	1543.6	1544.8	1544.6
1.0000	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2
APE		0.0006	0.0044	0.0004	0.0077	0.0167
Chi square(χ)		0.0059	0.0812	0.0052	0.0739	0.1296
308.15K						
0.0000	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4
0.2731	1468.6	1468.2	1463.6	1464.6	1461.0	1466.2
0.4407	1494.8	1494.8	1492.2	1497.2	1495.6	1490.6
0.6993	1512.2	1512.0	1516.8	1511.8	1515.8	1520.4
0.8139	1522.4	1522.4	1521.4	1526.2	1502.4	1526.8
1.0000	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6
APE		0.0008	0.0068	0.0006	0.0071	0.0137
Chi square(χ)		0.0050	0.0719	0.0021	0.0608	0.1449
313.15 K						
0.0000	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4
0.2731	1458.6	1458.2	1454.6	1451.0	1456.6	1450.6

0.4407	1482.2	1482.4	1483.4	1484.6	1487.0	1485.8
0.6993	1504.8	1504.0	1507.2	1506.2	1509.2	1505.2
0.8139	1514.6	1514.8	1511.8	1517.8	1518.8	1511.0
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
	APE	0.0007	0.0038	0.0005	0.0063	0.0286
	Chi square(χ)	0.0049	0.0477	0.0029	0.0576	0.1568

Table 3 Viscosity theories for the binary system of E -4-HB with aniline/o-Chloro aniline at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

x_1	η_{Exp} (mPas)	Hind (mPas)	Gruenberg- Nissan (mPas)	Wijk (mPas)	Arrhenius (mPas)	Kendall- Monroe equation (mPas)
E-4-HB + aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234
0.2136	2.106	2.106	2.104	2.108	2.105	2.107
0.4547	1.968	1.968	1.967	1.964	1.962	1.961
0.6493	1.663	1.663	1.665	1.667	1.666	1.668
0.8753	1.419	1.419	1.418	1.416	1.412	1.415
1.0000	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286
	Interaction parameter	1.114	0.434	1.163	2.209	2.064
	Standard deviation(σ)	0.232	0.318	0.501	0.525	0.226
308.15 K						
0.0000	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943
0.2136	1.761	1.761	1.763	1.764	1.765	1.768
0.4547	1.594	1.594	1.597	1.596	1.598	1.595
0.6493	1.375	1.375	1.376	1.372	1.371	1.376
0.8753	1.258	1.258	1.251	1.256	1.257	1.252

Interaction parameter		2.043	2.145	2.362	1.351	0.987
Standard deviation(σ)		0.136	0.437	0.641	0.726	0.981
			313.15 K			
	0.0000	3.105	3.105	3.105	3.105	3.105
	0.2367	2.962	2.962	2.967	2.969	2.963
	0.4158	2.549	2.549	2.546	2.543	2.546
	0.6304	1.954	1.954	1.955	1.958	1.957
	0.8786	1.627	1.627	1.624	1.623	1.625
	1.0000	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172
Interaction parameter		2.046	2.214	2.410	1.839	1.256
Standard deviation(σ)		0.082	0.138	0.363	0.565	0.728

Table 4 Viscosity theories for the binary system of p-MBA with formamide/DMF at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

x_1	η_{Exp} (mPas)	Hind (mPas)	Gruenberg- Nissan (mPas)	Wijk (mPas)	Arrhenius (mPas)	Kendall- Monroe equation (mPas)
p-MBA + Formamide						
303.15 K						
0.0000	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782
0.2032	2.425	2.425	2.428	2.422	2.429	2.426
0.4150	2.193	2.193	2.196	2.195	2.198	2.197
0.6344	1.968	1.968	1.962	1.961	1.965	1.960
0.8576	1.749	1.747	1.742	1.741	1.740	1.746
1.0000	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583
Interaction parameter		1.174	0.504	1.046	2.829	2.260
Standard deviation(σ)		0.263	0.358	0.651	0.725	0.462
308.15 K						

0.0000	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465
0.2032	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139
0.4150	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965
0.6344	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648
0.8576	1.672	1.672	1.675	1.677	1.676	1.670
1.0000	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424
Interaction parameter		1.071	0.446	0.905	2.484	2.467
Standard deviation(σ)		0.162	0.204	0.416	0.878	0.621
313.15 K						
0.0000	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254
0.2032	2.017	2.017	2.015	2.014	2.010	2.018
0.4150	1.872	1.872	1.874	1.877	1.879	1.876
0.6344	1.640	1.640	1.643	1.646	1.648	1.640
0.8576	1.526	1.526	1.522	1.527	1.524	1.525
1.0000	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345
Interaction parameter		0.962	0.207	0.715	2.250	2.234
Standard deviation(σ)		0.107	0.108	0.319	0.902	0.746
p-MBA + DMF						
303.15 K						
0.0000	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772
0.2731	0.923	0.923	0.926	0.925	0.928	0.924
0.4407	1.234	1.234	1.232	1.236	1.237	1.235
0.6993	1.412	1.412	1.414	1.418	1.416	1.417
0.8139	1.523	1.523	1.525	1.527	1.528	1.526
1.0000	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583
Interaction parameter		1.082	1.004	0.972	0.875	0.807
Standard deviation(σ)		0.104	0.127	0.209	0.310	0.093
308.15 K						
0.0000	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735

	0.2731	0.893	0.893	0.895	0.897	0.896	0.898
	0.4407	1.127	1.127	1.124	1.126	1.125	1.129
	0.6993	1.262	1.262	1.267	1.264	1.268	1.269
	0.8139	1.356	1.356	1.353	1.358	1.351	1.357
	1.0000	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424
Interaction parameter			1.043	1.155	1.669	1.351	0.973
Standard deviation(σ)			0.083	0.039	0.014	0.120	0.140
				313.15 K			
	0.0000	0.682	0.682	0.682	0.682	0.682	0.682
	0.2731	0.812	0.812	0.814	0.815	0.816	0.817
	0.4407	0.966	0.966	0.967	0.965	0.968	0.963
	0.6993	1.121	1.121	1.124	1.126	1.127	1.125
	0.8139	1.249	1.249	1.247	1.245	1.246	1.248
	1.0000	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345
Interaction parameter			1.017	0.994	0.817	0.639	0.560
Standard deviation(σ)			0.016	0.008	0.063	0.015	0.007

CONCLUSION

The deliberated values of speed of sound and viscosity from several theories have been correlated with the measured values. Speed of sound values obtained from Nomoto's and Vandael & Vangel relations are in good concurrence with the measured values. The Chi square values also support these upshots and the observed deviation of theoretical values of speed of sound from the experimental values is attributed to the presence of intermolecular interactions. The experimental values of viscosity are also correlated with the empirical relations of viscosity and these are in good agreement with the experimental values. It may be concluded that out of these theories, Nomoto's relation in the speed of sound Grunberg-Nissan is in the viscosity were the best suited relation for all the fluid mixtures.

REFERENCES

1. Chinnarao, Dharmana, Ch V. Padmarao, Ch Beena, M. Srilatha, M. V. V. Ramanjaneyulu, Praveen Choppara, N. Murali, and B. Venkateswara Rao(2023). "Acoustic, excess thermodynamical, molecular interaction and antimicro-bial activity studies on binary liquid mixtures of geranyl acetate and benzyl benzoate in the temperature range of 303.15 K–318.15 K." *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* 100(5) 100969.
2. Nagarjuna, A., KV Yamini Kanth, G. Balaji Prakash, and Debashis Das.(2019) "Molecular interactions in binary liquid, mixtures containing benzyl benzoate." *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry* 12,(4).
3. Pandey, J. D., V. Vyas, P. Jain, G. P. Dubey, N. Tripathi, and R. Dey. "Speed of sound, viscosity and refractive index of multicomponent systems: theoretical predictions from the properties of pure components." *Journal of molecular liquids* 81, no. 2 (1999): 123-133.
4. Shihab, Sk Suriya, Shaik Babu, and S. Sreehari Sastry.(2016) "Experimental and theoretical studies of speed of sound and viscosity in some liquid mixtures of Methyl Benzoate: a comparative study." *Rasayan Journal of chemistry* ,9(4)

5. Nomoto, Otohiko.(1958) "Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures. " *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* 13(12) ,1528-1532.
6. Van Dael, W., and E. Vangeel.(1975) "Theory of ultrasound." *Thermodynamic properties and velocity of sound, London: Butterworth* .
7. Junjie,Z(1984)."Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of benzene” *J. China Univ. Sci.Technol.* 14 298-299.
8. Isakovich,M. A.,and I.A.Chaban.(1966) "Propagation of sound in strongly viscous liquids” *Sov.Phys. JETP* 23 ,893-905.
9. Grunberg,LaAHN, and Alfred H. Nissan.(1949) "Mixture law for viscosity." *Nature* 164, 4175 , 799-800.
10. Hind, R. K.,E. McLaughlin,and A.R. Ubbelohde.(1960) "Structure and viscosity of liquids. Camphor+ pyrene mixtures"*Transactions of the Faraday Society* 56 ,328-330.
11. Katti, P. K., and M. M. Chaudhri.(1964) "Viscosities of Binary Mixtures of Benzyl Acetate with Dioxane, Aniline, and m-Cresol." *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* 9, (3) 442-443.
12. Siddharthan, N., and S. Jayakumar. (2016)"Theoretical evaluation of sound velocity, viscosity and density of binary liquid system." *Int. J. Chem. Sci* 14, 4
13. Tamura, Mikio, and Michio Kurata.(1952) "On the viscosity of binary mixture of liquids” *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan* 25, (1) 32-38.
14. Kincaid, John F., and Henry Eyring.(1938) "Free volumes and free angle ratios of molecules in liquids." *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 6, (10) 620-629.
15. Nagarjuna, A., Kvsn Raju, P. Arunkumar, and N. Kotilingaiah.(2022) "Volumetric studies on ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate with substituted amide liquid mixtures at different temperatures." *Neuro Quantology* 20 (1),1769-1777
16. Nagarjuna, A., Kvsn Raju, N. Kotilingaiah, and BM Praveen.(2023) "comparitive study of binary liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoate acid and amides." *European Chem . Bulletin*, 12 (SI6), 3395 – 3407

FUTURE PLAN OF WORK

- ♣ Plan to apply different density theories to the combinations.
- ♣ Other viscosity theories like three body and four body models can be applied.
- ♣ Partial properties can be evaluated for different ranges of compositions and temperatures.
- ♣ Measurements based on frequencies can be performed by ultrasonic technique.
- ♣ Higher homologous series of ionic liquids, amides, amines and benzoates can be considered.
- ♣ Perform our research using dielectric, XRD & NMR studies.

Speed of Sound Studies of Ethyl-4-hydroxy Benzoate with Formamide at Different Temperatures

Dr A. Nagarjuna^{1*}, Dr K.V.S. N Raju², Dr Shaik. S Begum³, Dr B.M Praveen⁴

^{1,2} PDF Scholar, Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Physics, Krishna University, Machilipatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

⁴Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka- 574146, India

Corresponding author: dranagarjunaphysics@tkrec.ac.in

Abstract: Record the measured values of densities (ρ) and speed of sounds (U) for the mixture of Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate(E-4HB) with formamide (FA) from temperature 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K. Several speed of sound theories like nomoto relation, ideal mixing relation, impedance relation, vangeel and vandael relation, rao's specific velocity relation and junjie relation have been determine and collate to measured values. By apply the chi-square test (χ) and average percentage error (APE) use to check validity of these theories. The upshots are discussing in-terms of in-tera molecule attractions betwixt the particles in two-fold mix.

Keywords: Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate, chi-square test, average percentage error, two-fold mix

Introduction

Conceptual assessment of ultrasonic velocity in binary liquid mixes and correlation with actual results represent molecular interaction in liquid mixtures, which is extremely helpful to construct thorough theoretical models for fluids [1,3]. Studying how compounds interact with different functional groups on these substances is essential to comprehending how protons behave.

The experimental speed of sound values in the current research were correlated with a number of semi-empirical formulas, including Nomoto's relationship, Ideal mixing relation, Impedance dependence relation, Rao velocity relation, and Junjie's method (referred to as "formulas 1-6") for the binary mixtures of E-4HB and FA.

Additionally, the mean percentage of error (APE) and chi-square test (χ) are use to

identify the best hypothesis that fits the particular chemical system under study.

Experimental

Standard procedures were followed to measure the density (ρ) and speed of sound (U)for the compounds of E-4HB with FA. All that measurement was done at 303.15K, 308.15K and 313.15K temperatures. Collation of measured and literature was given ion table 01

Table 01 Collation of measured with literature values of pure fluids

Name of the fluid	Temperature(K)	Density (Kg m ⁻³)		Speed of sound (m s ⁻¹)	
		Literature	Measured	Literature	Measured
E-4-HB	303.15 K	1.1035 ^a	1.1035	1523.0 ^a	1522.4
	308.15K	1.0313 ^a	1.0312	1541.4 ^a	1543.2

	313.15K	0.9973 ^a	0.9977	1572.6 ^a	1571.6
Formamide	303.15 K	1.1257 ^b	1.1252	1588.0 ^b	1586.6
	308.15K	1.1198 ^b	1.1187	1577.2 ^b	1574.4
	313.15K	1.1183 ^b	1.1179	1568.0 ^b	1567.2

^a Reference [12] ^b Reference [13]

Results and Discussion

The comparative values of amide and E-4HB at 313.15K is differ to other two temperatures because of less variation in density data at high pressure for Table 4.

The correlation of measured to determined values using several equations like Nomoto's relation [11], ideal mixing relation, impedance dependence relation [16], Vandal and Vangeel [14], Rao's velocity relation [2], Junjie method [15] for the systems of E-4HB.

Where,
 (n-1) degrees of freedom
 n- no. of data use.

U_{mix} (obs) = experimental values of speed of sound and

U_{mix} (cal) = calculate values of speed of sound.

with FA for three temperatures are reported in Table 2,3 & 4. The validity check of these theories by applying Chi-square test and by calculating average percentage error.

Chi-square test for goodness of fit

$$(x^2) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(U_{mix(obs)} - U_{mix(cal)})^2}{U_{mix(cal)}}$$

Average percentage error (APE)

$$APE = \frac{1}{n} \sum \frac{(U_{mix(obs)} - U_{mix(cal)})}{U_{mix(obs)}} \times 100\%$$

Table2. Speed of sound studies for E-4HB with FA at 303.15Ktemperature

X ₁	U _{EXP}	U _{NOM}	U _{IMR}	U _{IMP}	U _{JM}	U _{VDV}	U _R
0.0000	1586.6	1586.6	1586.6	1586.6	1586.6	1586.6	1586.6
0.1108	1580.2	1578.2	1576.4	1577.4	1578.8	1581.4	1579.4
0.2856	1574.4	1573.6	1573.2	1572.6	1574.2	1576.8	1574.8
0.3757	1571.6	1569.4	1570.6	1571.2	1570.8	1573.4	1572.2
0.4130	1568.0	1564.6	1563.4	1566.2	1564.8	1570.4	1569.8
0.5604	1561.4	1560.6	1562.2	1561.4	1560.4	1563.4	1562.6
0.6227	1554.8	1553.4	1555.6	1554.2	1553.0	1557.6	1556.2
0.7083	1548.6	1546.6	1542.4	1544.6	1546.8	1549.8	1549.2
0.8332	1537.8	1538.4	1536.6	1539.2	1538.6	1540.2	1539.4
0.9323	1528.6	1527.6	1526.4	1524.8	1527.4	1530.2	1529.6
1.0000	1522.4	1522.4	1522.4	1522.4	1522.4	1522.4	1522.4
APE		0.0290	0.0292	0.0291	0.0289	0.0295	-0.0293
CHITEST(x)		16.8166	17.1329	16.9744	16.7773	17.3718	17.2123

Table3. Speed of sound studies for E-4HB with FA at 308.15Ktemperature

X ₁	U _{EXP}	U _{NOM}	U _{IMR}	U _{IMP}	U _{JM}	U _{VDV}	U _R
0.0000	1574.4	1574.4	1574.4	1574.4	1574.4	1574.4	1574.4
0.1108	1570.2	1570.6	1571.2	1572.6	1571.4	1572.2	1571.8
0.2856	1567.8	1566.4	1568.6	1567.4	1567.6	1569.4	1568.2
0.3757	1562.4	1563.6	1564.4	1563.8	1563.0	1564.8	1562.8

0.4130	1560.8	1561.4	1560.8	1562.2	1561.8	1562.6	1561.6
0.5604	1558.4	1559.2	1557.4	1557.8	1558.8	1559.8	1558.6
0.6227	1555.6	1556.2	1555.8	1556.4	1554.6	1556.8	1555.4
0.7083	1552.0	1553.4	1554.6	1552.8	1553.2	1552.6	1553.8
0.8332	1549.6	1548.6	1547.4	1546.4	1548.8	1550.4	1549.4
0.9323	1546.2	1545.4	1544.8	1546.2	1547.4	1548.2	1547.6
1.0000	1543.2	1543.2	1543.2	1543.2	1543.2	1543.2	1543.2
APE		0.0287	0.0284	0.0285	0.0286	0.0288	-0.0286
CHITEST(x)		16.5420	16.1920	16.2695	16.4640	16.6595	16.4250

The foretelling aptness of several speed of sound analysis depends upon brown of interplay in a module. The deliberate values of speed of sound studies at three different temperatures are collated with measured values and it shows some deviations because the density of mixture will increase with increase of warmth and mass of sample.

When two fluids are mixed, the interplay between the molecules takes place because presence of several forces such as, charge transfer, dispersive force, dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole inter-activity, this is another important cause for deviation from observed to theoretical studies of Speed of sound. Not only these effects are sufficient to taken into account in these theories because the chi square value also and APE correlate at three temperatures, in these chi upshots most intuitive at IMP's relation. When compared to others chi value of JM and VDV values at three temperatures gives high it purely stipulates weaker bonding betwixt them. Further APE value gets right values at all temperatures except Rao's value. It gives negative, this deviation shows that particles interactivity take's place between, unlike molecules in the fluid mixture. The extent of digression may be attribute to assumptions put together in these theories for the nonpolar-polar and nonpolar-nonpolar interplay between the mites.[16]

Many of digressions are observed in some of intermediate congregation range this suggests that subsistence of tight proclivity for molecular inter play betwixt mix and as effects sturdy H-bonding takes place. [4,5,6,7,8,9,10]

Table4. Speed of sound studies for E-4HB with FA at 313.15Ktemperature

X1	U _{exp}	U _{NOM}	U _{IMR}	U _{IMP}	U _{JM}	U _{VDV}	U _R
0.0000	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6
0.1108	1570.8	1570.6	1570.4	1570.6	1570.8	1571.2	1571.4
0.2856	1570.2	1570.4	1570.4	1570.8	1570.6	1571.4	1570.6
0.3757	1569.8	1569.4	1569.6	1569.4	1569.8	1570.2	1569.8
0.4130	1569.4	1569.0	1569.0	1569.4	1569.6	1569.8	1569.2
0.5604	1569.0	1569.0	1569.0	1569.2	1569.4	1569.8	1569.0
0.6227	1568.6	1568.4	1568.2	1568.4	1568.6	1568.8	1568.4
0.7083	1568.4	1568.2	1568.2	1568.0	1568.4	1568.6	1568.0
0.8332	1568.0	1568.0	1568.0	1568.0	1568.0	1568.4	1568.0
0.9323	1567.8	1567.2	1567.2	1567.4	1567.6	1567.4	1567.2
1.0000	1567.6	1567.6	1567.6	1567.6	1567.6	1567.6	1567.6
APE		0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0306	-0.0305
CHITEST(x)		18.5062	18.5062	18.5473	18.5884	18.6708	18.5062

Conclusion

Measured values of speed of sound at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K for the binary mixtures of E-4HB with formamide are correlated to various relations. It may be concluded that impedance IMP's relation and NOM's relation are best suited for all the binary mixtures also VDV relation give higher deviation under study. The APE and Chi square values also support these upshots.

Acknowledgement

Authors A. Nagarjuna is thankful to his supervisor Dr. B.M Praveen, Research and innovation Cell Srinivas University, Mangalore for his valuable suggestions and discussions.

References

- [1] J. Glory, P.S Naidu, N. Jaya madhuri and K. Ravindra Prasad, "Study of Ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity in the binary mixtures of Benzyl benzoate with 1-octanol and Iso phorone", Research & Reviews :Journal of pure and applied physics, vol.1 ,no.2, p 5, 2013
- [2] N.Jayamadhuri, J.Glory, P.S Naidu and K. Ravindra Prasad, "Ultrasonic investigations of molecular interactions in binary mixtures of Benzyl benzoate with

acetonitrile and benzonitrile”, E-journal of chemistry, vol 8, no 1, p. 457, 2011

[3] S.V.Kumara Sastry, Shaik. Babu, Ha. Sie Tiong and S. Sreehari Sastry, “Ultrasonic investigation of molecular interactions in ternary mixtures at 303 K”, Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research, vol. 4, no 4, p. 2122, 2012

[4] K.Rajagopal and S.Chenthilnath, “Excess thermodynamic studies in ternary liquid mixtures of 2-methyl-2-propanol and cyclohexanone with ketones at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K”, Journal of Molecular Liquids, vol.155,no.1,p. 20,2010

[5] kun liu, Frank schuch and Erdogen kiran, “High pressure viscosity and density of poly (methyl methacrylate) + acetone and poly (methyl methacrylate) + acetone + CO₂ systems”, The journal of Supercritical fluids ,vol.39,no.1, p. 89,2006

[6] Sk. Md Nayeem, Imran khan, and D.Krishna rao, “Investigations of molecular interactions in binary mixture (benzyl benzoate + ethyl acetate) at T=308.15,313.15 and 318.15)K an insight from ultrasonic speed of sound and density”, Journal of molecular liquids ,vol.218,p.676,2016

[7] T.Karunakar, CH Srinivasu and K Narendra, “Thermoacoustic and infrared study of Molecular interactions in Binary mixture Aniline + 1-Butanol”, Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol .1, no.1, p.5,2013

[8] G. Ganapathi Rao, M.V.K. Mehar, K.V. Prasad and K. Samatha, “Ultrasonic Studies and Excess Properties of Binary Mixtures of Ethyl methyl ketone and Chlorobenzene At 308.15K”, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, vol.4, no.7, p.5512, 2015

[9] JD.Pandey, AK.Singh and Ranjan Dey, “Novel approach for prediction of ultrasonic velocity in quaternary liquid mixtures”, Pramana Journal of Physics, Indian Academy of Sciences, vol.64,no.1,p. 135, 2005

[10] Shaik.Babu S.V.Kumara Sastry, Ha.Sie Tiong, S.Sreehari Sastry,” Experimental and Theoretical Studies of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Ethyl Benzoate”, E-Journal of Chemistry , vol.9,no.4, p.2309,2012

[11] O. Nomoto , "Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures" Journal

of the Physical Society of Japan, vol.13, no 12, p.1528,1958

[12] A. Nagarjuna and S Babu,” Spectroscopic and volumetric study of binary liquid mixtures containing Ethyl - 4-hydroxy benzoate and alkanols”, Chemical Data Collections, vol.26, p.100347,2020

[13] A.Nagarjuna,K.L Yamini Kanth and G. Balaji Prakash, “Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures containing benzyl benzoate”,Rasayan Journal of Chemistry, vol.12, no14 , p.1774,2019

[14] W.Van Dael W and E.Vangeel , Proceeding of first International Conference on calorimetry and thermodynamics, Warsaw, p.555,1955

[15] Z.Junjie , “Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Benzene”, Journal of university of science and technology of china., vol.14, p.298,1984

[16] Shaik. Babu,” Theoretical prediction of Ultrasonic velocity in binary liquid mixtures”, E-Journal of chemistry, vol.8 no 1., p.330, 2011

COMPARITIVE STUDY OF BINARY LIQUID MIXTURES CONTAINING P-METHOXY BENZOATE ACID AND AMIDES

A. NAGARJUNA^{1*,2}, K.V.S. N RAJU^{1,3}, N. KOTILINGAIAH⁴, B.M PRAVEEN⁵

¹PDF Scholar, Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

²Department of Physics, TKR Engineering College (Autonomous), Medowli, Meerpet, Hyderabad-500097, India

³Department of Physics, Adikavi Nannaya University, Tadepalligudem, West godavari-534101, Andhra Pradesh, India

⁴Department of Chemistry, TKR Engineering College (Autonomous), Medowli, Meerpet, Hyderabad-500097, India

⁵Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka- 574146, India

Corresponding author: ayachitulanagarjuna@gmail.com

doi: 10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.302

ABSTRACT

The Speed of sound, density and viscosity values of binary mixtures containing P-methoxy benzoic acid (P-MBA) with Amides -Formamide, Di methyl formamide(DMF) and N-Methyl formamide (NMF) are measured from 303.15 K to 313.15K (5K interval) temperatures using standard techniques. Several thermo acoustic parameters like molar volume (V_m), isentropic compressibility (K_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), acoustic impedance (Z), surface tension (γ) and their excess parameters have been calculated from the measured values. These excess parameters have been fitted to Redlich–Kister type polynomial equation using the least square method. The determined values of partial and excess partial molar volumes ($\bar{v}_{m,1}$, $\bar{v}_{m,2}$) and ($\bar{v}_{m,1}^E$, $\bar{v}_{m,2}^E$) are drawn from V_m^E . Finally, FT-IR spectra of these mixtures at different mole fractions were carried out to analyze the hydrogen bonding formation between the molecules in terms of intra or intermolecular relations.

Keywords: Binary liquid mixtures, redlich-kister polynomial, FTIR spectroscopy, excess parameters, measured values

INTRODUCTION

Pure fluids and fluid blends used in this study are effective preservatives in many varieties like antimicrobial food preservative, antifungal as well as antiseptic agents, solvents as cosmetic and perfumery industries and also acts as metabolites in pharmaceutical industries. P-Methoxy benzoic acid ($C_8H_8O_3$) has antiseptic property and it is soluble in water, alcohols, and ethyl acetate because it is available in powder form. It is also known as P-anisic acid and draconic acid. P-Methoxy benzoic acid has a boiling of about 280 °C and a melting of 184 °C,

it is a metabolite of aniracetam. Measurement of density and ultrasonic velocity in binary liquid mixtures and its observed results of excess values reflects the molecular interaction in liquid mixtures, which is very useful to build comprehensive calculations like RK polynomials/partial molar volumes for the considered liquids. Similar kinds of results were obtained by the earlier workers [1-3] carried out variety of research investigations on the liquid mixtures. The effects shown by the molecules with other functional groups on these molecules plays a vital role in understanding the behavior of hydrogen bonding in the considered mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

P-methoxy benzoic acid (Hi Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India) is available in powder form. It was soluble in water with the mixture of 530 mg/1Lr at room temperature.

The binary liquid mixtures were prepared just before start the experiment for different samples with the help of mass variation. The uncertainty in the final mole fraction was estimated to be less than ± 0.0001 . The speed of sound was measured at 303.15K to 313.15K using ultrasonic interferometer (M/s Mittal Enterprises, India) operating at a fixed frequency of 2 MHz with an accuracy of ± 0.1 m/s. for the binary systems of P-MBA with formamide, DMF and NMF.

The densities of the pure components and their multi components were measured with 10 mL of specific gravity bottle in high accurate digital electronic balance (BajinathPremnath SF 400A, Kanpur, U.P) with an accuracy of ± 0.02 mg.

The viscosities of pure and compounds for the binary systems of P-MBA with formamide, DMF and NMF were measured with an Ostwald viscometer with an accuracy of 0.1%. The precision of experimentally measured values of density, viscosity, and speed of sound data was compared with their literature values are shown in Table 01

Table 1: Comparison of measured to literature values of pure liquids

Liquid	Temp (K)	Density(ρ) kg m ³		Viscosity(η) mPa s		Speed of sound(U) m.s ⁻¹		C _p J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	α k K ⁻¹
		lit	Expt	lit	Expt	lit	Expt		
P-Methoxy benzoic acid (a)	303.15	1.1896	1.1886	1.585	1.581	1559.6	1557.2	204.07	1.0004
	308.15	1.1226	1.1246	1.428	1.422	1539.6	1532.6	205.03	1.0013
	313.15	1.0956	1.0966	1.341	1.346	1520.6	1524.4	205.00	1.0028
Formamide (b)	303.15	1.1257	1.1255	2.877	2.784	1588.0	1584.6	107.11	0.9962
	308.15	1.1198	1.1197	2.500	2.461	1577.2	1581.4	105.20	0.9966
	313.15	1.1183	1.1186	2.273	2.251	1568.0	1564.0	108.56	0.9992
NMF (b)	303.15	0.9946	0.9944	1.585	1.566	1408.5	1408.4	124.95	0.9988
	308.15	0.9903	0.9902	1.462	1.474	1400.6	1401.6	126.05	0.9964
	313.15	0.9861	0.9858	1.352	1.361	1382.2	1393.2	129.47	1.0042
DMF (b)	303.15	0.9476	0.9468	0.767	0.770	1459.6	1454.2	152.00	1.0034
	308.15	0.9421	0.9419	0.726	0.732	1434.7	1431.8	153.02	1.0011
	313.15	0.9351	0.9343	0.679	0.681	1420.8	1417.6	157.14	1.0022

(a) Reference [4] (b) Reference [5]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The excess thermo-acoustical parameters measure the system's non-ideality as a consequence of associative/other interactions between the molecules. Excess properties of studied binary systems at different mole fractions have been calculated from the experimental values of densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and speed of sounds (U) of P-methoxy benzoic acid with formamide, DMF and NMF at temperatures from $T = 303.15$ K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K determined [6] by the equations from (1) to (4)

$$V_m^E = X_1M_1 + X_2M_2/\rho - (X_1M_1/\rho_1 + X_2M_2/\rho_2) \quad (1)$$

$$K_s^E = K_s - K_s^{id} \quad (2)$$

Benson & Kiyohara [7] suggested a relation for calculating the ideal mixture K_s^{id}

$$K_s^{id} = \sum \phi_i \{K_s, i^0 + T V^{i0(\alpha_i)^2}/C_{p,i}^0\} - T(\sum X_i V_i^0)(\sum \phi_i \alpha_i^{0,2}/\sum X_i C_{p,i}^0) \quad (3)$$

$$L_f^E = L_f - K_T (K_s^{id})^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

K_T be a temperature dependent constant whose value is $91.368 + 0.3565 T \times 10^{-8}$

$$Z = U * \rho \quad (5)$$

$$(\chi) = 6.3 \times 10^{-4} \cdot \rho \cdot U^{3/2} \quad (6)$$

Where ρ is the density, U be the Speed of sound of the mixture and $X_1, X_2, M_1, M_2, \rho_1, \rho_2, Z_1, Z_2$ and χ_1, χ_2 are the mole fractions, molar mass, densities, acoustic impedances and surface tensions of actual compounds. In equation (3) $T, \alpha_i^0, C_{p,i}^0$, and ϕ_i be the Temperature, thermal expansion coefficient, isobaric molar heat capacity and volume fraction of i^{th} component.

Surface tension forces are due to intermolecular forces between the liquid's molecules at the liquid's outer boundaries. Surface tension is a principal factor in capillary action. The higher values over the whole composition for these systems can be suggested that strong molecular interactions are present in these mixtures because of density and acoustic impedance values are varies with mole fraction this results increase the speed of sound. Similar studies were observed for excess surface tension in the considered binary liquids. surface tension (χ) and acoustic impedance (Z) were determined with the help of equation (5,6) reported in Table 2

Table 2 Calculated values of surface tension (χ) and acoustic impedance (Z)

Mole fraction	PMBA+ FA		Mole fraction	PMBA + DMF		Mole fraction	PMBA + NMF	
	$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	$Z \times 10^3$ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	$Z \times 10^3$ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		$\chi \times 10^{-9}$ N m ⁻¹	$Z \times 10^3$ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹
303.15K								
0.0000	8.1948	1.0504	0.0000	8.2228	1.0604	0.0000	8.8460	1.1287
0.2322	8.8022	1.1884	0.2240	9.6492	1.2028	0.2523	9.1522	1.1523
0.4701	9.4501	1.2866	0.4761	10.4616	1.2921	0.4819	10.1538	1.2617
0.6342	10.1328	1.4270	0.6789	11.3744	1.3266	0.6524	11.1603	1.3295
0.8246	11.8998	1.5192	0.8332	13.2249	1.3667	0.8286	12.1517	1.3743
1.0000	12.2796	1.5358	1.0000	14.2151	1.3790	1.0000	13.2651	1.3840
308.15K								
0.0000	7.9459	1.0549	0.0000	7.9801	1.0842	0.0000	8.1746	1.1359
0.2322	8.9133	1.1984	0.2240	9.2562	1.2129	0.2523	8.7450	1.1644

0.4701	9.1142	1.2499	0.4761	10.0908	1.3013	0.4819	9.7632	1.2735
0.6342	9.9833	1.3676	0.6789	10.9623	1.3222	0.6524	10.7272	1.3160
0.8246	11.6549	1.5975	0.8332	12.5275	1.3499	0.8286	11.5844	1.3317
1.0000	11.9075	1.6099	1.0000	12.9050	1.3851	1.0000	12.4350	1.3553
313.15K								
0.0000	7.8777	1.0595	0.0000	7.7763	1.0618	0.0000	8.1729	1.1458
0.2322	9.3680	1.2672	0.2240	8.9450	1.2217	0.2523	8.4470	1.1705
0.4701	10.1396	1.3934	0.4761	9.7417	1.3128	0.4819	9.4347	1.2806
0.6342	10.8890	1.5667	0.6789	10.4494	1.3422	0.6524	10.2812	1.3085
0.8246	11.7179	1.6647	0.8332	11.7952	1.3775	0.8286	10.9259	1.3295
1.0000	12.1724	1.6724	1.0000	12.1341	1.3887	1.0000	12.6481	1.3967

The excess values for the above parameters were fitted to a Redlich- Kister type polynomial by the nonlinear Least – squares method [8]

$$Y^E = X_1 (1-X_1) \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (2 X_1 - 1)^{i-1} \quad (7)$$

Where $Y^E = K_s^E, V^E, L_f^E$. The values of coefficient A_i were determined by a regression analysis based on the least- squares method.

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = [\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{\text{exp}}^E - Y_{\text{cal}}^E)^2 / (D-N)]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

Where D is number of experimental data points and N is number of parameters

Fig. 1(a-c) Variation of **Excess isentropic compressibility** with respect to mole fraction of PMBA + FA/DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

Fig. 2(a-c) Variation of **Excess molar volume** with respect to mole fraction of PMBA + FA/DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

Fig 3(a-c) Variation of **Excess free length** with respect to mole fraction of PMBA +FA/DMF /NMF at three different temperatures.

The estimations of these abundance parameters K_s^E , V_m^E and L_f^E are fitted to the R-K type polynomial condition and the coefficients A_i are dictated by the strategy for least squares, these qualities alongside the estimations of (σ) are appeared in table 3

By watching the deviations in the estimations of abundance parameters for the blend of double fluid blends under scrutiny, we can foresee the quality of associations between the particles of fluid mixture [9]. The deviations in the estimations of these abundance parameters are because of a few contributing variables, they are (1) The various powers of collaboration between the atoms, similar to the charge move powers and development of hydrogen bonds between particles prompts negative/positive abundance values (2) Geometrical fitting of one atom in to the next because of the varieties fit as a fiddle and size of the particles of segment fluids, it is called structural contribution. (3) Physical inter atomic forces.

Table 3 Parameters of Redlich-Kister equation (A_k) and Standard Deviation (σ) for P-MBA with FA/DMF/ NMF at different temperatures

Parameter	Temperature (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
P-MBA + Formamide					
$10^{12}K_s^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	-2.6218	0.2923	1.8532	0.0431
	308.15	-3.0613	0.3064	0.9877	0.0498
	313.15	-3.4820	0.4105	0.0953	0.0610
$10^6 V_m^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	2.3742	-0.1227	-1.0137	0.6402
	308.15	2.7109	-0.0328	0.0471	0.8217
	313.15	3.0296	0.1104	1.0045	0.9956
$10^{13}L_f^E/(m)$	303.15	-0.2921	0.1350	0.0668	0.0029
	308.15	-0.2131	0.0945	0.0949	0.0028
	313.15	-0.1426	0.0605	0.0782	0.0020

P-MBA + DMF					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	-2.0012	-0.8225	3.1475	0.0409
	308.15	-2.6173	-0.5763	3.1322	0.0516
	313.15	-3.1030	-0.2168	2.3809	0.0532
$10^6 V_m^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	3.4078	0.4973	-3.2442	0.8963
	308.15	4.0893	0.5705	-2.1330	1.1268
	313.15	4.5663	1.5875	-1.2388	1.3810
$10^{13}L_f^E/ (m)$	303.15	-0.0215	-0.0047	0.0284	0.2708
	308.15	-0.0181	-0.0039	0.0276	0.3779
	313.15	-0.0276	-0.0064	0.0318	0.4595
P-MBA + NMF					
$10^{12}K_S^E/(m^2.N^{-1})$	303.15	-0.0153	0.0002	0.0052	0.3962
	308.15	-0.0242	0.0040	0.0041	0.4864
	313.15	-0.0273	0.0074	-0.0032	0.5778
$10^6 V_m^E/(m^3.mol^{-1})$	303.15	0.5758	0.1866	-0.3220	0.1384
	308.15	0.6614	-0.0137	0.0292	0.1456
	313.15	0.2921	0.0766	-0.2655	0.0668
$10^{13}L_f^E/ (m)$	303.15	-0.0143	-0.0019	0.0049	0.0478
	308.15	-0.0197	-0.0042	0.0053	0.0310
	313.15	-0.0219	-0.0053	0.0082	0.0188

From the treatment of excess thermo acoustic quantities for liquid mixtures proposed by Desnoyers and Perron [10] in agreement with the original statements of Redlich and Kister from equation (7), table 3 concludes that the excess quantity (K_S^E , L_f^E and V_m^E) gives the spring of upshots in the systems it shows the non-ideality in the mixtures but the values of (σ) are less than one that indicates strong interactions at huge suffusion.

The obtained values of partial molar volumes are reported in Table 4 by using the equations (9-12), also tabulated the infinite dilution values of partial molar volume and Excess partial molar volumes at infinite dilution in table 5.

The partial molar volumes for all the binary systems can be calculated using the formulae

$$\bar{V}_{m,1} = V_m^E + V_1^* + X_2(\delta V_m^E / \delta X)_{P,T} \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{V}_{m,2} = V_m^E + V_2^* + X_1(\delta V_m^E / \delta X)_{P,T} \quad (10)$$

Where $\bar{V}_{m,1}$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}$ are the partial molar volumes and V_1^* and V_2^* molar volumes of pure compounds.

The values of infinite dilution of partial and excess partial molar volumes for the binary system ($V_{m,1}^{E,\infty}$, $V_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$) can be calculated by the following relations.

$$V_{m,1}^{E,\infty} = A_0 + A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + \dots = V_{m,1}^{\infty} - V_1^* \quad (11)$$

$$V_{m,2}^{E,\infty} = A_0 - A_1 + A_2 - A_3 + \dots = V_{m,2}^{\infty} - V_2^* \quad (12)$$

Where A_0 , A_1 , A_2 , A_3 are the coefficients obtained from R-K polynomial equation

Table 4: Partial molar volumes for PMBA with FA/DMF /NMF at different temperatures

Mole fraction	PMBA + FA		Mole fraction	PMBA+ DMF		Mole fraction	PMBA + NMF	
	$\bar{V}_{m,1} \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2} \times 10^{-5}$		$\bar{V}_{m,1} \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2} \times 10^{-5}$		$\bar{V}_{m,1} \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{V}_{m,2} \times 10^{-5}$
303.15K								
0.0000	3.28	20.14	0.0000	3.13	19.64	0.0000	3.14	18.79
0.2322	4.52	19.26	0.2240	4.24	18.53	0.2523	3.79	17.90
0.4701	4.77	18.14	0.4761	4.58	17.30	0.4819	4.06	16.84
0.6342	4.48	19.50	0.6789	4.78	19.66	0.6524	4.25	17.15
0.8246	5.48	20.76	0.8332	5.35	20.89	0.8286	5.39	18.57
1.0000	6.33	23.46	1.0000	5.84	22.27	1.0000	6.94	21.95
308.15K								
0.0000	3.88	19.14	0.0000	3.24	16.17	0.0000	4.15	15.66
0.2322	4.15	18.62	0.2240	4.29	15.35	0.2523	4.40	13.64
0.4701	4.89	17.11	0.4761	4.72	14.48	0.4819	4.96	11.58
0.6342	5.05	18.98	0.6789	5.81	16.16	0.6524	5.15	14.77
0.8246	5.87	19.47	0.8332	6.34	18.85	0.8286	6.49	17.82
1.0000	6.37	22.03	1.0000	7.79	21.04	1.0000	7.24	18.88
313.15K								
0.0000	4.36	19.27	0.0000	8.35	18.19	0.0000	10.63	15.82
0.2322	5.05	18.14	0.2240	9.85	17.44	0.2523	11.13	14.45
0.4701	5.74	17.07	0.4761	10.03	16.18	0.4819	11.63	13.80
0.6342	6.46	18.92	0.6789	10.93	18.76	0.6524	12.37	15.88
0.8246	7.51	19.67	0.8332	11.80	19.20	0.8286	13.39	18.08
1.0000	7.88	22.68	1.0000	11.91	21.44	1.0000	13.88	19.16

Table 5 Values of partial molar volume of the components at infinite dilution ($V_{m,1}^{\infty}$, $V_{m,2}^{\infty}$) and excess partial molar volume at infinite dilution ($V_{m,1}^{E,\infty}$ and $V_{m,2}^{E,\infty}$) for all the systems at three different temperatures

System	Temperature(K)	$V_{m,1}^{\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,2}^{\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,1}^{E,\infty} \times 10^{-5}$	$V_{m,2}^{E,\infty} \times 10^{-5}$
PMBA +FA	303.15	3.28	23.46	-3.05	-3.32
	308.15	3.88	22.03	-2.71	-2.63
	313.15	4.36	22.68	-3.80	-3.16
PMBA +DMF	303.15	3.18	22.27	-2.49	-2.89
	308.15	3.24	21.04	-4.55	-4.87
	313.15	4.15	21.44	-3.09	-3.22
PMBA +NMF	303.15	4.36	21.95	-3.55	-3.41
	308.15	8.35	18.88	-3.56	-3.25

313.15	10.63	19.16	- 3.25	-3.34
--------	-------	-------	--------	-------

The molecular interactions present in the P-MBA + amides are also reflected in terms of partial molar volumes. The obtained values are shown in table 4 and table 5, from which it culminates that strong interactions exist throughout the taking liquid mixtures. From these results, it is also observe that the partial molar volumes is proportional with concentration of the composition. Harkot suggested [11,12]that the large negative excess volumes for liquid mixtures are due to geometrical factors, and hydrophilic interactions that give the higher degree of dissociation results were obtained by the increase of specific conductivity in a mixture.

FT-IR SPECTRA

The FT-IR spectra of pure solvents have been done in the wave number region 400-4000 cm^{-1} and are presented in the (fig 4- fig 7). Partial band assignments of the solvent mixtures by comparing with the pure solvents have been made and compounds are discussed with the mole fractions at different cases considered in three combinations recorded at room temperature. Case (i)30% component (1) and 70% of the component (2),Case (ii)50% of component (1) and component(2) and case(iii) 70% of component(1) to 30% of component(2). For this figures the intensity of an absorption in the IR spectrum can be observed with variation in dipole moment that develops during the vibration. But, vibrations are develop a shift in dipole moment (C=O/C-O/C-H/N-H stretch) for P-MBA+ amides. From this outcome in a more intense absorption produce the analysis of hydrogen bonding formation in between the P-MBA+ amides mixture [13, 14].

Fig 4. FTIR analysis for Formamide

Fig 5 FTIR analysis for N methyl Formamide

Fig 6 FTIR analysis for Di Methyl Formamide

Fig 7 FTIR analysis of p-methoxy benzoic acid

CONCLUSIONS

The speed of sound, viscosity and densities of binary mixtures for P-Methoxy benzoic acid with amides were measured at temperature from 303.15K - 313.15K using standard techniques also compared using the standard relations obtained from the literature. Further various thermo - acoustic parameters were computed by the obtained data, the excess values of molar volume and excess acoustic impedance are found to be positive for all the binary systems over the entire range of composition. The values of excess properties of K_s^E and L_f^E are found to be negative for binary mixtures of P-Methoxy benzoic acid with formamide, DMF and NMF in the whole mole fraction range at the three different temperatures. The results can be explained in terms of the intra and inter molecular H-bonding of amide and the formation of the same between the polar and nonpolar molecules of the liquid mixtures. Further the values of the excess parameters are fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial equation and the results are also represented in table 3. Furthermore to showcase the molecular interactions in between methoxy molecules and amides with the upshots of partial molar volumes. Finally, FT-IR analysis of the pure solvent and their mixtures are also reported where the principal bands in the mixture.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Author A. Nagarjuna is thankful to Dr. B M Praveen, Director of R&D, Srinivas University, Karnataka for his valuable suggestions and discussions.

REFERENCES

1. D.R Godhani, P.B Dobariya, A.M Sanghani and J.P Mehta, Arab. J.chem., 10, (2017) 422
DOI:10.1016/j.arabj.2012.10.002
2. N.J Madhuri, P.S Naidu, J. Glory and K.R Prasad, E-J.Chem., 8, (2011) 457

DOI:10.1155/2011/464098

3. A.V Rao, P.Venkateswaralu, G.K Raman and A.V Rajulu, *Acta Polym.*, 43, (1992) 185
4. A. Nagarjuna , Shaik Babu and M. Gowrisankar,*Int.J.Amb.Energy.*,1, (2020) 1
DOI: 10.1080/01430750.2020.1725628
5. A.Nagarjuna, K.V.Yamini Kanth , G. Balaji Prakash and Debashis Das, *Rasayan.J.Chem.*, 12(4), (2019) 1774
6. S.M Nayeem, S. Nyamathulla, I. Khan and D.K Rao, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 218, (2016),676
DOI: 10.1016/j.molliq.2016.02.045
7. O. Kiyohara and G.C. Benson, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 11, (1979) 861
DOI:10.1016/0021- 9614(79)90067-3
8. O.Redlich and A.T Kister , *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 40, (1948) 345.
9. R. Balaji, M.G Sankar, M.C Sekhar and M.C. Shekar, *Kar. Int. J. Mod. Sci.*, 2, (2016) 10
DOI:10.1016/j.kijoms.2015.12.001
10. J.E Desnoyers and G. Perron , *J. sol. Chem.*, 26(8), (1997) 749.
11. M. Mc Dowall , C.A Joseph and Vincent, *J. Chem. Soc Faraday Trans.*, 70, (1974) 1862
12. J.Harkot, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 330, (2009) 467
13. P.K Pandey, A. Awasthi and A.Awasthi, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 187, (2013) 343
DOI:10.1016/j.molliq.2013.09.002
14. T.Karunakar, C.H Srinivasu and K.Narendra , *Res. Rev.P.Appl. Phys.*, 1, (2013) 5

Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) metal compounds of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde: Synthesis, crystalline structure, pharmacological assessment, and molecular docking research are all part of the process.

N. KOTILINGAIAH¹, A. NAGARJUNA², B.M PRAVEEN³, B SRINU⁴, K. SATEESH⁴

¹ PDF Scholar, Department of Chemistry, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

²Department of Physics, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College (Autonomous), JNTUH, Medbowli, Meerpet, Hyderabad-500097, Telangana, India

³Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka - 574146, India

⁴Department of Freshman Engineering, Geethanjali college of engineering and technology, Cheeryal, keesara, Medchal -501301, Telangana, India

Abstract

The ligand 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (2-ANA) and metal compounds of [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], and, [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] have synthesis and research by using analytic and spectroscopical techniques (UV, IR, 1H-NMR and Mass). The 2-ANA and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex single crystal X-ray diffraction experiments have been describe. Both compounds have intra/intermolecular hydrogen bonding, and the N-particle of the pyridine ring of 2-ANA is tetrahedrally coordinate to M-ion. Molecular docking research for microbiological examination, antioxidants, in antibacterial activity, and EGFR target were performed on metal chlorides, 2-ANA, and their complexes, which revealed that metal complexes have a synergistic effect on biological activity when compared to liberal ligand and M-Cl.

Keywords: Metal compounds; inter or intra molecular H-bonding; tetrahedrally; interactivity impact. 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (2-ANA); metal compounds; intra or inter particles H-bonding; tetrahedrally; interactivity influence.

1. Introduction

M-organic categorization, crystal development of technology [1], non-linear optic materiel [2-4], therapeutic [5], and catalytic nature of research [6] have all emerged as new areas of modern coordination chemistry in recent years [7]. Several classes of ligands have been produced over time for use in various uses [8-13].

Each category of ligand structure develop from 2-aminoaldehydes was widely use as construction pigmentation for black Orlon [14], as well as a number of biologically relevant compounds including such naphthyridine chemical compounds as antimutagenic, pain relievers [15], and anti-cancer activity [16]. The Co (II) compounds of nicotinaldehyde has recently been discovered to be an effective specific inhibitor of nicotinamidases, the metabolism enzyme leads to the development and pathogenesis of various pathogen micro-organisms [17]. Furthermore, the constant H-bonding motif has important applications in morphologic chemistry and molecular device, such as in the oxygen carrying conversion of haemoglobin and the morphologic nature of DNA molecules. Hard or weak, inter or intra molecule H-bonding provide an unusual supramolecular stacking structure in the solid state of 2-ANA and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex[18]. 2-ANA's stability and coordination chemistry differed significantly from those of its counterpart, 2-aminobenzaldehyde [19], are three possible co-ordination particles such as N atom of the pyridine ring (P-R)[20], which is the highly likely electron donor nature, and the another are the N-particle in amine and the O atom in aldehyde. Furthermore, previous research has shown that 2-ANA and parallel has been use to generate different M-compounds in which the N atom of the P-ring is linking to the M-ion [21]. The versatility of amino-aldehydes as ligands, as well as a possibility of have many possible metal interaction sites in ligand and constant intra or inter molecule H-bonding, prompted as to examine co-ordination capabilities of 2-ANA. We describe the preparation of 2-ANA and M-compounds with Co (II), Ni (II), and Cu (II) ions in this context. IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, and UV-region data were use to describe these compounds. ANA and the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex were study by using single crystal X-rays. The presence and different of hard/soft H-bond networks in 2-ANA and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complexes were discovered through crystal structure research. Selected microbes were investigated in vitro for antimicrobial properties versus two gram-positive pathogens, B. subtilis and S. aureus, as well as two gram-negative pathogens, K. pneumoniae and E. coli, and in antifungal activity against A. niger and P. notatum. Antioxidant and anti - inflammatory effects of the compounds were also investigated [22].

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials, procedures, and apparatus

All of the compounds employed were of synthetic quality. The solution was cleansed correspondingly to industry standards. E.Merck provided us with metal salts (India). The melting point was determined with B.Electro-thermal melting point equipment, and the elements analysis was performed, at room temperature, the ¹H and ¹³C-NMR data as acquired on Bruker Ascend-425 MHz analyzer using DMSO-D6 as component. The internal standard used to record these spectra was tetramethylsilane (TMS). TGA was carried out on a NETZSCH STA-2500 Regulus thermal polarizer in an N environment (RT-725°C) at 15-18°C/ minutes, by distributing the solid materials as KBr or Nujal mulls, FTIR spectra (3680-180 cm⁻¹

¹) was acquired on a PE 100S spectra[23, 24]. The IR spectrum of the ligands and M-compounds is measure in the region of 225-785 nm by using a JASCO V-670 SP-meter. The amount of M-Cl in the sample was assessed using a conventional technique [25].

2.2 The chemicals are synthesis

2.2.1 2-ANA synthesis

The ligand 2-ANA was produced using the process described previously and Yellow crystals appropriate for X-ray method was acquire by using re-crystallization from ethanol. 30 % yield C, 55.83; H, 3.95; N, 21.82. Anl. Cal. for C₆H₆N₂O%: C, 56.84; H, 3.89; N, 23.73. C was 58.81, H was 4.83, and N was 22.87. 3414 (N-H), 1655 (C=O), 1565 (C=N) (Pyridine) IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) (M.P. 96.0 C). 9.78 (s, ¹H), 7.15 (d, J = 7.0 Hz, ¹H), 7.00 (d, J = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 6.81-6.84 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 6.60-6.63 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 6.63-6.66 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 6.62-6.65 (s, 2H, -NH (m, 1H)). ¹³C-nmr (DMSO, ppm, 100 MHz): δ 189.11, 157.60, 148.16, 143.03, 111.41, and 113.67.

2.2.2 Synthesis of [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], 1

Synthesize compound of 2-ANA (0.471 g, 3.90 mmol) dissolve in 25 ml CH₃OH and CoCl₂.4H₂O (0.425 g, 3 mmol) dilute in 12 ml ethanol was mixed at ref. tem. for about 3.30 hours. High ethanol was remove in vacuum at the end of the reaction and after cooling, filtered, to produce 71% compound. Anl. Cal. for [Co(C₆H₆ON₂)₂Cl₂] (%): c, 39.58; H, 4.25; N, 12.51. Find: C, 35.63; H, 3.26; N, 13.44. m.p.298 °C (deco.); Ir (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3323 (ν_(N-H)), 1674 (ν_(c=O)), 1562 (ν_(c=N) (Py)). ¹H-NMR (DMSO, ppm, 425 MHz): δ 8.52 (s, 2H, -CHO), 7.89 (d, J = 8.0, 2H), 8.84 (d, J = 8.0, 2H), 8.31 (s, 4H, -NH₂), 5.62-5.65 (m, 2H). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO, ppm, 100 MHz): δ 191.11, 155.45, 153.25, 143.07, 113.48, 114.81.

2.2.3 Preparation of complex [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], 2

Complex two is made in the same way. Result of compound [Ni(C₆H₆ON₂)₂Cl₂] 66%. Anl. Cal. for [Ni(C₆H₆ON₂)₂Cl₂](percentage); C, 31.44; N, 11.69; H, 3.21. Find: C, 31.81; N, 11.90; H, 3.48. mp.313 °C; ir (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3465 (ν_(N-H)), 1645 (ν_(c=O)), 1560 (ν_(c=N) (Pyridine)). ¹H-NMR (DMSO, ppm, 300 MHz): δ 8.81 (s, 2H, -CHO), 8.98 (d, J=8.0, 2H), 8.12 (d, J = 8.0, 2H), 7.34 (s, 4H, -NH₂), 7.52- 6.56 (m, 2H). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO, PPM, 110 MHz): δ 183.57, 147.98, 144.15, 134.84, 102.85, and 107.71.

2.2.4 Complex [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] preparation, 3

Compound 3 is made in the same way¹. Result of compound [Cu(C₆H₆ON₂)₂Cl₂] 68%. Anl. Cal. for [Cu(C₆H₆ON₂)₂Cl₂](percentage): C, 27.85; N, 12.14 H, 3.45; Find : C, 25.79; N, 9.95; H, 2.45. mp.141 °C; ir (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3432 (ν_(N-H)), 1661 (ν_(c=O)), 1552 (ν_(c=N) (Py)). ¹H-nmr (DMSO, PPM, 300 MHz): δ 9.64 (s, 2H), 9.37 (d, J = 7.2, 2H), 7.05 (d, J = 7.4, 2H), 8.54 (s, 4H, -NH₂), 7.64-7.69 (m, 2H). ¹³C-nmr (DMSO, PPM, 100 MHz): δ 192.67, 157.21, 153.85, 144.92, 112.56, and 113.24.

2.3 Crystal structure determination

Ethanol liquid slowly evaporating, solitary ligand crystals (2-ANA) and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound, appropriate for X-ray data investigation, was produced, the SAINT programme was used to help with data integration and reduction. Using the tool SADABS, the data will be subjected to multiscan empirical absorption adjustments. Structures were solved by using direct and polished on F2 using the SHELXL-97 programme, which used full-matrix least squares. Anisotropic refinement was used on all non-hydrogen atoms. The hydrogen atoms were found and refined using Fourier mapping [26-31].

2.4 Investigations into bio-assays

2.4.1 Antimicrobial properties

The disc diffusion method was used to test the antimicrobial properties of the 2-ANA as well as transition metals versus two punnet pathogens (*Bacillus cereus*, *S. aureus*), two punnet microorganisms (*E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae*), and two fungal strains (*P. notatum*, and *A. niger*). Sterile conditions antimicrobial discs with a diameter of 5 mm have been used put over the nutritional agar material by using Whitman (No. 1) paper. 100 g/mL conc. chemicals were applied to disc using a micropipette (complexes were initially dissolved in DMSO); micro-organism and fungus were then cultured at 38°C and 26°C. The inhibitory area was measured in millimeters, identified by using conventional medicines. Antibiotic 28 g/disc (std. medicines) and std. Antibacterial medication Occur in a range (8g/disc) was utilized as DMSO was used as a zone of inhibition, whereas objective of ensuring were used, all experiments were done in the mean isolate, or the (MIC) estimates for the investigated drugs and references in g/mL, were collected in carried out in triplicate.

2.4.2 Antioxidant properties

Using the DPPH free radical technique reported in literature, the ability to scavenge free radicals of ligand 2-ANA and metal compounds was tested [32-34]. A scorbic solution, which was employed as a control, in 100% methanol, a 0.2 mM DPPH solution was produced. The test chemicals were dissolved in 0.3 percent DMSO and CH₃OH to make 1 mM stock solutions, and appropriate there was a substantial amount of antioxidant activity soluble in 95 percent methanol to prepare 1 mM solution. After diluting with methanol, several concentrations (2, 12, 32, and 95 M) of solutions were generated from the stock solutions. To the 2.5 mL of DPPH solution, 1 mL of chemical component was added. An Ultraviolet light spectrometer has been used to determine the absorption of component at 525 nm after 25 minutes. The absorbance of a blank DPPH component without test substance was measured at 520 nm as a control (A₀), the below equation used to calculate the % of absorbance value.

$$\text{Absorbance value} = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} * 100$$

Where,

A₀ = DPPH absorbance in absence of antioxidant

A_1 = DPPH absorb in presence of antioxidant.

The compounds' IC50 values were also computed.

2.4.3 Anticancer properties

The ligand and M-compounds was tested in vitro against five distinct cancer cell types in humans, including MCF-7 a cell line for melanoma, HeLa cell line for carcinoma, A-549 carcinoma of the lungs cell line, and 293 renal cell line from a human fetus. The typical medication was cis-platin. The MTT-microcultured tetrazolium was use to identify cell ability in condition of evaluate substances. This is a colorimetric quantitative approach for identifying cell viability [35]. The metabolic activity of living cells is the metric being measured. After solubilization in DMSO, cells that are biologically active convert a light salt of yellow reagent was added (MTT) to water-insoluble bright blue precipitate this can be applied immediately measured. The quantity of live cells is directly proportional to the formazan absorbance. MCF-7, HeLa, A-549, and HEK293 on a 96-well plate, cells were concentration on a plate of 1 10³ cells per excellent. A cell was cultivated in full medium overnight before being transferred to reduced serum media. As a control, 1 percent DMSO was employed. Following 45 hours of procedure with various doses of evaluated chemicals, the cells were cultured for a period of time in the CO₂ chamber for 3 hours and MTT (3.0 mg/mL). The media was then withdrawn from each well, and 100 μ L of DMSO was added to the precipitate was formed crystals must be dissolved. Optic density was determined by scanning the samples at 560 nm, connected using a cell amount, after thorough mixing. The percentage of viability was used to represent the results. All of the experiments were done three times. The IC50 graph pad prism was use to find the values. (5.05 version) using linear regression analysis, The IC50 value, which would be the amount needed, was used to compute the reaction factor to reduce cell viability by 50% [36].

2.5 Technique of calculation

2.5.1 Research on molecular docking

Research goal was to analysis the probable binding mechanisms with the aim EGFR protein complex body part by using models of docking studies and to explainer, interacting system of ligand and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], and [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complexes with target receptor. EGFR is a key player in cancer illness and a popular target for cancer inhibitors. Overexpression of EGFR is linked to a variety of malignancies, squamous-cell pulmonary cancer is one of the most common cancers (75 percent), of anal. tumors instances [37], glioblastoma (55 percent), and cancers of epithelium of both the neck and head (60 percent) (75-100 percent) [38]. The docking research was done with transition metals and ligands on the EGFR protein receptor. The RSC protein data library provided the EGFR crystal structures. The UCSF Chimera was use to purify the EGFR protein by eliminating water molecules and ligands. Chem Create Ultra 12.0 was use to draw the 3D geometry of M-complexes, and the 3D geometry

was thoroughly optimised[39-40]. In docking, motion-efficient proteins, ligands, and M-compounds was employed.

Molecular docking protocol

The stiff EGFR ligand and compounds developed created to bind with one another. in the ADT process. Interaction energies charges were created by combining non-polar H atoms, was apply to all partical of the protein structure. PDB geometry was translated to PDBQT form for future ADT research, and energy estimates were gone utilising strategies bases on genetics, non-polar H particle, Interaction energies fractional penalties, rotational bonds, and a carton matrix having sizes $60^3 \text{ \AA}^3$ create around the EGFR specific protein was allotted by using Molecular docking instruments 1.5.6 and width of (Angstrom): 0.3750. The highest number of assessments and the population size were 160 and 21, 00,000, respectively. The results were investigated using Discovery Studio 4.1.0. The whole procedure explains how to dock EGFR inhibitors in detail, including the receptor–compound interactions' interaction efficiencies.

3. Analysis of the findings

All of the compounds are non-hygroscopic and very stable at normal condition. Table 1 shows that the metal complexes have a 1:2:2 stoichiometry (M: Ligan:Cl) based on analytical data. In DMF, CH_3OH , ethanol, and, DMSO, all of complexes are readily soluble.[41].

3.1 Spectral investigations in the infrared and Far-infrared

Table S1 shows the IR spectrum analysis of the ligands and M-compounds. The peak for N-H of NH_2 of 2-ANA is 3386 cm^{-1} , a peak for C=O of CHO group is 1668 cm^{-1} , and the peak for frequency of bending $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of (py) ring is 1585 cm^{-1} . The IR data of compounds was comparable to that of (2-ANA), with slight differences in peak positions. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (pyridine) peak was shift to a low wave number in all complex spectra when compared to the free ligand, showing that 2-ANA is coordinated through the pyridine ring nitrogen atom. The modern peaks at $465\text{-}420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was attribute to M-N, whereas the peaks at 371, 312, and 285 cm^{-1} was allocated to ν_{MCl} , respectively [42-44].

3.2 UV-Vis spectra

The UV spectra of 2-ANA in DMF shows a wide band of absorbing at 265 nm, which has attribute to the pyridyl group's $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, and, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The absorb peaks at 352 nm has attribute to an intra -molecular charge carrier zone formed by ligand's $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{CHO}$ subunits (2-ANA). Bands with distinct characteristics with minor changes in blue were also visible in the matching metal complexes. Because of the d7,d8, and d10 electronic configuration, no $d \rightarrow d$ transitions are predicted for Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) compounds. Tetrahedral structure has postulated for M-compounds based on IR and analytical evidence.

3.3 NMR spectral studies

In (DMSO, ppm, 425 MHz), ¹H-nmr data of 2-ANA and compounds were recorded: The indications at δ 9.65 (s, ¹H), 8.83 (d, J = 9.14 Hz, ¹H), 8.35 (d, J = 9.18 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.79-7.91 (m, 1H). The ¹³C-nmr data of 2-ANA shows signals from 113.14 to 193.25 ppm. Carbonyl compounds carbon has a signal near 192.75 ppm, tertiary carbon atoms have spikes between 152.65 and 112.85 ppm, and the other carbon atoms have spikes at 111.57, 143.28, and 155.45 ppm. These signals in complex data, which occurred, shifts caused by positive coordinating, suggest that 2-ANA's pyridine N is engaged in M-ion bonding.

3.4 Thermal gravimetric research

Figure S2 a-d shows the thermograms of ligand 2-ANA and their M-compounds. The Table S2 shows the stages of decomposition, temperature ranges, reported breakdown components and compounds, as well as the mass loose % estimate. All of the compounds were heated to temperatures ranging from 26 to 775 degrees Celsius in a nitrogen environment. The ligand 2-ANA degraded in three steps, according to thermal data, from 52-225 °C, 212-465 °C and 465-712 °C for the loss of several pieces in order to keep C2 as a remnant, from 225-332 C, the Co(II) complex dissolved progressively, resulting in the loss of organic ligands, although CoCl₂ was retained as a residue. Breakdown of the Co(II) complex began at 216-362°C for the disappearance of chemical compounds in order to keep CoCl₂ residual, in contrast to decomposition of the Ni(ii) compound began at 173-451°C for continual weight reduces of ligands in order to use CoO as loss.

3.5 2-ANA and the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound crystalline structure

3.5.1 2-ANA

The ligand (2-ANA) crystallised in a mono-clinic arrangement a P21/c group of space and Z = 8. Table 2 lists the crystallographic parameters, whereas Table S3 lists the H-bonding data. An asymmetric unit in the crystal structure is made up of two 2-ANA molecules, designated a and b, that seem to have intra-molecular classic N-H....O, where one of the amine group's H binds to an O atom in the aldehyde group in carbonyl compound, producing a 6-cyclic ring. Two different types of fundamental molecular motifs occur from inter - particle H-bonding among N-H....N particles: N₃-H_{3b}....N₂ interactions in the inversion site of compounds in the multi-meric unit B and N₂-H_{2b}....N₁ interactions A monomer is a single molecule A, which results in molecular stacking arrangement in the shape of a salmon bone the b axis. Furthermore, the pyridine ring's non-classical poor hydrogen bond couplings C-H...N units result in a unique dimeric unit pattern stacking .Figure S3 c. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. S4, the hydrogen aldehydic H₁₂, In inter-particle non-classical interactions, the pyridine circle proton H₉ of dimmers CC* or H₄ of molecules A interact. H-bonding to oxygen atom as tri-furcated receiver O₁ in C-H....O. The intermolecular weak H-bonding between molecule A's pyridine circle proton H₃ with compound B's aryl atom of oxygen O₂ extends the molecular stacking on a 2D structure (Fig. S5). Connections between the

reactive pyridine groups of dimeric units CC* that are caused by length. (length =3.89Å) strengthen geometry of crystalline cohesiveness within the crystalline structure in atomic packing. In a word, 2-ANA's supra-molecular stacking shape is a 3D supra-molecular stack arrangement[44-45]. is made up of H-bonding can be classified as either classical or non-classical. networks, as seen in Fig. S6.

3.5.2 [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] complex

In the triclinic system, the [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] complex crystallised with the P-1 cluster of area and Z= 2. Table 2 lists the crystallographic information. Table S3 shows the specifics of the H-bonding data. The atmosphere of cooperation surrounding the Zn atom is deformed tetrahedral shape, with two positions filled by 2-ANA's pyridine nitrogen atoms, A and B, and the other two sites held by Cl₁, Cl₂. Figure 2, depicts the ORTEP diagram of [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2], while Table 3 a list of the options inter-atomic distances and bond angles. H-bonding contacts, including classically and non-classical may be found in the Co(ii) compound, according to findings. The intra - molecular H-bonding N-H...O that can be seen in 2-ANA crystalline geometry is preserved in complex geometry. Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 2, the complex molecule contains intra-molecular H connections that aren't classical such as Cl..H-N occurring as N5-H5b...Cl₂ and N3-H3...Cl₁. Non-classical intermolecular hydrogen bonds are also present in the 2-ANA and [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] complex, as they are in the free ligand. A few of the halide compounds participating in the C9-H9....Cl₂ hydrogen - bonding contact inside the inter-particle non-classical pyridine ring, resulting in 1-D the complex's sequence (Fig. S7). The bifurcated electrophilic atom of oxygen O1 of an aromatic rings of receptor A in compound particle acts as a twisted electrophile for pyridine ring hydrogens H3 and H4, whereas the H2 hydrogen and allyl hydrogen H5 of ligand A in same compound molecule take part in non-classical inter-molecular weak H-bonding with the bi-furcated electrophilic oxygen atom O2 of the binding site As a result, 2-ANA in the complexes is implicated in two kinds of inter-molecular bifurcation soft H-bonding with the aryl group's oxygen atom in 3D crystal structure. Figure S9, depicts the 3D network of non-classical H connections that exist.

3.6 Antibacterial properties:

The ligand 2-ANA has little action against the pathogens in vitro, but the complex [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] has highly reactivity against *S. aureus* (13.7 g/mL) and medium reactivity versus three species: *E. coli* (30 g. mL⁻¹), *K. pneumoniae* (30 g. mL⁻¹), and *B. subtilis* (30 g. mL⁻¹). The compounds [Cu(2-ANA)2Cl2], [Ni(2-ANA)2Cl2] have influence to weak antibacterial properties versus, *B. bacillus*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumonia*, and *E. coli*, in relation to reference compounds. Although 2-ANA has no action against the genus, the excellent activity shown by [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] might be attributed to 2-ANA's coordination with Co (ii). The products' (MIC) are listed in Table 4. When comparison to [Ni(2-ANA)2Cl2] and [Cu(2-ANA)2Cl2] complexes, the [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2] combination had superior antibacterial activity. When compared to the [Cu(2-ANA)2Cl2] complex, [Co(2-ANA)2Cl2], and [Cu(2-ANA)2Cl2]

complexes have only modest activity against, *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* K. pneumoniae.

3.7 Anti - fungal properties:

The anti-fungal properties of 2-ANA and their M-compounds was tested in vitro versus by fungus strains *A. niger* and *P. notatum*, and results were comparison to reference medication Ketoconazole by using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) measurements. Table 5 shows that compound [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] as very good anti-fungal properties versus *P. notatum*, *A. niger*, such values (12.4 g/mL, 12.4 g/mL), whereas the compound [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] as medium to low anti-fungal properties versus *A. niger* strains with values of 45 g/mL. Despite the fact that the ligand 2-ANA had no anti-fungal action, it did show good to moderate activity when bound to metal ions, which could be due to a synergistic effect. In comparison to other metal complexes, the Co (ii) compound as demonstrated very good action versus *P. notatum*, and *A. niger*.

3.8 Anti-oxidant properties

Table 6 shows the IC₅₀ values of produce ligand as well as their coordination compounds; raising the conc. of the complex improves the exploring action. Figure 3 shows the percentage inhibition (IC₅₀) of metal complexes (1-3). The findings shows that as comparison to transition metals, the scavenging ability of the free ligand (IC₅₀ = 22.10±1.45 μM) is much lower. The [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound has a high activity level, with an IC₅₀ of 10.14±2.50 μM. With an IC₅₀ of 14.20±2.69 μM, [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] exhibits considerable activity, whereas [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] exhibits medium nature versus an IC₅₀ of 19.23±2.35 μM. The scavenging activity of the ligand and transition metals is rising in order based on their IC₅₀ values.

3.9 Anti-cancer properties

The anti-cancer properties of produce substances is test by using the MTT test with anti-cancer medication cis-platin as a reference versus, MCF-7, HeLa, HEK-293, and A549 cells. Curves of survival, A549, and MCF-7 were creating by plotting the association in between drug concentration as well as the survival percent. Table 7 shows the IC₅₀ values for produce compounds versus cell lines that were examined. When compared to the conventional medication cis-platin, the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex showed considerable action versus 3 cancer lines MCF-7, HeLa, and A549, as well as IC₅₀ values of 22.720.45 M, 18.070.28 M, and 18.280.24 M, respectively. With IC₅₀ values of 23.170.31, 33.280.12, and 30.230.06 M, respectively, the [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex exhibits moderate activity, whereas the [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex exhibits limited activity with IC₅₀ values of 41.540.27, 40.870.35, and 42.930.37 M, respectively. HeLa, MCF-7, and A549 cancer cell are all cytotoxic to the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂]

complex. On studied cell lines, the [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound is not cytotoxic. Based on IC₅₀ values, the [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound is solely cytotoxic to the HeLa cell line. On the HeLa cell line, the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound shows anticancer action. In conclusion, the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex has substantial activity, the [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex has moderate activity, and the [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex has limited activity versus MCF-7, HeLa, and A549.

4. Docking of molecules

The L and M-compounds have minimal coupling energies of -5.85, -6.69, -6.03, and -6.33 K cal/mol, approximately, for EGFR protein receptor. The peptide receptor was harmed by transition metal complexes more effectively than ligands, suggesting their ligands 2-ANA in compound have a tendency to horizon for creation of grille protein. In molecular docking, this entanglement forces experiments clearly suggest in anti-cancer properties findings, as shown, with metal compound having the loss hinge values and demonstrating good anticancer activity via interacting with the EGFR transporters for proteins, ligand and products attach to Hydrophobic connections and H-bonding connect with the EGFR specific protein, according to molecular docking studies. Instead of creating a cluster in the receptor's binding pocket, the drug 2-ANA forms a single molecule, Fig. 5 a-c shows optimum conformations of M-compounds such as [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], and [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂], Seven H bonds were found with the Ligand of M-compounds and EGFR protein receptor in the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂]-receptor complex. Two H bonds, one interaction Lys721 and aldehyde group's O-atom, and other with N-atom of one 2-ANA's -NH₂ group, had bond lengths of 2.17 Å⁰ and 1.62 Å⁰, respectively, and bond angles of 122.27 Å⁰ and 127.32 Å⁰ in complex. One H bond was discovered around Arg816 and O-particle of the aldehyde group, with a bond distance of 2.25 Å⁰ and a bond angle of 116.14 Å⁰; another H bond was discovered around Asn819 and H-particle of -NH₂ group, with a bond length of 2.34 Å⁰ and a bond angle of 117.67 Å⁰; and three leftover hydrogen bonds was form with Asp831. Bond distances of two H atoms from -NH₂ set were engaged in bonding of 2.04 Å⁰ and 2.69 Å⁰, bond angles of 104.74 Å⁰ and 86.11Å⁰, respectively, some other H connection was created between H particle of -NH₂ set of second 2-ANA of [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound and bond length of 1.81Å⁰ and bond angle of 123.55 Å⁰. [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound establishes repulsive contacts with amino acids Arg817, Asn818, Asp831, and Lys721 among these hydrogen bonding interactions.

When the ligand in [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂]-receptor compound engaged effectively with protein receptor, two H bonds was generated. One H bond was establishes around Asp813 and H-atom of -NH₂ group, with a bond distance of 2.36 Å and a bond angle of 114.42, Another strong H connection was created in between two of them, Arg817 and N-particle of amine set, with a bond length of 2.13 Å and a bond angle of 136.64.

Six hydrogen bonds were discovered in the [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂]-receptor complex, In combination with Lys721 polypeptide chains, the N-particle of –NH₂ and O-particle of the aromatic ring of 2-ANA receptor formed two H bonds surrounding them, bond lengths 2.13 Å⁰, 2.04 Å⁰ and bond angles 154.59, 112.87. Two bonds was form with ASP831 amino acids when they interacted with H atoms of 2-ANA's -NH₂ group in compounds, and bond length of 2.31 Å⁰, 2.13Å⁰, and bond angles of 122.06, 97.88, and last two are Asn818 and Arg 817, both of which had an O-atom in the aromatic ring and a H atom, of 2-ANA's –NH₂ group, with bond distances of 2.02 Å⁰, 2.29 Å⁰, and additional unfavorable contact with the amino acids, Thr830, Val702, Asn818, and Asp831 were discovered among these interactions. Only three hydrogen bonds were found in the ligand (2-ANA) protein complex. Two H bonds occurred around Cys751 and Hatoms of -NH₂ group with bond lengths of 2.12 Å⁰ and bond angles of 95.86⁰ and 101.1⁰, respectively, Phe832 and O-particle of carbonyl set created one H bond with a bond length of 1.85 Å⁰ and a binding energies of 148.26, by possessing seven hydrogen bonds[46-48], the [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex has the lowest binding energy compared to [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] and [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂]. The L and compounds with least binding energy exhibit strong cytotoxicity by using in anti-cancer tests. The results of docking research on molecules show they are highly correlated, given the anti-cancer data information from the experiments in vitro.

5. Conclusions

A number of spectroscopic methods were used to produce the ligand and M-compounds of Co(ii), Ni(ii), and Cu(ii), through N atom of pyridine ring, 2-ANA functions as a monodentate ligand towards metal ions, forming a tetrahedral shape surrounding the metal in the complexes. When compared to cis-platin reference drug, [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] complex showed anti-oxidant properties with IC₅₀ value of 12.142.50 M in IC₅₀ values for DPPH radical scavenging experiment show significant anticancer effects versus HeLa, MCF-7, and A549 of 18.022.19 M, 20.711.32 M, and 16.260.26 M, respectively, in the MTT assay. This complex also show potent Anti-fungal properties versus *A. niger* and *P. notatum* species when comparison to Streptomycin conventional medication, and show anti-bacterial properties versus *S. aureus* microorganisms when comparison to Streptomycin conventional medication. Ketoconazole was use as reference drug. The [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound has the least amount of binding energy of -6.89 K.cal/mol and had greater anti-cancer efficacy in molecular docking of molecular studies against the EGFR protein. The results of molecular docking are highly correlated with in vitro anticancer efficacy. In comparison to [Ni(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] and [Cu(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compounds, [Co(2-ANA)₂Cl₂] compound was show to a powerful, , antibacterial agent, anticancer, and, antioxidant.

References

- [1] B.F. Abrahams, S.R. Batten, M.J. Grannas, H. Hamit, B.F. Hoskins, R. Robson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 38 (1999) 1475-1477.
- [2] B. Moulton, M.J. Zaworotko, *Chem. Rev.* 101 (2001) 1629-1658.
- [3] M. Eddaoudi, B. Moler, H. Ji, B. Chen, T.M. Reineke, M. O’Keeffe, O.M. Yaghi, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 34 (2001) 319-330.
- [4] H. Li, M. Eddaoudi, M. O. Keffe, O.M. Yaghi, *Nature* 402 (1999) 276-279.
- [5] L. Brammer, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 33 (2004) 476-495.
- [6] P. Metrangolo, F. Meyer, T. Pilati, D.M. Proserpio, G. Resnati, *Chem. Eur. J.* 13 (2007) 5765-5772.
- [7] M.D. Ward, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 251 (2007) 1663-1667.
- [8] O.R. Evans, W.B. Lin, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 35 (2002) 511-522.
- [9] S. Dibella, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 30 (2001) 355-366.
- [10] B.J. Coe, L.A. Jones, J.A. Harris, Et al, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 126 (2004) 3880-3891.
- [11] N. Shahabadi, S. Kashanian, F. Darabi, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 45 (2010) 4239-4245.
- [12] B. Peng, H. Chao, B. Sun, F. Gao, L.N. Ji, J. Zhang, *Trans. Met. Chem.* 32 (2007) 271-277.
- [13] A. Pui, C. Policar, J.P. Mahy, *Inorganic Chimica Acta* 360 (2007) 2139-2144.
- [14] Division of organic chemistry, Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad, India, *Synthesis* 23 (2008) 3787-3792.
- [15] C. Lherbet, D. Soupaya, C. Bandoin- Dehoux, C. Andre, C. Blonski, P. Hoffmann, *Tetrahedron Letters* 49 (2008) 5449-5451.
- [16] G. Evens, P. Caluwe, *Macromolecules* 12 (5) (1979) 803-808.
- [17] M.C. Wani, P.F. Ronman, J.T. Lindley, M.E. Wall, *J. Med. Chem.* 23 (1980) 554- 560.
- [18] J.A. Wendt, S.D. Deeter, S.E. Bove, C.S. Knauer, R.M. Brooker, C.A. Szafran, R.D. Schwarz, J.J. Kinsorac, K.S. Kilgore, *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 17(2007) 5396-5399.
- [19] Y.J. Hwang, M.L. Chung, U.D. Sohan, C.I. Korean. *J. Physiol. Pharmacol* 17 (2013)517-523.
- [20] J.B. French, Y. Cen, T.L. Vrablik, P. Xu, E. Allen, W. Hanna-Rose, A.A. Sauve, *Biochemistry* 49 (2010) 10421-10439.
- [21] F.H. Allen, V.J. Hoy, J. Howard, V.R. Thalladi, G.R. Desiraju, C.C. Wilson, G.J. McIntyre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 119 (1997) 34-77.
- [22] B. Swamy, J.R. Swamy, *Transition Met. Chem.* 16 (1991) 35-38.
- [23] Q. Jingui, S. Nanbing, D. Chaoyang, Y. Chuluo, L. Daoyu, W.D. Michael, W. Baichang, C. Chuangtian, *Polyhedron* 18 (1999) 3461-3464.
- [24] Y. Li, Z. Leu, H. Deng, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. E: Struct. Rep. Online*, E63 (2007) m3065.
- [25] K. Mahesh, F. Scott, M. Yuriy, K. Mohan Rao, *Journal of Chemical Sciences* 127 (2015) 1135-1144.

- [26] J.R. Ferraro, low-frequency vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds, Plenum press, New York. 1971.
- [27] R.J.H. Clark, J. Chem. Soc. (1963) 1377.
- [28] A.I. Vogel. A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, 3rd Edn. Longman ELBS, London 1968.
- [29] G.Thomas Majewicz, P. Caluwe, J. Org. Chem. 39(5) (1974) 720-721.
- [30] Bruker Analytical X-ray systems. SAINT – Ver. 6.45 copyright (c) Inc, Madison, Wisconsin, USA 2003.
- [31] G.M. Sheldrick, SADABS Program for Absorption Correction, Version 2.10, Analytical X – ray systems, Madison, Wisconsin, USA 2003.
- [32] G.M. Sheldrick, SHELXL–97, A Program for crystal structures Refinement, University of Göttingen, Germany 1997.
- [33] A.W. Bauer, W.M. Kirby, J.C. Sherris, M. Turck, Am. J. Clin. Pathol. 45 (1966) 493-495.
- [34] A. Braca, N.D. Tommasi, L.D. Bari, C. Pizza, M. Politi, I. Morelli, J. Nat. Prod. 64 (2001) 892-896.
- [35] M. R. Saha, S.M.R. Hasan, R. Akter, M.M. Hossain, M.S. Alamb, M. A. Alam, M.E.H. Mazumder, Bangl. J. Vet. Med. 6 (2008) 197-198.
- [36] M.S. Blois, Nature 181(1958) 1199.
- [37] P. Skehan, R. Storeng, D. Scudiero, A. Monks, J. McMohan, D. Vistica, J.T. Warren, H. Bokesch, S. Kenncy, M.R. Boyd, J. Natl. Cancer Inst. 82 (1990) 1107-1112.
- [38] A. Monks, D. Scudiero, P. Skehan, R. Shoemaker, K. Paull, D. Vistica, C. Hose, J. Langley, P. Cromise, J. Natl. Cancer Inst. 83 (1991) 757-766.
- [39] F. Walker, L. Abramowitz, D. Benabderrahmane, X. Duval, V. Descatoire, D. Hénin T. Lehy. T.Aparicio, Human Pathology 40 (2009) 1517-1527.
- [40] V. Kumar, A. Abbas, J. Aster. Robbins basic pathology. Philadelphia, Elsevier/Saunders. 2013, pp. 179-185. ISBN 9781437717815.
- [41] W.J. Pietro, M.M. Francl, W.J. Hehre, D.J. Defrees, J.A. Pople, J.S. Binkley, J. Am. Chem. Soc. 104 (1982) 5039-5045.
- [42] M.J. Frisch, G.W. Trucks, H.B. Schlegel, Gaussian 09, Revision B.01 Gaussian, Inc. Wallingford CT 2009.
- [43] W.J. Geary, Coord. Chem. Rev. 7 (1971) 81-122.
- [44] K. Nakamoto, Infrared spectra of Inorganic and Coordination compounds, Wiley and Sons, New York 1986, pp. 212-256.
- [45] K. Nakamoto, Infrared and Raman spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds, 5th Edn, Wiley-Interscience, New York 1997, pp. 86-90.

[46] G.A. Jeffrey, An introduction to Hydrogen bonding Oxford University press 1997.

[47] Z.T. Zhang, Q.Y. wang, J. Chem. Cryst. 35 (2005) 989-994.

[48] C. Janiak. J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans. (2000) 3885-3890.

Spectroscopic and Textural Analysis of Glucose Dispersed Fundamental Nematic Liquid Crystals

K. V. S. N. Raju^{1,2} · Shaik Salma Begum³ · A. Nagarjuna⁴ · B. M. Praveen⁵

Received: 4 March 2023 / Accepted: 2 May 2023

© The Author(s) under exclusive licence to Sociedade Brasileira de Física 2023

Abstract

Glucose dispersed 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) was studied and the presence of glucose molecules was confirmed through UV–visible spectroscopy and image analysis. The slight increment in the absorbance in 5CBG is attributed to the presence of carbon atoms of glucose and made the 5CB lattice to activate for the radiation. The statistical parameters computed using textural images of the 5CB and 5CBG were compared to draw the conclusions for bio-sensor applications of the 5CB nematic liquid crystal. The parameters computed namely, contrast, correlation, energy, homogeneity and standard deviation, helped to state that 5CB was a strong nematic liquid crystal having high stability in terms of incident radiation and sensitive to bio-molecules. The refractive index and direct band gap of samples are computed using UV–Vis spectra. These values are in support of the conclusions drawn from image analysis technique.

Keywords Glucose molecules · UV–visible absorbance · Contrast · Correlation · Energy · 5CB and 5CBG

1 Introduction

The first discovered materials having nematic phase with high chemical and photochemical stability in the region of room temperature are cyanobiphenyl family of liquid crystals. These liquid crystal compound possess white colour, low relative viscosity and high positive dielectric anisotropy [1–4], and these features made them to have an advantage in field-effect displays. Liquid crystal (LC) state of matter is the combined phase of molecular properties of crystal and flow properties of liquid. The chemical diversities and various phases of LC materials signify revolutionary applications in low-power consumption and flat panel display technology. The applications of LC

phases are wide ranging from structural materials to neural interface found in biomedical devices [5–9]. The recent addition to the ever expanding field of liquid crystals is ionic liquid crystals which form columnar, smectic and bi-continuous cubic phases and provide well-organized one-dimensional, two-dimensional and three-dimensional channels for transporting electrons and ions [10–12].

The recent advances in liquid crystals up to this year 2021 reveal the authors to take the chain length, optical texture into more consideration for deciding various interesting properties of the liquid crystals and making them to participate in diverse applications [13–15]. The H-bonded supramolecular complexes formed with azophenyl nicotinate derivatives exhibit non-linear geometry in V-shaped and chair-shaped models. Long-range mesomorphism is attributed to chair shape complexes than that formed in V-shaped complexes [16]. The geometric parameters of these supramolecular complexes are dependent on the flexible chain lengths and on the electronic nature of the molecular shape [17]. The synthesis procedure followed by the researcher also plays important role in tailoring the textural, optical, electrical and thermal properties of the liquid crystal [18–23].

The current article is focused on generating novel parameters of fundamental nematic liquid crystal and observed the attractive properties tailored through dispersion of glucose in the matrix of the liquid crystal. The optical textures

✉ K. V. S. N. Raju
raju.kvsnr@gmail.com

¹ Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka 574146, India

² Department of Physics, Adikavi Nannaya University Campus, Tadepalligudem, W.G.Dt, A.P 534101, India

³ Department of Physics, Krishna University, Machilipatnam, A.P 521003, India

⁴ Department of Physics, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Meerpet, Hyd 500097, India

⁵ Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka 574146, India

captured with digital camera are analyzed to obtain the physical parameters of the images which in turn gave the remarkable conclusions for the engineering applications of the sample.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The fundamental nematic room temperature liquid crystal that has been used from decades in the research and applications was 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) and was received from Merck (Singapore) with 99% purity. The 5CB was then tailored with pure glucose powder through dispersion method in the weight ratio of 5wt%. The microscope glass slides were purchased from Spectrum Chemical Mfg. Corp., California, and the glass cover slips of 0.17 mm in thickness were used to prepare the sample glucose dispersed 5CB (5CBG) for optical texture observation under polarizing optical microscope. Preparation of the sample and digital images of both 5CB and 5CBG under crossed polarizer position were explained in detail in our previous papers [23].

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The studied samples (5CB & 5CBG) were treated under UV-visible rays ranging from 200 to 500 nm of wavelength for chemical analysis. The UV-visible spectrophotometer used was of Jasco make purchased from Japan with model No: V-670.

Refractive Index Refractive index (n) is another essential optical constant which plays a crucial role in designing optical devices and provides information about local fields, polarization and phase velocity of light in propagating material. The n of materials can be calculated on the basis of transmittance T [20].

$$T_s = 10^{(-A)} \times 100$$

$$n = \frac{1}{T_s} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{T_s} - 1} \quad (1)$$

where T_s is the percentage transmission coefficient (Transmittance) and A is the absorbance.

Energy Band Gap The UV-visible spectrum helped to obtain the direct band gap energy of the samples using the following equation:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/\gamma} = B(h\nu - E_g) \quad (2)$$

The above equation is based on the Tauc method where α is the energy-dependent absorption coefficient, h is Planck's constant, ν is the incident photon frequency, E_g is the band gap of the material and B is a constant. γ is the factor equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ for direct band gap and 2 for indirect band gap materials [21].

2.2.2 Image Analysis

The statistical parameters of the thermotropic liquid crystal compounds 5CB and 5CBG including phase transition behaviour were investigated using MATLAB software implemented on digital images of the same collected in cooling. The following theory is behind the calculations:

Contrast Contrast is a second-order statistical parameter. It is one of the important factors in any subjective evaluation of image quality. Contrast is created by the difference in visual properties that makes an object distinguishable from other objects within the same field of view. It is calculated from the grey level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) of the texture.

$$\text{Contrast} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (i-j)^2 \text{GLCM}(i,j) \quad (3)$$

Homogeneity The homogeneity of a region of an image is related to the changes of intensity that appears in that region. It measures the closeness of distribution of values in the GLCM.

$$\text{Homogeneity} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (P(i,j))^2 \quad (4)$$

Energy Energy is also a second-order statistical parameter. The energy measures textural uniformity, that is, pixel pair repetitions. Energy of the textures is the rate of change in the colour/brightness/magnitude of the pixels over local areas.

$$\text{Energy} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \text{GLCM}(i,j)^2 \quad (5)$$

Correlation Correlation is the function of displacement of the filter. Correlation parameters of the textures denote surface characteristics of an object in digital camera images.

$$\text{Correlation} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\{ixj\} \times \text{GLCM}(i,j) - \{\mu_x \mu_y\}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \quad (6)$$

where μ_x and μ_{xy} are the mean and σ_x and σ_{xy} are standard deviations of probability matrix GLCM along row and column wise x and y , respectively.

Standard Deviation The standard deviation (Σ) of a texture measures the dispersion of image in grey level intensities

and can be understood as a measure of the power level of the alternating signal component acquired by the camera.

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (I(i,j) - \mu)^2}{N - 1}} \quad (7)$$

3 Results and Discussion

UV–visible spectroscopy of both the samples was taken in the wavelength range of 200–500 nm and was plotted as shown in Fig. 1. From the absorption and transmission spectra of the samples, it is clear that glucose molecules closely interacted with the 5CB lattice and shifted the absorbance and transmittance towards lower wavelength of the incident UV–visible radiation [18, 19]. Hence, it is suggested that 5CBG can give quick response to external radiation than pure 5CB. The absorption frequency and absorbance and transmission frequency and transmittance of the samples are mentioned in Table 1. The slight increment in the absorbance in 5CBG is attributed to the presence of carbon atoms of glucose and made the 5CB lattice to activate for the radiation.

From the values of transmittance, we found the refractive index of 5CB and 5CBG [22]. The plot of refractive index (RI) as a function of wavelength is shown in Fig. 2. It clearly shows the decrease in the RI values of 5CBG compared to 5CB and shift in the lower wavelength side. This behaviour is attributed to opaque nature of Glucose particles in the lattice of nematic mesogen 5CB.

The UV–visible spectrum is also used to compute the band gap energy values of 5CB and 5CBG which is shown in Fig. 3a and b. It is presumably understood that the band gap of 5CB is less than that of 5CBG and the values are tabulated in Table 2. The increase in the band gap of 5CBG is attributed to the presence of glucose molecules in the lattice of 5CB and creates perturbation in the lattice arrangement which in turn results into the shift of new energy levels of the activator atoms and thus energy band gap is enhanced [21].

The textural images of 5CB and 5CBG are collected at room temperature with nematic phases and heated till liquid phase is achieved. These digital images are further processed using MATLAB software to obtain the above-mentioned parameters. All the images of LC textures at different temperatures are separately uploaded in the MATLAB software. The variations of the parameters are calculated with respect to temperature plotted.

The image contrast of the textures of 5CB taken from 200 to 400 °C is shown in terms of graphical view in Fig. 4a and corresponding glucose added 5CB (5CBG) is

shown in Fig. 4b. The homogeneity of the images of textures of the samples is graphically represented in Fig. 5a for 5CB and Fig. 5b for 5CBG. The energy of the pixels of the textures of the samples are plotted in the same temperature range in Fig. 6a and b. Other statistical parameters, that is, correlation and standard deviation, are shown in Figs. 7a and 8a for 5CB and Figs. 7b and 8b for 5CBG. These graphs helped to find the phase transitions of the studied samples and checked with our previous studies. The contrast and standard deviation have shown upward bump in their values with increasing temperature, whereas the behaviour of the other computed parameters like energy, homogeneity and correlation has shown downward bump in their values with increasing temperature. The remarkable changes in the corresponding parameters are very clear at phase transitions of the samples. All the significant peaks of the above plots are related to nematic phase of the 5CB and 5CBG [18, 21].

As contrast represents the distinguishable feature of the sample from other surroundings in terms of vision, Fig. 4a and b reveals that the nematic phase of the liquid crystal material possesses high contrast compared to its crystal and liquid states, therefore helps the author to mark the liquid crystal sample in its mesogenic state for display device applications. The homogeneity of the samples 5CB and 5CBG is minimum at their nematic phase, which strengthen the stability of the samples. Homogeneity represents the changes in intensity of the image, so the change in the intensity is minimum in nematic state of the liquid crystal, which is observed from Fig. 5a and b. Energy of the textures reports the relative variation in the colour or brightness of the pictures over a localized region. From Fig. 6a and b, it is very clear that the rate of change of colour or brightness is minimum for both 5CB and 5CBG in their nematic states. This explores that changes in pixels or colour or brightness of the texture is high in orderly mannered crystal and disordered liquid states of the samples. Again stability of the texture is achieved in the nematic phase of the samples. The function of displacement of the Kernel over the image is the correlation of the image and is showing deeper value at nematic phase of the samples. The displacement of filter over the textural positions of the samples was observed low at nematic state and high at solid and liquid states. The glucose dispersed 4-cyano-4'-pentybiphenyl has exhibited different behaviour compared to its pure form. This is observed from Fig. 7a and b. The correlation values of 5CB are minimum in nematic phase, and for 5CBG, the minimum correlation is observed beyond its liquid state. This feature reports that glucose particles are intact with the molecules of 5CB and influenced its lattice [19].

The power level measurement of the AC signal from the camera is known as standard deviation and the

Fig. 1 UV–visible absorbance and transmittance of 5CB and 5CBG

(a)

(b)

Table 1 Absorption, transmission, and refractive indices of 5CB and 5CBG

Sample	5CB		5CBG	
Absorption frequency (Hz)	9.84×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}	10.7×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}
Absorbance (A.U)	4.2	0.9748	4.3	0.9452
Transmission frequency (Hz)	9.61×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}	10.2×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}
Transmittance (A.U)	0.1143	10.59	0.1177	11.34
Frequency	9.46×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}	9.93×10^{14}	8.88×10^{14}
Refractive index	2.2314	0.4172	2.6979	0.3990

samples under study have shown remarkable peaks at nematic and isotropic states as observed from Fig. 8a and b. This shows that the power level will be incremented whenever phase changes. Also, the 5CB sample exhibited less standard deviation in its nematic phase when compared to isotropic phase; however, 5CBG has shown quite opposite behaviour in this feature. The specific values of computed image parameters from MATLAB at different temperatures of 5CB and 5CBG are tabulated in Table 3. From Table 3, it is clear that contrast of 5CB and 5CBG was the same in crystal state and drastically decreased in nematic phase of 5CB and increased in nematic phase of 5CBG. The correlation values also showed controversial variation when moving from crystal to nematic phase in 5CB and 5CBG. The value is decreased in 5CB and increased in 5CBG. However, the energy of the images of 5CB and 5CBG increased while transforming from

Fig. 2 Refractive index profile of 5CB and 5CBG

Fig. 3 Band gap profile of 5CB and 5CBG

crystal to nematic phase. Homogeneity of the samples even after including glucose is not much changed. This implies that the intensity of images is maintained with less change.

Now, the very interesting feature of these studies is that the standard deviation of the samples has changed drastically with reverse behaviour between 5 and 5CBG. It is

Table 2 Energy band gap of 5CB and 5CBG

Sample	Direct band gap (in eV)
5CB	3.68
5CBG	4.05

Fig. 4 Temperature-dependent textural contrast of **a** 5CB, **b** 5CBG

(a)

(b)

observed from Table 3 that 5CB has given increment in standard deviation, whereas 5CBG has decreased in transformation phase. This implies that power level of 5CB is more in nematic phase and it is less in 5CBG in order to

acquire AC signal from the camera. So, the surface orientations of the 5CB are evenly altered due to the dispersion of glucose which is evident from the computations.

Fig. 5 Temperature-dependent textural homogeneity of **a** 5CB, **b** 5CBG

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Temperature-dependent textural energy of **a** 5CB, **b** 5CBG

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Temperature-dependent textural correlation of **a** 5CB, **b** 5CBG

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 Temperature-dependent textural standard deviation of **a** 5CB, **b** 5CBG

(a)

(b)

Table 3 Image processed parameters of 5CB and 5CBG

Sample	5CB		5CBG	
Transition temperature	25–35 °C		23–33 °C	
LC phase	N		N	
Temperature	25 °C (Cr)	34 °C (N)	23 °C (Cr)	32 °C (N)
Contrast	0.0451	0.00256	0.0451	0.00896
Correlation	0.9987	0.84106	0.78655	0.95918
Energy	0.4674	0.7565	0.64254	0.76701
Homogeneity	0.9704	0.9844	0.96804	0.99752
Standard deviation	28.30295	49.01524	17.54226	14.45041

4 Conclusions

The samples under study 5CB and 5CBG are characterized through UV–visible spectroscopy and image processing. The UV–visible spectroscopy is in support to the presence of dispersed glucose in the 5CB. The advanced statistical parameters of the digital images of the textures of these samples computed reveal the highest stability of the nematic phase of both the samples. Contrast, homogeneity, energy, correlation and standard deviation values are computed using MATLAB software to the digital images of the samples which are taken in cooling mode. All the computed parameters are inter-related to each other, which strongly gives the information about the surface orientations of the samples. The increased values of contrast, energy homogeneity and correlation parameters of the glucose dispersed 5CB molecules is observed and is imputed to the carbon and oxygen interactions of the mutual molecules. The lattice distortion is not observed much in 5CBG as nematic phase still persists. These studies have made the authors to conclude that the 5CB is a strong liquid crystal material and will exhibit surface changes due to the bio-molecules.

Data Availability the calculated parameters in this article are good agreement for the given liquid crystals materials exhibit surface changes.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest The authors declare no competing interests.

References

1. F. Reinitzer, J. Liq. Cryst. **9**, 421–441 (1888)
2. X. Lyu, A. Xiao, D. Shi, Y. Li, Z. Shen, E.Q. Chen, S. Zheng, X.H. Fan, Q.F. Zhou, J. Polym. **202**, 122740–122741 (2020)
3. T. Kato, M. Yoshio, T. Ichikawa, B. Soberats, H. Ohno, M. Funahashi, Nat. Rev. Mater. **2**, 17001 (2017)
4. T. Kato, J. Uchida, T. Ichikawa, T. Sakamoto, Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **57**, 4355–4371 (2018)
5. K. Goossens, K. Lava, C.W. Bielawski, K. Binnemans, Chem. Rev. **116**, 4643–4807 (2016)
6. R. Alnoman, F.K. Al-Nazawi, H.A. Ahmed, M. Hagar, Mol. **24**, 4293–4310 (2019)
7. R.B. Alnoman, H.A. Ahmed, M. Hagar, K.A.A. Al-Ola, B.S. Alrefay, B.A. Haddad, R.F. Albalawi, R.H. Aljuhani, L.D. Aloqebi, S.F. Alsenami, Mol. **25**, 1549–1555 (2020)
8. R. Rihani, N. Tasnim, M. Javed, J.O. Usoro, T.M. D'Souza, T.H. Ware, J.J. Pancrazio, J. Neuromod. **14**, 13364 (2021)
9. R.T. Rihani, A.M. Stiller, J.O. Usoro, J. Lawson, H. Kim, B.J. Black, D. Vindhya Reddy, J. Maeng, V.D. Varner, T.H. Ware, J.J. Pancrazio, Acta Biomater. **111**, 54–64 (2020)
10. A.P. Gardymova, M.N. Krakhalev, V.Y. Zyryanov, Mol. **25**, 1740–1747 (2020)
11. P.K. Bhowmik, M.K.M. Al-Karawi, S.T. Killarney, E.J. Dizo, A. Chang, J. Kim, S.L. Chen, R.C.G. Principe, A. Ho, H. Han, Mol. **25**, 2435–2440 (2020)
12. S.M. Alauddin, N.F.K. Aripin, T.S. Velayutham, A. Martinez-Felipe, Mol. **25**, 2579–2591 (2020)
13. K.P. Bhowmik, Molecules **26**, 3713 (2021)
14. K.M. Herbert, H.E. Fowler, J.M. McCracken, K.R. Schlafmann, J.A. Koch, T.J. White, Nat. Rev. Mater. **7**, 23–28 (2021)
15. J. Krakhalev, Sci. Rep. **11**, 17433 (2021)
16. O.A. Alhaddad, K.A.A. Al-Ola, M. Hagar, H.A. Ahmed, Mol. **25**, 1510–1519 (2020)
17. L.A. Al-Mutabagani, L.A. Alshabanah, H.A. Ahmed, M. Hagar, K.A.A. Al-Ola, Mol. **25**, 1420–1429 (2020)
18. P. Zhu, W. Liu, B. Li, Y. Li, Y. Yang, Liq. Cryst. **48**, 1365–1372 (2020)
19. D. Wan, X. Gu, J. Li, M. Hu, Z. Che, Q. Guo, L. Mo, J. Li, Z. An, J. Liq. Cryst. **48**, 1392–1401 (2021)
20. M. Thomas, Juergen, App. Spect. **74**, (2020)
21. P. Makuła, M. Pacia, W. Macyk, J. Phys. Chem. Lett. **9**(23), 6814–6817 (2018)
22. R. Vafaie, A. Vahedi, M.S. Zakerhamidi, H. Tajalli, J. Liq. Cryst. **48**, 1417–1428 (2021)
23. K.V.S.N. Raju, S. Salma Begum, S. Babu, J. Pharm. Sci. Res. **9**, 269–274 (2017)

Publisher's Note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Springer Nature or its licensor (e.g. a society or other partner) holds exclusive rights to this article under a publishing agreement with the author(s) or other rightsholder(s); author self-archiving of the accepted manuscript version of this article is solely governed by the terms of such publishing agreement and applicable law.

Search in mail

- 99+ Compose
- Mail
- Inbox 308
- Starred
- Snoozed
- Sent
- Drafts
- Meet More

Labels
personal

A Nagarjuna

Sir, Reply mail to 24th Jul 2023 Please find the attachment of my modified paper after reducing the plagiarism

TKREC conference <icdtccs@tkrec.ac.in>
to me

Jul 27

Dear Authors,

Similarity Index of the paper is 7%. Thank you for sending the paper to ICDTCCS.
Your article is selected for the Publication as well as presentation.

For payment.

Account number	: 148113500000654
Bank	: The Karur Vysya Bank, Meerpet, Hyderabad.
IFSC	: KVBL0001481
Beneficiary Name	: TEEGALA KRISHNA REDDY ENGINEERING COLLEGE

Complete the form

<https://forms.gle/D4YBga8dM1LMeX3G9>

Speed of sound and Viscosity theories of benzoate liquid mixtures

A.NAGARJUNA¹, B.M PRAVEEN², K.V.S.N Raju³

¹PDF Scholar, Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

²Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

³Department of Physics, Adikavi Nannaya University, Tadepalligudem, WG-534101, A P, India

ABSTRACT:

Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) values of various mole fractions of **System I:** Ethyl-4- hydroxy benzoate (E4HB) with aniline (AN), o- chloroaniline (OCA) and **System II:** P-methoxy benzoic acid (PMBA) with formamide (FA), D-methyl formamide (DMF) were measured using the accepted methods at 303.15, 308.15, and 313.15K. Measured values of speed of sound and viscosity have been correlate using the empirical relations Nomoto's relation, Ideal mixture relation, Junjie's method and Rao's relation for speed of sound and various relations due to Gruenberg-Nissan model, Hind rule, Arrhenius equation, Wijk and Kendall- Monroe relation for viscosity. The validity of these theories will check the goodness of fit from chi square test, average percentage error (APE) for speed of sound and interaction parameter, standard deviation(σ) for viscosity were calculated.

Key words: Mole fraction, accepted methods, empirical relations, speed of sound, viscosity

INTRODUCTION:

Measurement of speed of sound gives the valuable information about the physicochemical behavior of the fluid and fluid mixtures. Several empirical relations and theories are available for the theoretical computation of speed of sound and viscosity in fluid and fluid mixtures. They are broadly used in perfumery and pesticides. The benzenes are a widely used industrial chemical. Benzene is found in crude oil and is a major part of gasoline. It's used to make metabolites, plastics, resins, synthetic fibers, rubber lubricants, dyes, detergents and pharmacy. The amides of commercial importance are acetamide, also called formamide and dimethylformamide, which are used as solvents, sulfa drugs and nylons and amines play important roles in many drugs, cosmetics, detergents, plastics, and antimicrobials. In present study the authors want to observe the molecular interactions between the similar featured fluids using speed of sound and viscosity theories. [1, 3]

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION:

The binary liquid mixes were created using mass variation for several samples just before began the experiment began. Measurements of the speed of sound ranged from 303.15 K to 313.15K by using ultrasonic interferometer(M/s Mittal Enterprises, India) operating at a fixed frequency of 2 MHz with an accuracy of ± 0.1 m/s.

The density of pure component and its multiple components was determined with an accuracy of ± 0.02 mg using 10ml specific gravity bottles on a high-precision electronic digital balance (Baijnath Premnath SF

400A, Kanpur, USA). Viscosity was measured with Viscometer by Ostwald regarding E-4-HB and P-MBA binary systems. Various temperatures were used to calibrate the viscometer, by using double-distilled water. The experimentally measured data of density, viscosity, and sound velocity were compared with theoretical relations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Speed of sound theories: The prognostic activities of speeds of sound theories based upon the brawn of interactivity persuading in a framework. The deviation in upshots may be ascribed to the precision made in these theories for the odd-odd speaks interactivities between the notes in the whole captivation. This implies the impedance relation (U_{IMP}) and Nomoto (U_{NMR}) and reveals merit of concurrence among theoretical to measured data. The measured values of speed of sound along with their theoretically determined values of Nomoto's, Ideal mixing, Junjie's, Vandael & Vangel and Rao's [4-7] with mole fraction in the twofold fluid blends of p-MBA /E-4-HB at three different temperatures were noticed at table 1 & 2. The APE and chi square test (χ) is also included for the individual twofold blends. U for both real and framework increases/decreases with ρ and z compliance with mole fraction. This drift is due to own alliance of solvent molecules have more strong dipole-induced interactions between the molecules. For sound production Eyring and Kincaid [14] was proposed that U should increase/decrease with alteration of L_f decreases in mixing of speaks.

On other side, slight changes in Junjie U_{JN} , Rao's (U_R) and Vandael & Vangel (U_{VDV}) relations. This type of alterations are presumed in the blends due to volume variation after fluid mixing, also there is much deviation in theoretical prediction of U with measured data recommend the exits of solid inclination for the relationship between the segment atoms because of hydrogen bond in the mix.

The Chi-square and APE values are less for all these theories. These upshots are used to judge non-ideality behavior in the fluid blends and it can also perceive the note ally with positive/negative alteration in ' U ' specifies atomic dissociation/ association of species by heap of solvent. Regarding this behavior of twofold blends implies positive digression in ' U ' accredits elastic nature of spherical notes is liable for the atomic coalition. [2,15] **Viscosity theories:** The standard deviation is small in all systems where the interactions are less there exists strong interactions between mixes. This shows that, the envisage flair of various viscosity theories depend upon the strength interplay prevailing in a system. The experimental and theoretical viscosity values of Gruenberg-Nissan model, Hind rule, Arrhenius equation, Wijk and Kendall-Monroe relations [9-13] for pMBA /E-4-HB systems are presented in table 3&4 along with interaction parameters and standard deviations. On all of these models fairly predicted viscosity theories, they are reasonably close to the measured values for the twofold mix reported in this work, this showing the validity of studied theoretic models for twofold mix. Out of all equations used to correlate measured data of mix viscosity standard deviation calculated using Wijk and Hind is lower than other theories. Hence, Hind and Wijk theories are more convenient and fit well for this mix. [8,16]

CONCLUSION

The deliberated values of speed of sound and viscosity from several theories have been correlated with the measured values. Speed of sound values obtained from Nomoto's and Vandael & Vangel relations are in good concurrence with the measured values. The Chi square values also support these upshots and the observed deviation of theoretical values of speed of sound from the experimental values is attributed to the presence of intermolecular interactions. The experimental values of viscosity are also correlated with the empirical relations of viscosity and these are in good agreement with the experimental values. It may be concluded that out of these theories, Nomoto's relation in the speed of sound and Hind is in the viscosity were the best suited relation for the fluid mixtures.

Table 1: Speed of sound theories for the binary system of E -4-HB with aniline/o-Chloroaniline at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

X_1	U_{EXP} m.s ⁻¹	U_{NOM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{IMR} m.s ⁻¹	U_{JM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{VDV} m.s ⁻¹	U_R m.s ⁻¹
E-4-HB + Aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4	1224.4
0.2136	1318.2	1318.2	1314.0	1316.6	1318.8	1312.2
0.4547	1398.6	1394.0	1397.4	1391.2	1396.6	1389.2
0.6493	1454.6	1454.2	1452.6	1451.8	1458.4	1456.0
0.8753	1507.4	1507.8	1504.6	1507.4	1507.4	1507.4
1.0000	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6
APE		0.0006	0.0052	0.0013	0.0058	0.0149
chi square(χ)		0.0046	0.0622	0.0038	0.0613	0.1714
308.15 K						
0.0000	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4	1214.4
0.2136	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2	1286.2
0.4547	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8	1378.8
0.6493	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4	1484.4
0.8753	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6	1516.6
1.0000	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6
APE		0.0015	0.0057	0.0011	0.0050	0.0165
chi square(χ)		0.0054	0.0674	0.0035	0.0647	0.1239
313.15K						
0.0000	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4	1192.4
0.2136	1248.8	1248.2	1241.8	1240.8	1239.6	1249.6
0.4547	1378.2	1378.6	1373.4	1371.6	1381.0	1376.8
0.6493	1464.6	1464.0	1462.8	1468.0	1470.8	1461.4
0.8753	1544.2	1544.8	1541.6	1547.4	1539.4	1549.0
1.0000	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6

APE	0.0004	0.0032	0.0007	0.0039	0.0032	
chi square(χ)	0.0046	0.0374	0.0086	0.0329	0.0272	
E-4-HB +O-Chloroaniline						
303.15K						
0.0000	1464.4	1464.4	1464.4	1464.4	1464.4	1464.4
0.2367	1488.2	1488.6	1481.2	1484.6	1482.6	1486.6
0.4158	1492.6	1492.2	1494.6	1498.2	1494.2	1499.8
0.6304	1504.6	1504.0	1507.6	1506.0	1509.8	1505.2
0.8786	1517.4	1517.2	1519.4	1512.8	1511.4	1518.6
1.0000	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6	1524.6
APE	0.0006	0.0062	0.0005	0.0068	0.0132	
Chi square(χ)	0.0056	0.0548	0.0048	0.0052	0.1434	
308.15K						
	1458.2	1458.2	1458.2	1458.2	1458.2	1458.2
0.0000						
0.2367	1474.2	1474.8	1478.2	1471.4	1474.6	1470.6
0.4158	1494.6	1494.2	1492.4	1494.0	1491.8	1496.8
0.6304	1518.8	1518.0	1512.6	1514.6	1516.2	1510.0
0.8786	1530.4	1530.6	1532.4	1536.4	1534.2	1538.4
1.0000	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6	1542.6
APE	0.0005	0.0027	0.0003	0.0036	0.0185	
Chi square(χ)	0.0043	0.0416	0.0027	0.0549	0.1136	
313.15 K						
0.0000	1438.4	1438.4	1438.4	1438.4	1438.4	1438.4
0.2367	1467.2	1467.2	1467.2	1467.2	1467.2	1467.2
0.4158	1492.8	1492.8	1492.8	1492.8	1492.8	1492.8
0.6304	1524.2	1524.2	1524.2	1524.2	1524.2	1524.2
0.8786	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6
1.0000	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6	1571.6
APE	0.0004	0.0039	0.0005	0.0026	0.0142	
Chi square(χ)	0.0063	0.0439	0.0035	0.0506	0.1539	

Table 2: Speed of sound theories for the binary system of p-MBA with formamide/DMF at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

X_1	U_{EXP} m.s ⁻¹	U_{NOM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{IMR} m.s ⁻¹	U_{JM} m.s ⁻¹	U_{VDV} m.s ⁻¹	U_R m.s ⁻¹
p-MBA +Formamide						
303.15K						
0.0000	1583.4	1583.4	1583.4	1583.4	1583.4	1583.4
0.2032	1580.2	1580.2	1580.6	1581.4	1582.2	1581.6
0.4150	1574.6	1574.6	1574.2	1576.6	1574.0	1575.4

0.6344	1568.0	1568.0	1568.8	1568.4	1561.2	1567.2
0.8576	1562.8	1562.8	1562.4	1561.8	1560.6	1561.6
1.0000	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6	1557.6
APE		0.0001	0.0042	0.0002	0.0062	0.0105
chi square(χ)		0.0074	0.0546	0.0056	0.0457	0.1407

308.15K

0.0000	1576.4	1576.4	1576.4	1576.4	1576.4	1576.4
0.2032	1570.2	1570.2	1570.2	1570.2	1570.2	1570.2
0.4150	1568.8	1568.8	1568.8	1568.8	1568.8	1568.8
0.6344	1554.6	1554.6	1554.6	1554.6	1554.6	1554.6
0.8576	1547.4	1547.4	1547.4	1547.4	1547.4	1547.4
1.0000	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6
APE		0.0002	0.0069	0.0002	0.0072	0.0184
chi square(χ)		0.0061	0.0476	0.0046	0.0606	0.1871

313.15K

0.0000	1572.4	1572.4	1572.4	1572.4	1572.4	1572.4
0.2032	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2	1568.2
0.4150	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6	1545.6
0.6344	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8	1538.8
0.8576	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2	1530.2
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
APE		0.0004	0.0036	0.0008	0.0036	0.0022
chi square(χ)		0.0042	0.0397	0.0084	0.0397	0.0247

p-MBA+DMF**303.15K**

0.0000	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4	1458.4
0.2731	1486.2	1486.2	1481.2	1485.2	1486.0	1480.2
0.4407	1508.6	1508.6	1506.6	1503.0	1501.2	1518.2
0.6993	1524.8	1524.8	1529.8	1527.2	1523.6	1531.8
0.8139	1541.4	1541.4	1540.4	1543.6	1544.8	1544.6
1.0000	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2
APE		0.0006	0.0044	0.0004	0.0077	0.0167
Chi square(χ)		0.0059	0.0812	0.0052	0.0739	0.1296

308.15K

0.0000	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4	1434.4
0.2731	1468.6	1468.2	1463.6	1464.6	1461.0	1466.2
0.4407	1494.8	1494.8	1492.2	1497.2	1495.6	1490.6
0.6993	1512.2	1512.0	1516.8	1511.8	1515.8	1520.4
0.8139	1522.4	1522.4	1521.4	1526.2	1502.4	1526.8
1.0000	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6	1533.6
APE		0.0008	0.0068	0.0006	0.0071	0.0137
Chi square(χ)		0.0050	0.0719	0.0021	0.0608	0.1449

313.15 K						
0.0000	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4	1422.4
0.2731	1458.6	1458.2	1454.6	1451.0	1456.6	1450.6
0.4407	1482.2	1482.4	1483.4	1484.6	1487.0	1485.8
0.6993	1504.8	1504.0	1507.2	1506.2	1509.2	1505.2
0.8139	1514.6	1514.8	1511.8	1517.8	1518.8	1511.0
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
APE		0.0007	0.0038	0.0005	0.0063	0.0286
Chi square(χ)		0.0049	0.0477	0.0029	0.0576	0.1568

Table 3 Viscosity theories for the binary system of E -4-HB with aniline/o-Chloroaniline at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

x_1	η_{Exp} (mPas)	Hind (mPas)	Gruenberg -Nissan (mPas)	Wijk (mPas)	Arrhenius (mPas)	Kendall- Monroe equation (mPas)
E-4-HB + aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234	2.234
0.2136	2.106	2.106	2.104	2.108	2.105	2.107
0.4547	1.968	1.968	1.967	1.964	1.962	1.961
0.6493	1.663	1.663	1.665	1.667	1.666	1.668
0.8753	1.419	1.419	1.418	1.416	1.412	1.415
1.0000	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286
Interaction parameter		1.114	0.434	1.163	2.209	2.064
Standard deviation(σ)		0.232	0.318	0.501	0.525	0.226
308.15 K						
0.0000	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943	1.943
0.2136	1.761	1.761	1.763	1.764	1.765	1.768
0.4547	1.594	1.594	1.597	1.596	1.598	1.595
0.6493	1.375	1.375	1.376	1.372	1.371	1.376
0.8753	1.258	1.258	1.251	1.256	1.257	1.252
1.0000	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196
Interaction parameter		1.071	0.446	0.905	2.484	2.467
Standard deviation(σ)		0.162	0.204	0.416	0.878	0.621
313.15 K						
0.0000	1.724	1.724	1.724	1.724	1.724	1.724
0.2136	1.587	1.587	1.584	1.588	1.582	1.586
0.4547	1.438	1.438	1.436	1.435	1.437	1.434
0.6493	1.391	1.391	1.397	1.394	1.396	1.398
0.8753	1.269	1.269	1.265	1.267	1.263	1.264
1.0000	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172

Interaction parameter	0.962	0.207	0.715	2.250	2.234	
Standard deviation(σ)	0.107	0.108	0.319	0.902	0.746	
E-4-HB+Ocholoro aniline						
303.15 K						
0.0000	3.814	3.814	3.814	3.814	3.814	3.814
0.2367	3.426	3.426	3.423	3.427	3.425	3.422
0.4158	3.121	3.121	3.124	3.126	3.125	3.128
0.6304	2.843	2.843	2.842	2.845	2.848	2.847
0.8786	2.518	2.518	2.516	2.512	2.514	2.519
1.0000	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286	1.286
Interaction parameter	2.124	2.364	2.823	1.323	1.163	
Standard deviation(σ)	0.140	0.229	0.546	0.728	0.847	
308.15 K						
0.0000	3.476	3.476	3.476	3.476	3.476	3.476
0.2367	3.266	3.266	3.264	3.268	3.265	3.269
0.4158	3.047	3.047	3.042	3.046	3.041	3.045
0.6304	2.784	2.784	2.786	2.788	2.789	2.782
0.8786	2.441	2.441	2.444	2.442	2.445	2.446
1.0000	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196	1.196
Interaction parameter	2.043	2.145	2.362	1.351	0.987	
Standard deviation(σ)	0.136	0.437	0.641	0.726	0.981	
313.15 K						
0.0000	3.105	3.105	3.105	3.105	3.105	3.105
0.2367	2.962	2.962	2.967	2.969	2.961	2.963
0.4158	2.549	2.549	2.546	2.543	2.545	2.546
0.6304	1.954	1.954	1.955	1.958	1.956	1.957
0.8786	1.627	1.627	1.624	1.623	1.628	1.625
1.0000	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172	1.172
Interaction parameter	2.046	2.214	2.410	1.839	1.256	
Standard deviation(σ)	0.082	0.138	0.363	0.565	0.728	

Table 4 Viscosity theories for the binary system of p-MBA with formamide/DMF at T= 303.15 K, 308.15K and 313.15K

x_1	η_{Exp} (mPas)	Hind (mPas)	Gruenberg -Nissan (mPas)	Wijk (mPas)	Arrhenius (mPas)	Kendall- Monroe equation (mPas)
p-MBA + Formamide						
303.15 K						
0.0000	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782	2.782

0.2032	2.425	2.425	2.428	2.422	2.429	2.426
0.4150	2.193	2.193	2.196	2.195	2.198	2.197
0.6344	1.968	1.968	1.962	1.961	1.965	1.960
0.8576	1.749	1.747	1.742	1.741	1.740	1.746
1.0000	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583
Interaction parameter	1.174		0.504	1.046	2.829	2.260
Standard deviation(σ)	0.263		0.358	0.651	0.725	0.462

308.15 K

0.0000	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465	2.465
0.2032	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139	2.139
0.4150	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965	1.965
0.6344	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648	1.648
0.8576	1.672	1.672	1.675	1.677	1.676	1.670
1.0000	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424
Interaction parameter	1.071		0.446	0.905	2.484	2.467
Standard deviation(σ)	0.162		0.204	0.416	0.878	0.621

313.15 K

0.0000	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254
0.2032	2.017	2.017	2.015	2.014	2.010	2.018
0.4150	1.872	1.872	1.874	1.877	1.879	1.876
0.6344	1.640	1.640	1.643	1.646	1.648	1.640
0.8576	1.526	1.526	1.522	1.527	1.524	1.525
1.0000	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345
Interaction parameter	0.962		0.207	0.715	2.250	2.234
Standard deviation(σ)	0.107		0.108	0.319	0.902	0.746

p-MBA + DMF**303.15 K**

0.0000	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772	0.772
0.2731	0.923	0.923	0.926	0.925	0.928	0.924
0.4407	1.234	1.234	1.232	1.236	1.237	1.235
0.6993	1.412	1.412	1.414	1.418	1.416	1.417
0.8139	1.523	1.523	1.525	1.527	1.528	1.526
1.0000	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583	1.583
Interaction parameter	1.082		1.004	0.972	0.875	0.807
Standard deviation(σ)	0.104		0.127	0.209	0.310	0.093

308.15 K

0.0000	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735	0.735
0.2731	0.893	0.893	0.895	0.897	0.896	0.898
0.4407	1.127	1.127	1.124	1.126	1.125	1.129
0.6993	1.262	1.262	1.267	1.264	1.268	1.269
0.8139	1.356	1.356	1.353	1.358	1.351	1.357
1.0000	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424	1.424

Interaction parameter	1.043	1.155	1.669	1.351	0.973
Standard deviation(σ)	0.083	0.039	0.014	0.120	0.140
313.15 K					
0.0000	0.682	0.682	0.682	0.682	0.682
0.2731	0.812	0.812	0.814	0.815	0.816
0.4407	0.966	0.966	0.967	0.965	0.968
0.6993	1.121	1.121	1.124	1.126	1.127
0.8139	1.249	1.249	1.247	1.245	1.246
1.0000	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345	1.345
Interaction parameter	1.017	0.994	0.817	0.639	0.560
Standard deviation(σ)	0.016	0.008	0.063	0.015	0.007

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors Dr. Nagarjuna. A, is thankful to his PDF supervisor Dr. B.M Praveen, Director, Research and innovation Cell, Srinivas University, Mangalore for his valuable suggestions and discussions

REFERENCES

1. Chinnarao, Dharmana, Ch V. Padmarao, Ch Beena, M. Srilatha, M. V. V. Ramanjaneyulu, Praveen Choppara, N. Murali, and B. Venkateswara Rao. "Acoustic, excess thermodynamical, molecular interaction and antimicrobial activity studies on binary liquid mixtures of geranyl acetate and benzyl benzoate in the temperature range of 303.15 K–318.15 K." *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* 100, no. 5 (2023): 100969.
2. Nagarjuna, A., KV Yamini Kanth, G. Balaji Prakash, and Debashis Das. "Molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures containing benzyl benzoate." *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry* 12, no. 4 (2019).
3. Pandey, J. D., V. Vyas, P. Jain, G. P. Dubey, N. Tripathi, and R. Dey. "Speed of sound, viscosity and refractive index of multicomponent systems: theoretical predictions from the properties of pure components." *Journal of molecular liquids* 81, no. 2 (1999): 123-133.
4. Shihab, Sk Suriya, Shaik Babu, and S. Sreehari Sastry. "Experimental and theoretical studies of speed of sound and viscosity in some liquid mixtures of Methyl Benzoate: a comparative study." *Rasayan Journal of chemistry* 9, no. 4 (2016).
5. Nomoto, Otohiko. "Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures." *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* 13, no. 12 (1958): 1528-1532.
6. Van Dael, W., and E. Vangeel. "Theory of ultrasound." *Van Dael W. Thermodynamic properties and velocity of sound, London: Butterworth* (1975).
7. Junjie, Z. "Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Benzene." *J. China Univ. Sci. Technol.* 14 (1984): 298-299.
8. Isakovich, M. A., and I. A. Chaban. "Propagation of sound in strongly viscous liquids." *Sov. Phys. JETP* 23(1966): 893-905.
9. Grunberg, LaAHN, and Alfred H. Nissan. "Mixture law for viscosity." *Nature* 164, no. 4175 (1949): 799-800.
10. Hind, R. K., E. McLaughlin, and A.R. Ubbelohde. "Structure and viscosity of liquids. Camphor+ pyrene mixtures"

Transactions of the Faraday Society 56 (1960): 328-330.

11. Katti, P. K., and M. M. Chaudhri. "Viscosities of Binary Mixtures of Benzyl Acetate with Dioxane, Aniline, and m-Cresol." *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* 9, no. 3 (1964): 442-443.
12. Siddharthan, N., and S. Jayakumar. "Theoretical evaluation of sound velocity, viscosity and density of binary liquid system." *Int. J. Chem. Sci* 14, no. 4 (2016).
13. Tamura, Mikio, and Michio Kurata. "On the viscosity of binary mixture of liquids." *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan* 25, no. 1 (1952): 32-38.
14. Kincaid, John F., and Henry Eyring. "Free volumes and free angle ratios of molecules in liquids." *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 6, no. 10 (1938): 620-629.
15. Nagarjuna, A., Kvsn Raju, P. Arunkumar, and N. Kotilingaiah. "Volumetric studies on ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate with substituted amide liquid mixtures at different temperatures." *Neuro Quantology* 20, no. 13 (2022): 1769-1777
16. Nagarjuna, A., Kvsn Raju, N. Kotilingaiah, and BM Praveen. "Comparative study of binary liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoate acid and amides."

STUDY OF INTERMOLECULAR INTERACTIONS IN ETHYL-4-HYDROXY BENZOATE LIQUID MIXTURE

^{1,2}A.Nagarjuna*^{1,3}KVSN Raju,⁴B.M Praveen

¹PDF Scholar, Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146, India

²Department of Physics, TKR Engineering College (R9), Medowli, Meerpet, Hyderabad-500097, India

³Department of Physics, Adikavi Nannaya University, Tadepalligudem, West godavari-534101, Andhra Pradesh, India

⁴Director, Research and Innovation Council, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka- 574146, India

ABSTRACT

The viscosity, density, and speed of sound values of binary mixture of ethyl-4-hydroxybenzoic acid with various mole fractions of aniline (AN), o-chloroaniline(OCA), and o-toluidine (OT) were measured from standard methods at 303.15, 308.15, and 313.15K. Many of thermo-acoustic characteristics, including compression that is isentropic(K_s^E), inter-molecular free length (L_f^E), molar volume (V_m^E), acoustic impedance (Z^E) and their excess properties, Measured values of speed of sound have been correlate using the empirical relations Nomoto's relation, Ideal mixture relation, Junjie's method and Rao's relation for the mixture. Further examine H-bonding creation in terms of inter-actions between dissimilar substances of considered binary system.

Key words: Binary mixtures, Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoic acid, excess properties and standard techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Study of Physico-chemical characteristics of fluid mixtures understanding the changes in thermodynamic behavior in a given mixture. One of the most significant uses of these features is their potential to reveal details of system structure effects and intermolecular interactions. Ethyl-4-hydroxy-benzoate, ($C_9H_{10}O_3$) is ethyl ester of p-hydroxy benzoic acid, or Ethyl paraben's. It is also utilized as an antifungal preservative and has a high melting point ranging from 115^o-118 °C. The antibacterial properties of ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate are used extensively in the food, cosmetic, and textile industries. It serves as an ingredient in cleaners, hair dyes, beverages, lotions, shampoos, and other products. On the other hand Anilines, also known as amino benzene or phenyl amine, are organic

EXPERIMENTAL

Compounds that belong to the category of substances in organic chemistry. These substances are classified as aromatic amines and are thought to be poisonous in nature. An oily liquid with a musty and fishy smell, aniline is yellowish and somewhat brownish in color. It has the stench of rotting fish.

The non-bonding interactions like hydrogen bonding and additional forces present, such as charge transfer, dispersive force, and dipole-dipole interactions that happen in the investigated liquid mixes are explained in this work. [1-3] The excess characteristics were calculate by using observe principles of viscosity (η), density (ρ), & sound speed (U), and these values were then simplified the theoretical relations of speed of sound then compare with the experimental results of speed of sound.

The density of pure component and its multiple components was determined with an accuracy of

± 0.02mg using 10ml specific gravity bottles on a high-precision electronic digital balance (Bajinath Premnath SF 400A, Kanpur, USA). Viscosity was measured with a viscometer by Ostwald. Various temperatures were used to calibrate the viscometer, by using double-distilled water.

Just before the experiment began, the binary liquid mixtures were created using mass variation for several samples. The final mole fraction's degree of uncertainty was calculated to be less than 0.0001 percent.

Measurements of the speed of sound ranged from 303.15 K to 313.15K by using ultrasonic interferometer (M/s Mittal Enterprises, India) operating at a fixed frequency of 2 MHz with an accuracy of ±0.1m/s. regarding binary systems, E-4-HB with aniline, O-Chloroaniline, O-toluidine. The unknown for speed of sound was ±0.7 m s⁻¹.

The experimentally measured data on density, viscosity and sound velocity are compared with research values and are shown in Table 01.

Table 01: Comparison of pure fluid densities, viscosities, and sound speeds with obtained values.

Liq.	Temp T (K)	Density(ρ)kg m ⁻³		Viscosity(η) mPaS		Speed of sound (U) m.s ⁻¹		C _p J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		lit	Expt	lit	Expt	lit	Expt	
E-4-HB [a]	303.15	1.1035	1.1037	1.283	1.293	1523.0	1525.4	304.03
	308.15	1.0313	1.0315	1.198	1.195	1541.4	1544.6	317.64
	313.15	0.9973	0.9985	1.175	1.173	1572.6	1576.2	338.27
Aniline [b]	303.15	0.8019	0.8023	2.224	2.235	1228.2	1225.4	191.01
	308.15	0.7982	0.7986	1.958	1.947	1217.8	1215.6	192.05
	313.15	0.7946	0.7864	1.700	1.723	1198.8	1197.2	193.70
O-Chloro Aniline [c]	303.15	1.2026	1.2025	3.825	3.815	1469.6	1464.8	218.41 ^e
	308.15	1.1980	1.1967	3.412	3.479	1453.3	1457.2	222.37 ^e
	313.15	1.1930	1.1946	3.060	3.105	1435.2	1434.8	231.82 ^e
O-toluidine [d]	303.15	0.9900	0.9935	4.433	4.467	1572.2	1575.4	211.30 ^e
	308.15	0.9859	0.9877	5.666	5.684	1553.2	1557.2	213.41 ^e
	313.15	-----	0.9748	-----	6.126	-----	1535.6	218.66 ^e

^a Reference [7] ^b Reference [8] ^c Reference [9] ^d Reference [10] ^e Estimated from NIST web book

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

(i) Excess Properties

The excess properties of research binary system E-4-HB containing aniline, O-chloroaniline and O-toluidine at, T = 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15K was calculated by using an excel spreadsheet and are shown in Figures 1–3 [4,5]

The observed values of K_s^E , V_m^E , L_f^E and Z^E can be explained by different effects depending on chemical, physical & geometrical properties of current components of binary system under

research. Physical interactions are mainly concerned with dispersion forces, which positively affect V_m^E and L_f^E . The positive V_m^E values over entire blend composition range may be due to disruption of predominant hydrogen structures by formation of weak hydrogen bonds, between E-4-HB and OCA/OT molecules and insertion of smaller molecules into cavities created by larger molecules, Z values that are positive for mixtures in composition range indicate that interaction between E-4-HB and substituted amines is stronger than the ester or

amine–amine interactions. How strongly two things interact E-4-HB and was replaced amino particles appears to be highly reliant on position of ethyl groups in amino molecules. Substituted amine, when molecules are pure, they have a smaller more H-bonds than primary amines. Chemical/ specific interactions arise from formation and breaking of hydrogen bonds and another complex inter-actions, ending in negative upshots of L_f^E and K_s^E due to geometric effects that allow molecules of smaller size to enter the structure of other molecules.

Mixing E-4-HB with replaced amines can lead to H-bond formation between amideH-atom and ester carbonyl group, and vice versa. The sound speed of amine mixtures was found to decrease with increasing E-4-HB mole fraction

and that of substituted amines with increasing hydroxyl mole fraction three contrasting temperatures. The outcome displays a positive deviation from Z^E for all compositions [6, 11]. Plausible qualitative interpretations for behavior of this mixture with composition have proposed. As mentioned earlier, amine molecule has an extensive intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonding network due to the strong proton accepting group C=O in the molecule. Addition of E-4-HB with OT causes slow hydrogen bond dissociation in hydroxyl molecule, at same time, hydrogen bonding between Aniline and E-4HB is also possible because it has three H-bond moreover, donations to the C=O group of proton acceptors. [12, 13]

Fig.1 Excess isentropic compressibility with respect to mole fraction of E-4-HB + Aniline/OCA /OT at three different temperatures

Fig. 2 Excess molar volume changes depending on mole fraction of E-4-HB + Aniline/OCA /OT at three various temperatures

Fig.3 Extra free length in relation to mole fraction varies of E-4-HB + Aniline/ OCA / OT at three different temperatures

(ii) Speed of sound theories

The exhibitoryadroitnessof speeds of sound theories based upon the brawn of interactivity influence in a framework. The measured values of speed of sound along with their theoretically determined values of Nomoto's, Ideal mixing, Junjie's, Vandael & Vangel and Rao's [16-19] with mole fraction in the twofold fluid blends of E-4-HB + amines at three different temperatures were noticed at table 2. The deviation in upshots may be ascribed to the précised made in these theories for the odd-odd speaks interactivities between the motes in the whole captivation. This implies the impedance relation (U_{IMR}) and Nomoto (U_{NMR}) and reveals merit of concurrence among theoretical to measured data. Speed of sound for both real and experimental increases/decreases with acoustic impedance compliance with mole fraction. This drift is due to own alliance of solvent

molecules have more strong dipole-induced dipole interactions between the molecules.

From table 2 we also observe slight changes in Junjie U_{JN} , Rao's (U_R) and Vandael & Vangel (U_{VDV}) relations. This type of alterations are presumed in the blends due to volume variation after fluid mixing, also there is much deviation in theoretical prediction of speed of sound with measured data recommend the exits of solid inclination for the relationship between the segment atoms because of hydrogen bond in the mix.

The Chi-square and APE values are less for all these theories. These results are used to judge non-ideality behavior in the fluid blends and it can also perceive themoteally with positive/negative alteration in speed of sound specifies atomic dissociation/association between molecules.

0.2469	1481.2	1481.6	1481.8	1481.6	1483.2	1484.2
0.4353	1496.6	1496.2	1496.2	1493.0	1495.6	1498.6
0.6674	1514.4	1514.8	1514.6	1517.4	1516.4	1519.4
0.8759	1532.8	1532.0	1532.4	1535.8	1537.8	1536.8
1.0000	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6
APE		0.0001	0.0063	0.0002	0.0027	0.0103
Chi square		0.0029	0.0216	0.0013	0.0419	0.1086
313.15 K						
0.0000	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8	1434.8
0.2469	1474.2	1474.4	1474.6	1471.2	1473.2	1476.2
0.4353	1496.4	1496.8	1496.0	1495.4	1498.4	1493.4
0.6674	1527.6	1527.0	1527.6	1523.6	1521.6	1528.6
0.8759	1561.8	1561.6	1561.4	1564.8	1563.8	1566.8
1.0000	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2
APE		0.0003	0.0052	0.0006	0.0037	0.0137
Chi square		0.0043	0.0409	0.0047	0.0512	0.1829
E-4-HB +O-Toluidine						
303.15K						
0.0000	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4	1575.4
0.2068	1563.2	1563.6	1563.8	1561.2	1565.2	1566.2
0.4051	1552.8	1552.2	1552.0	1554.8	1553.8	1555.8
0.6076	1541.6	1541.8	1541.2	1546.6	1544.6	1546.6
0.8054	1536.4	1536.0	1536.6	1533.4	1535.4	1532.4
1.0000	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4	1525.4
APE		0.0003	0.0051	0.0005	0.0052	0.0141
Chi square		0.0021	0.0358	0.0037	0.0062	0.1254
308.15K						
0.0000	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2	1557.2
0.2068	1553.2	1553.4	1553.0	1551.2	1554.2	1556.2
0.4051	1549.6	1549.8	1549.8	1548.6	1542.6	1547.6
0.6076	1547.4	1547.6	1547.2	1546.4	1548.4	1546.4
0.8054	1546.8	1546.0	1546.4	1548.8	1545.8	1545.0
1.0000	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6	1544.6
APE		0.0002	0.0045	0.0003	0.0036	0.0113
Chi square		0.0021	0.0201	0.0010	0.0309	0.1126
313.15 K						
0.0000	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6	1535.6
0.2068	1540.2	1540.8	1540.0	1541.2	1543.2	1544.2
0.4051	1545.4	1545.2	1542.8	1543.4	1544.4	1547.4
0.6076	1550.6	1550.4	1551.2	1553.6	1552.6	1554.6
0.8054	1567.8	1560.0	1560.4	1562.8	1564.8	1565.8
1.0000	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2	1576.2
APE		0.0002	0.0048	0.0004	0.0036	0.0129
Chi square		0.0047	0.0386	0.0038	0.0418	0.1523

(iii) FT-IR SPECTRA

FT-IR data of fewer cleaners (Figures 4-7) and their mix with other compositions were performed in the wave number range of 500-3500 cm^{-1} . The single-shot FT-IR spectra of this three blends with different compositions show that there are some differences in peaks that include components, specifically 30% E-4-HB with 70% aniline and two more compositions for E-4-HB+OCA/OT blends, but there is no difference in compositional peaks of other two blends. A partial assignment of solvent mixtures and pure solvent bands has been performed and

discusses accordingly. The main absorption bands of esters, are due to C=O (extending) & N-H (extending) motions. The C=O shift (extending) frequency of various amines in E-4-HB also results from the breaking of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds in amides and their formation between different molecules in liquid mixtures. This is due to intra-intermolecular hydrogen-bond dissociation of amine molecules or its formation between molecules. [14, 15]

Fig 4. FT-IR analysis of Ethyl-4-hydroxybenzoate pure component

Fig 5. FTIR analysis of Aniline pure component

Fig 6. FT-IR analysis of O-Chloroaniline pure component

Fig 7. FT-IR analysis of O-Toluidene pure component

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental values of sound of speed, viscosities and densities for the binary mixture E-4-HB with amines at 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K was determined. In addition, thermo acoustic variables of various types were determined by comparing gathered info by using standard relations taken from research. The excess molar volume values are discovered to be positive and low with relation to all binary systems across compositional range at all temperatures. The extra attributes K_s^E and L_f^E are negative for mixture binary over entire range of moles per mole at three degrees. The outcomes

are explicable by breakdown of intra-intermolecular H-bonds of amines and its creation between different components of liquid mixtures. In addition, certain interactions between dipoles may exist in all blends, particularly between OCA and OT, which is confirmed by the higher value of acoustic impedance of the thermo-acoustic function. In addition, the Speed of sound values of impedance relation (U_{IMR}) and Nomoto (U_{NMR}) and reveals merit of concurrence among all the theoretical to measured data. Analysis of the pure solvent and its mixes using FT-IR, assigning the main benzoate and amine bands are also reported. The

shift of main bands supports the formation of new H-bonds between the components of mix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Author Dr. Nagarjuna. A, is thankful to his PDF supervisor Dr. B.M Praveen, Director, Research and innovation Cell, Srinivas University,

Mangalore for his valuable suggestions and discussion.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chinnarao, Dharmana, Ch V. Padmarao, Ch Beena, M. Srilatha, M. V. V. Ramanjaneyulu, Praveen Choppara, N. Murali, and B. Venkateswara Rao. "Acoustic, excess thermodynamical, molecular interaction and anti-microbial activity studies on binary liquid mixtures of geranyl acetate and benzyl benzoate in the temperature range of 303.15 K–318.15 K." *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* 100, no. 5 (2023): 100969.
- [2] Reid, R.C. J.M Prausnitz, and B.E Poling, "The Properties of Gases and Liquids", 4th ed., (McGraw Hill book company, New York) 1987
- [3] Rajagopal, K., and S. Chentilnath. "Excess thermodynamic studies in binary liquid mixtures of 2-methyl-2-propanol with ketones at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K." *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 155, no. 1 (2010): 20-28.
- [4] Kalimulla, T., Shaik Babu, D. Das, M. Gowrisankar, and K. Govinda Rao. "Ultrasonic investigations in binary liquid mixtures of 2-methylcyclohexanone with formamide, n-methyl formamide and n, n-dimethylformamide at different temperatures." *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research* 11, no. 7 (2019): 2645-2655.
- [5] Narasimha Rao, C., S. Ramanaiah, A. Chowdappa, K. Sivakumar, and P. Venkateswarlu. "Thermodynamic and transport properties of binary liquid mixtures of cyclohexanol with isomeric chlorotoluenes." *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids* 53, no. 2 (2015): 264-274.
- [6] Garcia, Begoña, Rafael Alcalde, and José M. Leal. "Excess properties for binary liquid mixtures of propionic acid with aniline derivatives." *Canadian journal of chemistry* 69, no. 3 (1991): 369-372.
- [7] Nagarjuna, A., and Shaik Babu. "Spectroscopic and volumetric study of binary liquid mixtures containing Ethyl-4-hydroxy benzoate and alkanols." *Chemical Data Collections* 26 (2020): 100347.
- [8] Nagarjuna, A., Shaik Babu, and M. Gowrisankar. "Thermo-physical and spectroscopic studies of liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoic acid." *International Journal of Ambient Energy* 43, no. 1 (2022): 1974-1985.
- [9] Chandra Sekhar, M., A. Venkatesulu, M. Gowrisankar, and T. Srinivasa Krishna. "Thermodynamic study of interactions in binary liquid mixtures of 2-Chloroaniline with some carboxylic acids." *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids* 55, no. 2 (2017): 196-217.
- [10] Saini, Neeti, J. S. Yadav, Sunil K. Jangra, Dimple Sharma, and V. K. Sharma. "Thermodynamic studies of molecular interactions in mixtures of o-toulidine with pyridine and picolines: excess molar volumes, excess molar enthalpies, and excess isentropic compressibilities." *The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics* 43, no. 5 (2011): 782-795.
- [11] Siddharthan, N., and S. Jayakumar. "Theoretical evaluation of sound velocity, viscosity and density of binary liquid system." *Int. J. Chem. Sci* 14, no. 4 (2016).
- [12] Sulthana, Shaik Parveen, M. Gowrisankar, Shaik Babu, and Dheiver Santos. "Investigation of ketonic effect in molecular interactions of 2-methylcyclohexanone with aniline, N-methyl aniline and N, N-dimethyl aniline at various temperatures." *International Journal of Ambient Energy* 43, no. 1 (2022): 894-904.

- [13] Thirumaran, S., and J. Ramesh. "Acoustic and excess thermodynamical studies on 1-alkanols with DMA in cyclohexanone at different temperatures." *Rasayan J Chem* 2 (2009): 733-739.
- [14] Awasthi, Aashees, Madhu Rastogi, and J. P. Shukla. "Ultrasonic and IR study of molecular association process through hydrogen bonding in ternary liquid mixtures." *Fluid phase equilibria* 215, no. 2 (2004): 119-127.
- [15] Karunakar, T., and C. H. Srinivas. "Thermo acoustic and infrared study of molecular interactions in binary mixture aniline+ 1-butanol." *Res. Rev.: J. Pure Appl. Phys* 1 (2013): 5-15.
- [16] Shihab, Sk Suriya, Shaik Babu, and S. Sreehari Sastry. "Experimental and theoretical studies of speed of sound and viscosity in some liquid mixtures of Methyl Benzoate: a comparative study." *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry* 9, no. 4 (2016).
- [17] Nomoto, Otohiko "Empirical formula for sound velocity in liquid mixtures." *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* 13, no. 12 (1958): 1528-1532.
- [18] Van Dael, W., and E. Vangeel. "Theory of ultrasound." *Van Deal W. Thermodynamic properties and velocity of sound, London: Butterworth* (1975).
- [19] Junjie, Z. "Calculation of Ultrasonic Velocity in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Benzene." *J. China Univ. Sci. Technol* 14 (1984): 298-299.

Indian Institution of Industrial Engineering

BOMBAY
CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

This is to certify that the article entitled

**SPEED OF SOUND AND VISCOSITY THEORIES OF BENZOATE
LIQUID MIXTURES**

Authored By

A. NAGARJUNA

Department of Physics, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka-574146,
India.

Published in

Industrial Engineering Journal : ISSN 0970-2555

Volume:52, Issue 9, No.9, SEPTEMBER : 2023

UGC Care Approved, Group I, Peer Reviewed Journal

with IF=6.82

Editor in Chief

